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Social Innovation in Marginalised Rural Areas

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Deliverable D5.4

Final Report on Cross-Case Studies Assessment of Social Innovation

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List of Acronyms

AT	Austria
BEPA	Bureau of European Policy Advisers
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CLLD	Community-Led Local Development
CS	Case study
CSA	Community Supported Agriculture
DP	Diverging Path
DPP	Dimensions of divergence paths
EAFRD	European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development
EIP	European Innovation Partnerships
ES	Spain
ESF	European Social Fund
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations
GR	Greece
IA	Innovation action
INFOCAT	Emergency plan for Catalonia
LEADER	Liaison Entre Actions de Développement de l'Économie Rurale
MARHP	Ministry of Agriculture, Water Resources and Fishery
MRA	Marginalised rural Areas
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NL	The Netherlands
NRP	New Regional Policy
OEP	Office of Livestock and Pastures
POT	Perceived opportunities and threats
RDP	Rural Development Programme
SFADF	Secretariat de les Federacions d'Agrupacions de Defensa Forestal
SI	Social innovation
SITT	Social Innovation Think Thank
SK	Slovakia
UK	United Kingdom
UNESCO	The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

Deliverable 5.4 provides a transversal and systematic analysis of the case studies in the SIMRA project using aggregated qualitative and quantitative data based on the relevant social innovation issues and characteristics assessed. The cross-case analysis identifies commonalities and differences across cases in relation to the principal issues and characteristics of social innovation processes in Marginalised Rural Areas and examines complex and situated relationships and interactions.

The cross-case assessment of the main social innovation issues and characteristics was based on the investigation of important trends identified within five cross-cutting themes of enquiry. The first theme of enquiry is into the factors that influence the emergence and development of social innovation in terms of both the context and characteristics of actors. The second theme of enquiry is into the process of reconfiguration and the changes of social practices (e.g. new networks, new government arrangements). The third theme of enquiry concerns the model of social innovation development and the identification of trajectory of divergence. The fourth theme of enquiry is about the impacts of the social innovation on dimensions of territorial capital (economy, society, environment, governance). The fifth theme of enquiry refers to the analysis of policy impacts on social innovation and social innovation policy implications. Each theme of enquiry was assessed, and the interactions across themes, to understanding the cases, their contexts, and their territorial impacts.

The process of transversal and systematic analysis relies on both qualitative (semi-structured interviews) and quantitative data (structured interviews, indicators, and social network analysis) retrieved from the individual Case Study Reports. The Reports contain both descriptive results and quantitative evaluation, which were used jointly in this deliverable to provide a comprehensive understanding of the multi-dimensional characteristics of social innovation initiatives.

The approach used for the cross-case analysis of social innovation initiatives is based on a standardised structure following a model used for the scientific papers. Each theme of enquiry has been analysed by sets of authors who are in project partners contributing to the activity of Task 5.4. The most appropriate approach has been selected for the cross-case analysis for each topic (e.g. conceptual and analytical framework, assessment, data interpretation and presentation of important findings, cross-case observations) with respect to the relevant dimensions identified in the SIMRA theoretical framework and in line the SIMRA definition of Social Innovation. Limitations of methodologies is also been discussed.

In addition to the analysis undertaken for each theme of enquiry, composite indicators were calculated which were based upon the methodology developed in Secco *et al.* (2019; D4.3) to better understand Social Innovation in Marginalised Rural Areas on a large scale. The aim of the standardised structure is to streamline the process of producing peer-reviewed publications from each Section of this Deliverable.

The cross-case findings have been used to prepare recommendations on factors linked to the success and failure of social innovation initiatives in relation to impacts of policies or on policies, and subsequent use in Work Package 6.

1. Introduction

1.1 Rationale and Objectives of the Deliverable

The main objective of Deliverable 5.4. is to perform a cross-case analysis of the eleven SIMRA Case Studies (Type A) of Social innovation (SI) emerging in Europe and in the Mediterranean basin in Marginalised Rural Areas (MRAs). The cross-case analysis aimed at a transversal and systematic investigation of the cases of social innovation and the identification of patterns of similarities, differences, weaknesses and strengths across them.

Five main aspects are investigated: influencing factors that support or hinder social innovation in specific contexts; the hypothesis of diverging paths / models of development; the process of reconfiguration of social practices; impacts of social innovation on the four dimensions of territorial capital (society, economy, environment and governance); and policy impacts on, and policy implications of, social innovation.

The cross-case analysis is based on empirical evidence collected from the eleven cases (Type A) selected in Work Package 3 (Valero et al., D3.3) and analysed in Work Package 5 (Górriz-Mifsud et al., 2018, D5.1; Govigli et al., D5.3), using the theoretical framework developed in Work Package 2 (Klůvanková et al. 2017; D2.2; Klůvanková et al. 2020), the evaluation framework developed in Work Package 4 (Secco et al., 2017, D4.2;), and the broader governance framework conditions developed in Working Packages 6 (Ludvig et al., 2017, D6.1).

Information retrieved from the analysis of Types B and C Case Studies will be used to confirm general trends and support key findings. The results of the analyses of the cases (Types A, B and C) are reported in the "Individual Case Study Reports" which are kept restricted and confidential to project partners due to the sensitivity of the information contained therein, to protect the anonymity of participants and certain data, and to avoid compromising the publication of scientific findings and intellectual property.

The findings of the cross-case analysis presented in Deliverable 5.4 serves to derive and prepare recommendations on factors linked to the success and failure of social innovation in marginalised rural areas. They will be used in Work Package 6 to write guidelines and recommendations for target groups, regional stakeholders and policy markets. In addition, the report provides critical considerations on methodological limitations and potentials in terms of comparability and generalisations of the set of methods for the assessment of social innovation in marginalised rural areas in agriculture, forestry and rural development, as proposed by Work Package 4 in SIMRA.

1.2 Scope of the Document

The scope of Deliverable 5.4 is to present the cross-case analysis on success factors and failures related to social innovation initiatives in marginalised rural areas that resulted from juxtaposing and comparing empirical information collected from the eleven Type A Case Studies analysed in Task 5.3. The report seeks to provide a thorough and aggregate perspective of two main aspects: the factors that constrain and facilitate the emergence and development of the Social Innovations, and the effects of Social Innovations at the territorial level (on economy, society, environment, and governance). These two aspects are linked to the two general SIMRA research questions outlined in Górriz-Mifsud *et al.* (2018; D5.1):

1. **Input-oriented questions:** What factors have affected the development of the Social Innovation? What were the constraining and facilitating factors, including context, agents and policy questions?
2. **Output-oriented questions:** What are the effects of the Social Innovation (evaluated in the four dimensions of social, economic, governance and environment)?

By understanding these processes, factors and characteristics of social innovation through empirical cases, this report provides information on which conditions enable the emergence of social innovation in marginalised rural areas, providing insights into how to implement similar initiatives outside of the those of SIMRA activities.

1.3 Structure of the Document

This report consists of eleven sections. The sections are structured using the format of a scientific paper and organised as follows: Introduction, Methods, Results, Discussion, Cross-case assumptions, and References. The sections can be treated as stand-alone but contribute to the derivation of general recommendations on the factors of links to success and failure of social innovation (Section 10).

Section 2 conceptualises the approach for cross-case analysis of Social Innovation in Marginalised Rural Areas. Section 3 evaluates the overall validity of the methodological approach developed in Work Package 4 for the analysis of social innovation in the selected SIMRA case studies. Section 4 analyses the factors influencing the development of social innovations. Section 5 reports on a cross-case analysis based on the reconfiguration of social practices, providing information on new networks, governance arrangements, and social practices. Section 6 checks the hypothesis of diverging paths and explanatory models of social innovation development. Section 7 carries out a cross-case investigation of the impacts of social innovation on territorial dimensions. Section 8 identifies the supporting and hindering policies that influence social innovation. Section 9 reports on the overall main findings and holistic understanding of social innovation initiatives. The report ends with the principal feedback from the SIMRA Social Innovation Think Tank Workshop held in Aberdeen, UK, October 2019, and recommendations for social innovation success (Section 10).

2. Approach to Cross-Case Analysis

Authors: Elisa Ravazzoli and Cristina Dalla Torre

2.1 Introduction

Cross-case analysis is a term widely used to refer to a method to summarise, integrate, combine and compare the findings of two or more Case Studies on a specific topic or research question that aims to produce a synthesised outcome. It is a proxy term for research synthesis (Cruzes and Dybå, 2011). There are several techniques available for cross-case analysis (Khan and VanWynsberghe, 2008). In this report, cross-case analysis is a method to synthesise a body of knowledge/evidence from empirical analyses of different individual Case Studies to explore and compare similarities and differences as well as causal relationships across the cases.

The final aim of the cross-case analysis is to use the empirical evidence from multiple cases to form a generalised explanation of the phenomena under study and to support empirical generalisation. This method goes beyond the limits of the empirical findings of the individual studies, no matter how well designed and executed they may be, to the extent to which they may be useful for generalisation (Cruzes and Dybå, 2011). Compared to the examination of single case studies, the analysis of multiple case studies has the potential to produce compelling interpretations with enhanced external validity, i.e. the validity of applying findings of a scientific study outside the context of that study and generalising the results to and across other situations in time and space. In any discipline, field or sector scientific advancement depends on the accumulation of knowledge from various aspects of a phenomenon. Hence, by extending the overall evidence base beyond the single case, cross-case analysis is a suitable approach for integrating and providing new interpretative explanations. It enables the combination of factors that have contributed to achieving certain outcomes, helps to construct explanations as to why one case differs from others, and enhances understanding of how relationships may exist among individual cases (Ragin, 1997). Furthermore, cross-case analysis allows the comparison of cases from one or more settings, communities, or groups, providing opportunities to learn from different cases and to gather critical evidence to modify policy.

In this deliverable, by comparing information from SIMRA Case Studies that are characterised by a high degree of heterogeneity, knowledge will be advanced in the understanding of social innovation and innovative governance mechanisms and how to boost them. This knowledge will be insight to marginalised rural areas, of which scientific evidence of the enabling conditions, supporting factors, and impacts of social innovation are incomplete.

2.2 General Approach

Carrying out a cross-case analysis is a complex task. It requires a comprehensive understanding of the characteristics of each individual case, specifying *how*, *where*, and *why* it carries on as it does, and understanding processes and outcomes with attention paid to how they are qualified by local context. It entails organising and presenting the relevant evidence extracted from the main sources in such a way that it is possible to make patterns and relationships visible within and across cases, identifying potential causal links (i.e. factors that led to specific outcomes). Finally, it requires building a general explanation which brings together the main findings, and which fits each of the individual cases, even although the cases will vary in their details (Yin 2013, p. 112). In performing the cross-case analysis, it is necessary to take into account the flexible nature of the cases being selected, the mixed (qualitative and quantitative) methods used to perform the analysis, the approach used to analyse the empirical information, and the heterogeneous character of the data which reflect the structure of the project (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Connection of Deliverable D5.4 with other Working Packages and Tasks. (Source: Section authors).

The procedure used to analyse social innovation across the SIMRA Case Studies is characterized by three concurrent flows of activities (Figure 2).

The first activity is characterised by identifying the main themes of enquiry to cross-analyse (e.g. factors influencing social innovation, hypothesis of diverging paths) and their specific features; as well as by acquiring in-depth knowledge of individual cases in relation to the features that characterise the selected themes of enquiry. An evaluation of the overall validity of the methodological approach used to analyse social innovation in marginalised rural areas is provided in Section 3.

The second activity consists of performing the cross-case analysis within the selected themes of enquiry (from Sections 4 to 8). For each theme of enquiry, it is necessary to follow a research approach, run the cross-case analysis, and interpret the findings, which means to (in detail):

- Develop a conceptual and analytical framework necessary for the cross-analysis of the cases for each theme of enquiry, which is consistent with the SIMRA theoretical framework developed in Work Package 2 (Klůvánková *et al.*, 2017; D2.2) and the SIMRA evaluation framework developed in Work Package 4 (Secco *et al.*, 2017; D4.2).
- Perform the cross-case analysis using the evidence from the assessment of social innovation in the individual cases for each theme of enquiry. Given the indicators have been improved from the initial list employed by the case study teams when collecting and analysing data at the case study level, the equivalence between “old” (used in the Data Collection Tools, Report 5.1, and in the Case Study analyses, Report 5.4) and “new” (i.e. in Deliverable 4.3) is presented in the relevant sections.
- Interpret the data and present the important findings for each theme of enquiry, identifying similarities and differences across the cases that enable the interpretation of the phenomenon under study. Findings are based on Case Study Type A. In addition, SIMRA partners EFI and EURAC contrasted the main findings with those of case studies B and C, including the supporting references where appropriate along the different chapters. Some of the main findings will be context-bound, while for others, generalisation will be possible.

- Make cross-case assertions about the theme of enquiry after the cross-case analysis. These assertions will take evidence from the cases to show how similarities and differences characterise the theme of enquiry, and they will explore causal relationships and common mechanisms across the cases.

The final activity consists of calculating composite indicators for the theme of enquiry and to show interesting relationships across the cases and themes with the aim of providing a better understanding of social innovation initiatives in marginalised rural areas (Section 9); and of extrapolating patterns of success factors that can be transferred to new marginalised rural settings, also based upon the results and feedback received during the Stakeholder Workshop held in Aberdeen in October 2019 (Section 10).

Figure 2. Diagram showing general approach for cross-case analysis. (Source: authors of the deliverable).

The guiding principles of the cross-case analysis are:

- i) to compare the heterogeneity of the cases primarily by identifying common mechanisms and not by looking for correlations between variables,
- ii) to identify commonalities and differences to discover whether similar mechanisms and processes drive changes in divergent situations,
- iii) to provide insights on what has worked in the cases which can then be replicated elsewhere and what has not worked, and what has influenced the emergence and development of social innovation and the achievement of positive impacts.

2.3 Selected Themes of Enquiry for Cross-case Analysis

The scope of the cross-case analysis is to identify patterns (similarities, differences, weaknesses, strengths) and the common mechanism of social innovation across case studies. The analysis has not been structured according to topics of case studies (e.g. agriculture, forestry, rural development) because the cases are very diverse (e.g. context, process of development, impacts) rendering such clustering of limited value.

To investigate the process of social innovation across the cases, five themes of enquiry were identified:

- The factors that hinder or enable the emergence and the development of social innovation in terms of both context and characteristics of actors. The factors, elements or features are: triggers, needs, context (availability/lack of resources, perceived opportunities and threats), agency (ideas, values, leadership, motivation, networks, knowledge) and policies that positively and/or negatively supported social innovation. The main research question to

answer is: *What were the common constraining and facilitating factors across the case study (CS) that have influenced the development of the social innovation?*

- The process of reconfiguration and the changes of social practices (the “new rules of the social game”) which are represented by governance arrangements, networks, and attitudes. The main research question to answer is: *What characterizes the process of reconfiguring social practices?*
- The model of social innovation development and the identification of trajectories of divergence. This includes an investigation of key factors or features such as type of actors and knowledge, viability, depth of change as developed in the Working Packages 2 and 3. The main research question is: *How have cases with similar Social Innovation constraining and facilitating factors developed different diverging paths?*
- The impacts or effects of the social innovation at the territorial level and the investigation of the effects (negative and positive, long-term, in a widespread manner) of social innovation on society, economy, environment, and institutional governance. The main research question is: *What are the common effects across cases of social innovation in terms of social, economic, governance, and environmental impacts?*
- Policy under three considerations: i) policy impacts on social innovations, which provide financial support, information, networking and regulatory tools; ii) policy implications in terms of the formulation, transformation, or abandonment of policies based on activities or experiences with social innovation initiatives; iii) the neutral role of policy in influencing social innovation (Ludvig *et al.*, 2018; D6.2). The main research question is: *Which policies commonly support or hinder Social Innovation? What are the impacts of Social Innovation on policies? How do they interrelate?*

The themes of enquiry for the cross-case analysis of social innovation initiatives have been selected to be consistent with the main components of social innovation as defined in the Conceptual Framework developed in Work Package 4 (Secco *et al.*, 2017; D4.2), based on the theoretical framework developed in Work Package 2 (Klůvanková *et al.*, 2017; D2.2) as shown in **Figure 3**. They also link to the theoretical model on dimensions of divergence developed within Work Packages 2 and 3 and to the analysis of policy impacts and implications conducted in Work Package 6 (Ludvig *et al.*, 2018; D6.2).

Figure 3. SIMRA framework for the evaluation of Social Innovation and its impacts in Marginalised Rural Areas. (Source: Secco *et al.*, 2017; D4.2: 36).

2.4 Data Retrieval and Method for Cross-Case Analysis

The cross-case examinations within each theme of enquiry are based on the qualitative and quantitative assessments of social innovation in the eleven Type A Case Studies undertaken in Task 5.3. Only the assessments performed for Type A Case Studies are used because they applied the full methodology. The analysis performed in Types B and C Case Studies were used to consolidate findings, confirm general trends and add value to existing interpretations. They were not considered in the cross-case assessment because they did not apply the full SIMRA methodology and cannot explain patterns within each theme.

As described in Gorriz-Mifsud *et al.*, 2018 (D5.1, p. 6, Table 1), for Types B and C case studies it was not compulsory to apply all the quantitative data collection tools (4 to 6) and the semi-structured interview with a policy expert (Tool 8). For Type B cases, only structured and semi-structured interview Tools (3 and 7) with the innovator, and running a Focus Group (Tool 2), were compulsory. For Type C cases, only the semi-structured interview with the innovator (Tool 7) and the Focus Group (Tool 2) were compulsory.

The assessment of individual cases was based on a triangulation between qualitative and quantitative data which enables the application of a mixed methods analysis. The social innovation assessments are reported in Individual Case Study Reports which contain the empirical analysis for all the SIMRA Case Studies (Types A, B, and C). The Individual Case Study Reports are stored in the SIMRA intranet in the relative case study folders. A list of the case studies on which the cross-case analysis is based and an overview of some of their characteristics are provided in Table 1. For a synthesis of the individual

case study, refer to Gorriz-Mifsud *et al.*, 2018 (D5.1); for information on the case studies, refer to the dedicated SIMRA Webpage (www.simra-h2020.eu/index.php/simra-case-studies/).

Table 1. Case Study categorisation, characteristics and reference source.

Category	Case Study and brief description	Location	Acronym	Source
A	Forest Defence Groups <i>Integration of volunteer-based institution for wildfire prevention within the regional wildfire prevention and suppression scheme in Catalonia.</i>	Spain	ADF	Rodríguez Fernández-Blanco <i>et al.</i> , 2019: R5.4.a
A	Lohcarron Community Development Co <i>Community involvement in decision making processes on woodland ownership and its strategic management for local development.</i>	United Kingdom	LAG	Barlagne <i>et al.</i> , 2019: R5.4.j
A	Noidanlukko Co-operative <i>Grassroots network and platform for documenting, communicating and sharing knowledge on environmental issues and human-nature relationships, especially concerning nuclear power and other mega projects planned in the area.</i>	Finland	FIN	Melnykovich and Sarkki, 2019: R5.4.e
A	Pro Val Lumnezia <i>Collaborative bottom-up process among the local industry association and all municipalities of the valley for the strategic development of the area.</i>	Switzerland	LUM	Marini Govigli <i>et al.</i> , 2019: R5.4.b
A	Revitalising plans for Vlkolinec <i>Reconstruction of historic landscape structures and features via the revival of traditional farming approaches and a participatory approach.</i>	Slovakia	REV	Melnykovich <i>et al.</i> , 2019: R5.4.k
A	Hawaruhof <i>Rearrangement of a farm into a producer-led community supported agriculture farm.</i>	Austria	HAW	Melnykovich <i>et al.</i> , 2019: R5.4.f
A	Learning growing living with women farmers social co-operative <i>Women farmer co-operative offering delocalized childcare service provision on the farms.</i>	Italy	WOM	Dalla Torre <i>et al.</i> , 2019: R5.4.d
A	Dairy producer's public-private partnership <i>Transferring extension and milk control activities from national institutions to Producers Organizations.</i>	Tunisia	DAI	Melnykovich <i>et al.</i> 2019: R5.4.h
A	VàZapp' <i>Rural hub promoting careers opportunities for young people seeking to rejuvenating farmer entrepreneurship and create new business models.</i>	Italy	VAZ	Marini Govigli <i>et al.</i> , 2019: R5.4.g
A	A box of sea <i>Creation of a fairer market that protects the marine environment, supports small fishing communities and provides better information to consumers regarding seafood.</i>	Greece	SEA	Marini Govigli <i>et al.</i> , 2019: R5.4.i
A	Green care farm <i>Rearrangement of a farm into a green care farm targeting people with disabilities.</i>	The Netherlands	CAR	Dijkshoorn <i>et al.</i> , 2019: R5.4.c
B	Carbon smart forestry in forest commons in Ajdovščina	Slovenia	SKC	

	<i>Comparing the implementation of Carbon forestry in two rural communities, with adaptive capacity.</i>			Brnkalakova et al., 2019: R5.4.n
B	Carbon smart forestry in forest commons in Nízke Tatry <i>Comparing the implementation of Carbon forestry in two rural communities, with disturbances in adaptive capacity.</i>	Slovakia	SLC	
B	Agroforestry in Guadeloupe <i>Association of vanilla farmers leading a project for diversifying and increasing their productivity by engaging in agroforestry practices.</i>	France	GUA	Barlagne et al., 2019: R5.4.s
B	Réseau Urbain Neuchâtelois <i>Public-private partnership based on a regional contract grouping 11 municipalities of the Val-de-Travers region and 11 local companies active in micro-technology aiming at local development.</i>	Switzerland	FLE	Marini Govigli et al., 2019 R5.4.l
B	Herenboeren <i>The first community supported agriculture initiative in The Netherlands</i>	The Netherlands	HER	Polman et al., 2019 R5.4.m
B	Forum Nazionale Agricoltura Sociale <i>Platform for the exchange and promotion of Social Farming experiences in Italy.</i>	Italy	FAS	Dalla Torre et al., 2019 R5.4.r
B	Braemar Community Hydro Co-operative <i>Community energy scheme based on hydro-power production</i>	United Kingdom	BRA	Slee, 2019. R5.4.q
C	Huntly district Development trust <i>Community energy scheme based on wind-power production</i>		HUN	
C	Argan co-operative of rural women <i>Rural women's cooperative aiming to improve the livelihoods of rural women via the valorisation and commercialization of argan oil.</i>	Morocco	ARG	Chorti et al., 2019 R5.4.o
C	Non wood forest product (NWFP) <i>Project aiming at promoting NWFP micro-enterprises for improving the livelihoods of forest communities and contributing to the sustainable management of forestry resources in Tunisia.</i>	Tunisia	NWF	Labidi et al., 2019 R5.4.p
C	CRES-Vidovici - Adriatic coast: Resilience of Rural Island's <i>Project of touristic valorization of an island village through re-migration processes.</i>	Croatia	CRO	Klúvanková et al., 2019 R5.4.t
C	Environment Friendly Villages Network – ElBehera Governorate <i>Establishment of a local waste management system including municipal infrastructure and training programmes in school.</i>	Egypt	VIL	Nawar and Marini Govigli, 2019. R5.4.u

(Source: Section authors).

For the cross-case analysis of all the themes of enquiry, both qualitative information and quantitative data (i.e. indicators) on social innovation assessment were used from the Individual Case Study

Reports. These serve to both describe and interpret the cases using case narratives, and to perform a cross-case comparison across the SIMRA cases.

Primarily, the indicators were used to calculate a descriptive statistic (minimum, maximum, mean). The indicators used to describe the social innovation processes and projects in each dimension have been compiled using the results from the Focus Group (Tool 2), the structured interviews with the social innovation actors (Tools 3 to 6), and additional information collected by the evaluator in Tool 1 (i.e. the budget of the initiative and the census of social innovation actors). These indicators have been used in conjunction with qualitative information (Tools 7, 8) to triangulate the findings (Secco *et al.*, 2019; D4.3).

The use of a quantitative indicator enables to summarise several aspects of social innovation for which it was created. In the SIMRA project, indicators with various ranges were proposed, based on the type of data collected. The normalization of these indicators makes it possible to compare them by adopting the same range [0 to 1] and to aggregate them (OECD, 2008) in composite indicators with the techniques described before. For this reason, the Min-Max (with respect the indicator range) normalisation approach has been adopted. , as described before. Some indicators for which many Case Studies have reported missing values (NA), have been treated with caution while making comparisons. However, overall, they provide insights for the themes of enquiry. A full list of indicators and normalised values is provided in **Appendix 2**.

3. Evaluation of the Overall Validity of the Methodological Approach

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3.1 Introduction

Deliverable 4.3 (Secco *et al.*, 2019) presents the refined, final version of the SIMRA Evaluation Framework and the innovative set of methods for the evaluation of Social Innovation in Marginalised Rural Areas and its impacts. The Evaluation Framework is based on the SIMRA definition of social innovation and has been adjusted after its initial application in two pioneer Case Studies and eleven Type A case studies. The definition and the Evaluation Framework enabled an understanding to be gained of the essential dimensions and sub-dimensions of social innovation by specifying the multi-dimensional and dynamic features of the complex phenomenon considered. In the set of methods for evaluation Secco *et al.* (2019; D4.3) took into consideration: i) the different elements of evaluation, with their implications for the practice of evaluation, such as geographical and temporal scales, actors involved in the various stages (i.e. the social innovation process phase, project phase, and the overall initiative that includes both process and project); ii) possible evaluation users with their specific needs; iii) possible focuses of the evaluation based on the criteria chosen case by case.

Taking all these issues into consideration, the overall SIMRA Evaluation Approach proposes four options for designing and carrying out the evaluation of social innovation in marginalised rural areas (Deliverable 4.3, Section 4):

- (i) SIMRA Rapid Evaluation, which focuses on the core concepts of the SIMRA definition of social innovation;
- (ii) SIMRA Detailed Evaluation, which focuses on dimensions and sub-dimensions of social innovation as proposed in the SIMRA Evaluation Framework;
- (iii) SIMRA Conventional Evaluation, which is based on the criteria of relevance, efficiency, effectiveness, impact and sustainability (REEIS) analysed for both the social innovation process and the project;
- (iv) Potential *ad hoc* combinations of options (i) to (iii), based on the specific needs of the evaluator and the specific evaluation objectives.

Both quantitative and qualitative tools are suggested to be used, the results of which can be integrated and triangulated. The elements needed to implement the evaluation are included and fully described in Secco *et al.* (2019; D4.3).

The process of progressively refining and optimising the innovative set of methods of evaluation was lengthy and complex. From an initial, preliminary set of questions and questionnaires (tested in the two pioneer case studies), Work Package 4 developed an advanced set of tools for data collection and for the calculation and interpretation of indicators (used in the eleven Type A case studies). The final set of tools for data collection, data entry, data processing, analysing, and reporting was completed, taking into consideration all the methodological weaknesses and limitations, as well as the conceptual complexities or inconsistencies, which emerged during the empirical testing carried out in the case studies.

Therefore, in this Section, the limitations of the SIMRA Evaluation Approach and of the innovative set of methods used for the evaluation of the social innovation cases are only presented in brief. The first part presents the methodological limitations in terms of the comparability of results amongst Case Studies, and generalisations of findings that are based on the eleven Type A Case Studies evaluated in the SIMRA project. The second part focuses on the potential and the limitations of the set of different tools proposed within the SIMRA Evaluation Approach based on the evidence provided by their application in the two pioneer cases and the eleven Type A case studies. The third part describes the

potential and limitations of the indicators proposed based on feedback received, and by considering the findings with the triangulation process performed on the comparison between qualitative and quantitative outputs.

The evidence presented in this Section is based on the feedback received, mainly, from the case study teams through Tool 11. Additional feedback from the Case Studies was collected during the full project partner meeting, Padova, Italy, June 2018. The leaders of Work Package 5 also provided information being responsible for the development of the qualitative and quantitative data in each case study, and the consequent triangulation and reporting of results. Feedback received by Work Package 5 has been structured into three different groups (see Deliverable 4.3):

- (i) **Questions and questionnaires**, based on the information received through Tool 11, as completed by the different case study teams¹;
- (ii) **Indicators**, based on the evidence that emerged during the data entry and development process (e.g. computations), as well as the reliability of the findings or outputs obtained as indicated by the feedback from the Work Package 5 leader;
- (iii) **Comparison and triangulation between qualitative and quantitative outputs** collected using the different tools, based on the analysis performed in collaboration with Work Packages 4, 5 and 6.

Secco *et al.* (2019; D4.3), in its first part provides clarification of the most relevant criticisms that emerged in relation to questions and questionnaires, indicators, and triangulation, and explains how these have been considered by Work Package 4 in the process of progressively improving the evaluation approach and method. Therefore, this Section is intended to add to the understanding of some of the key points mentioned in Deliverable 4.3.

3.2 Methodological Limitations in Terms of Comparability

Reflecting on the limitations of the evaluation method proposed, it is essential to provide evidence of criticisms in relation to: (i) setting the “boundaries of the evaluation”; (ii) aspects of the “quantitative method proposed”. These issues could limit the choices of comparability. Specific options are proposed in relation to normalisation, weighting, and the aggregation of composite indicators later in this section.

Secco *et al.* (2019; D4.3) identified limitations associated with different phases of social innovation noting that, in certain circumstances (i.e. when multiple processes and projects characterise a social innovation initiative), it is not simple to distinguish between the phases identified as “the social innovation process” and “the social innovation project”. So, some project activities could simultaneously also be preliminary process actions for a new project within the same social innovation initiative. When the social innovation initiative develops multiple projects, it might be difficult to carry out the evaluation, due to difficulties in clearly identify which actors were involved in which projects, how resources were allocated to the various projects, and which benefits are specifically derived from one project instead of another. It might also be difficult to have a clear picture of how the budget is distributed between the various projects. Moreover, as seen in the empirical cases, the development of a social innovation initiative is not linear, and repeated reverse loops can occur.

Thus, the evaluator should be aware that in the real evaluation practice, the specific conditions of the social innovation initiative under evaluation could be more complicated compared to those identified in the SIMRA Evaluation Framework. Consequently, the evaluator should adapt the focus of evaluation by disentangling the specific elements of the process and project(s) to be evaluated and by making clear whether some project activities are part of a new process or not, and what is/are the project(s)

¹ Note, in the final SIMRA Manual for the Evaluation of Social Innovation (second part of Deliverable 4.3), Tool 11 now has a different title and purpose.

specifically included in the evaluation. In particular, when the “threshold” between the social innovation process and the social innovation project(s) is not clearly identifiable, the evaluator should force the choice (i.e. take a decision on where to set the boundaries and split the initiative into its two phases, process and project) and explain it to all of the interviewees. The timeline exercise proposed within the first part of Tool 2 is intended to help the evaluator clarify this issue and identify the correct threshold between process and project(s). It is difficult to include the reverse, non-linear loops that may occur in the temporal development of a real social innovation initiative in the quantitative evaluation. So, they are described qualitatively.

Concerning the quantitative method proposed, it is essential to recall that the construction of a composite indicator requires the following steps (OECD, 2008):

- (i) definition of a theoretical framework for the selection of variables;
- (ii) selection of data based on indicators that are already available (or definition of new data to be collected);
- (iii) imputation of missing data in order to provide a complete dataset;
- (iv) multivariate analysis to study the overall structure of the dataset and guide the subsequent choices in terms of normalisation, weighting, and aggregation;
- (v) normalisation of indicators;
- (vi) weighting and aggregation.

The design of the SIMRA methodology followed all of these steps in relation to the four options mentioned (SIMRA Rapid, Detailed, and Conventional evaluations, or ad hoc combinations), with some necessary adaptations due to the specifics of the phenomenon analysed. The SIMRA project used for a case study analysis, with in-depth analysis of eleven examples of social innovation initiatives selected across Europe, North Africa, and the Eastern Mediterranean. This choice limits the possible comparability of results of the different case studies as they are located within very different social, institutional, and economic contexts. An additional limitation is due to all of the initiatives referring to the broad concepts of agriculture, forestry, and rural development. However, they are *de facto* spread across very diverse settings and sectors such as social farming to sustainable energy solutions, a rural social movement against nuclear infrastructure, and volunteer groups for preventing forest wildfires.

The absence of secondary data available for several key aspects of the social innovations required the definition of new, primary data to be collected. The limited number of case studies, together with the relatively limited number of actors typically involved in these initiatives (which ordinarily occur at a local level and often are in initial phases of development, thus involving few people and organisations), reduced the total amount of data available and limited the scope for carrying out a reliable multivariate analysis. The small number of cases analysed reduced the possibility of comparing the quantitative results statistically, and thus the type of conclusions which can be drawn.

The SIMRA Evaluation Approach started with the development of a theoretical evaluation framework for the selection of key variables, then to the data collection, both primary and secondary, for the construction of the dataset of qualitative and quantitative variables. In relation to the quantitative variables, a database of indicators was developed (see Technical Annex of the SIMRA Manual for the evaluation of social innovation included in Deliverable 4.3). Whereas the methodology for developing composite indicators normally requires implementing a multivariate analysis of the dataset to understand the underlying structure of the data, which is required for providing evidence if some composite indicators have reduced information compared to others. This analysis can be performed by using Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Factor Analysis (FA), or Cronbach Coefficient Alpha.

In the case of the SIMRA methodology, a descriptive comparison of the quantitative and qualitative results was used. Differently from OECD's suggested steps (OECD 2008), a multivariate analysis to check the robustness of the composite indicators has not been performed because the sample of

eleven Type A Case Studies was small compared to the number of variables and related indicators. Consequently, the results would not present known statistical properties.

Focusing on the normalisation, in SIMRA different normalisation approaches have been proposed, as usually suggested in the scientific literature (Min-Max with respect to the indicator range, Min-Max with respect to the data collected, categorical scales, and indicators above or below the mean). These were tested. The small number of cases on which they have been calculated did not permit checks on their reliability of the majority of these normalization approaches. Therefore, a Min-max with respect to the indicator range has been adopted, which allows the same range of values (0 to 1) to be used for all indicators. This is calculated by subtracting the minimum value of the indicator and dividing the result by the range of the indicator considered.

Nevertheless, the evaluator should consider different normalisation options and then choose the one which best fits the specific features of the dataset of indicators and composite indicators computed for the specific case of social innovation under evaluation. Examples of other methods of normalisation are standardisation (or z-scores), distance to a reference country (if this is possible based on the type of evaluation considered), categorical scales, min-max with respect to the data collected (and not the indicator range), and indicators above or below the mean.

Concerning the weighting, the equal weighting (EW) of indicators was chosen (i.e. all are given the same weight). This choice could have associated risks of inserting an element of double counting into the computation of a composite indicator through the combination of variables with a high degree of correlation. Thus, practice suggests computing the Pearson correlation coefficient in order to choose indicators with a low degree of correlation or to adjust their weight by considering this correcting factor. In this analysis, the issue is highlighted but not to select or adjust the composite indicators because the number of the limited number of Case Studies.

The evaluator can choose this option if the number of cases observed are sufficient. An alternative option could be to give the same weight to sub-dimensions, so that each indicator has a different weight based on the number of indicators used to describe each sub-dimension. This option could be a good solution if the evaluator chooses to create an ad hoc combination of indicators. Another strategy to weight indicators is to use participatory methods that incorporate the opinions of stakeholders such as experts, citizens and politicians. This strategy works well when applied in a national context with a clear national policy on the topic. When the topic is new in policy terms and the national contexts are multiple or different, then this weighting approach could lead to questionable results. So, it was not implemented in this project.

Regarding the aggregation of composite indicators, in SIMRA a linear (or additive) aggregation method, which requires the computation of the average values of the indicators, is used because all the indicators have the same measurement unit (0 to 1). The decisive element underpinning this choice is its simplicity. However, the linear aggregation entails restrictions in the interpretation of the weighting (if they exist). Moreover, the method requires that there be no conflict or synergy amongst indicators, as they must be independent. Other option which could be considered are geometric and non-compensatory multi-criteria approaches. For additional information, the evaluator can refer to OECD (2008; p.33).

3.3 Potential and Limitations of the Set of Tools

This section presents: i) a brief overview of the tools used for data collection, data entry and data processing; and ii) comments on the criticisms made during implementation of the tools, and how they were addressed in successive revisions until the final set which was included in Deliverable 4.3 (Secco *et al.*, 2019).

The final evaluation method used in SIMRA comprises a set of tools for data collection. Tool 1 is devoted to preparing the evaluation and in two parts. In part 1, called the “desk phase”, the evaluator

is required to analyse all the documents related to the social innovation project(s) to gather specific information needed to structure the initial steps of the evaluation. In part two, the evaluator collects specific information, verifies the information already collected, and clarifies specific elements (e.g. costs, contributions, sources of funding, number of beneficiaries) through a structured interview with the project manager of the initiative.

Tool 2 is based on a group interview and comprises two parts characterised by two different techniques for data collection. Part one is an *ad hoc* future search conference needed to explore the history, actors, and context of where the social innovation took place. Part two is a Focus Group to gain insight to the changes in the context and the impacts determined by the social innovation initiative.

Tools 3 to 6 are structured questionnaires with various targets: Tool 3, the core group of the innovator(s) and follower(s); Tool 4, the social innovation network (i.e. the transformers as well as the innovators and followers not interviewed with Tool 3); Tool 5, the project partners involved in the social innovation project; and Tool 6, a selected sample of the beneficiaries of the initiative. All of the Tools 3 to 6 pose questions in relation to the five parts of the social innovation: reflection, reaction, reconfiguring, realisation, and replication.

Two tools have been developed for the qualitative assessment: Tool 7 is the interview guideline for innovators and key people involved in the social innovation, and Tool 8 is the interview guideline for policy experts. These last two tools focus on the same dimensions of the social innovation as identified in the SIMRA evaluation framework for the quantitative evaluation, exploring them from a qualitative perspective and proposing the use of the content analysis technique for finding and interpreting results.

The Work Package 4 research team designed the tools in a way that assures their flexible use in different local contexts and topics or sectors of intervention. Evaluators should use only those tools which satisfy their specific evaluation needs (see Section 4 of the Manual included in Deliverable 4.3 for further details). They can reduce the length of the questionnaires by keeping only the questions that are needed to calculate the selected indicators. The limitations to the initial version of the data collection tools applied by the case study teams were aggregated into: (i) general comments and (ii) specific comments (on Tools 2 through 8).

Most of the general comments refer to Tool 2. This tool structures the entire evaluation process, setting the basic concepts (process, project and initiative, and the SIMRA terminology developed for each dimension of social innovation), and identifying the key actors of the social innovation initiative (innovators, followers, transformers, project partners, project managers, and beneficiaries). The application of the new concepts proposed in the SIMRA Evaluation Framework to real contexts was time-consuming and required adaptations and progressive refinement. Consequently, adaptations of Tool 2 drew on the experience of using the approach, the heterogeneity of each group of stakeholders participating and their different capacities and motivations, and the range of specific issues across the cases. To facilitate the implementers of the data collection tool and increase standardisation across the case studies, Work Packages 4 and 5 developed *ad hoc* frequently asked questions (FAQs) that help each case study team to understand the concepts and questions and how to deal with case-specific issues. An excerpt of the FAQs for Tool 2 is provided in **Figure 4**.

As additional supporting material, Work Package 4 developed a short video of the SIMRA Evaluation Approach, published on YouTube (www.youtube.com/watch?v=qCfeLxX6I7c), to facilitate the understanding of key concepts and their interrelations. The video was also intended for communicative purposes towards the stakeholders of each case study. However, it is recognised that a new framework is difficult to understand in a short time, and the video was provided only in English.

Further critical elements identified by the case study teams from information gathered through the other data collection tools were: (i) the time required for the data collection and the application of the

full methodological approach with different stakeholders; (ii) the logical sequence, or order followed, of the questions in the questionnaire; (iii) the perception of repetition of questions in different parts of the questionnaire.

Criticisms by the respondents of elements of the process of gathering data using the other tools were: (i) difficulties in the identification of the social innovation process and project due to a lack of a clear-cut distinction between the two phases; (ii) reservations towards providing economic data due to strategic and privacy reasons; and (iii) difficulties in the identification of the impacts created by the social innovation.

Other comments on more general aspects of the tools, indicators, and the evaluation framework focused were in relation to:

- the use of the Likert Scale range of 1 to 10, which was considered not to be easy to use in all contexts²;
- the long-term social innovation initiative due to some social innovation network actors no longer being part of the project.

All of these comments, and the other feedback received, were taken into consideration during the revision of the evaluation tools and indicators. However, it was not feasible for the final set of tools and indicators to accommodate all of the feedback from SIMRA partners.

TOOL 2 - FOCUS GROUP

- *In which sense do the **focus group (FG) participants** need to be homogeneous?*
 - Ideally, you should have FG participants with a similar level of knowledge on the Social Innovation initiative; this is the crucial criterion. If there are sufficient potential participants, a balance of their profile would be desirable of between 6 and 12 participants. They should cover: Case Study representatives (approx. 5), policy makers (approx. 4), and ad-hoc key experts (approx. 3). If Case Study teams wish to double check the consistency of the FG composition they should confer with UNIPD. In general, avoid including actors with internal conflicts (a focus group is not the proper technique to manage them).
- *I managed to contact only 6 people for the FG and I am worried that if I will contact more I might risk unbalancing the **group composition** in terms of knowledge (there will be one or two people who will have a much deeper expertise on the Case Study). What should I do?*
 - It is plausible that by inviting more participants the group becomes more heterogeneous regarding the knowledge of the Social Innovation initiative. Yet, the priority criterion is on the focus group size (no less than 6 people and no more than 12), more than on the heterogeneity. Moreover, the remit of the moderator will be to balance the different levels of knowledge, as well the personal characteristics of the participants (for example, shy people vs dominant ones).
- *I am worried that some of the given scientific terminologies will not be properly understood by participants. What should I do? Do I need to define them beforehand to participants?*
 - A glossary is provided in Secco et al. (2017; D4.2) and Gorriz et al. (2017; D5.1), which includes relevant scientific terms used in the evaluation framework and the protocol. Always present the exact (translated if possible) scientific term to the participants. If you perceive that there is some difficulty in understanding, prepare concrete examples that can be understood by participants. According to the context and expertise level of participants, you can decide to show the WP4's video with the main terminology of the evaluation framework.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qCfeLxX6I7c>

Figure 4. An example of a FAQ developed for Tool 2. (Source: Section authors).

Not all of the case study teams had experience with organising and managing participatory research approaches such as focus groups, or with the practice of evaluation. A special training session was organised in Bolzano, Italy (January 2018) to provide data collectors with a standardised understanding of the methods for data collection. However, three full days were insufficient to become familiar with a complex set of tools, and the process of their dynamic design. A longer time would have been required to guarantee that all the members of the case study teams had complete understanding of the methodologies (focus group, questionnaires, semi-structured interviews) and the necessary

² In relation to the Likert scale, the SIMRA Evaluation Approach follows the suggestion of Borgatti *et al.* (2013) in this regard in their seminal work on the analysis of social networks.

specialised competencies and practice. This limitation was reported by several participants in their feedback following the training course. The same case study teams had the impression that, for example, the length of time to complete the Focus Group was due in part to the challenge of managing talkative participants and still be able to respect the time planned for the discussion and remain focused on the discussion topics.

In general, data entry and data processing worked very well due to the clarity and structure of the OPINIO software, which was used for online data entry, and that the MS Excel file used for analysis was automated (i.e. the formulas for the computation of indicators were embedded in the file). The feedback received regarding data entry was the limitations of the OPINIO tool in not having a facility to record additional comments for close-ended questions, and that the MS Excel file needed a manual check of the quality of the data collected.

3.4 Potential and Limitations of the Indicators

Feedback provided by the case study teams, and suggestions on operational issues from Work Package 5, has enabled Work Package 4 to improve the final set of indicators. In order to guarantee consistency across the case studies, the indicator fiches developed by Work Package 4 were used by Work Package 5 for checking the final reporting and triangulation of qualitative and quantitative data. The case study teams only had responsibility for the computation of the indicators. Work Package 5 leaders were asked to provide feedback on problems with computations and the reliability of indicators. Based on these comments the majority of the indicators in the initial version were retained in the final set of indicators, some have been deleted, and some were modified slightly.

The main problems that arose with the indicators which were subsequently deleted were:

- (i) The number of observations on which they were calculated. There was a risk that indicators which are based only on Tools 3 or 5 could be calculated on just one record, which creates problems for analysis especially with questions based on the perceptions of actors;
- (ii) Some topics were perceived as being too sensitive by respondents (e.g. answers to questions about costs and resources were not always reliable);
- (iii) The representativeness of beneficiaries (a few case study teams were not able to interview a representative sample of beneficiaries using Tool 6, which affected the final estimates produced);
- (iv) The variability in answers to as small a number of questions led to insufficient variability in the answers to provide a robust analysis.

See Secco *et al.* (2019; D4.3) and the associated Technical Annex and Manual for the specifications of the process implemented, how feedback in the implementation of the SIMRA Evaluation Approach and methods was used in the development of a final set of indicators.

In the concluding part of this section, findings are presented in relation to the triangulation of quantitative indicators and qualitative data collected through Tools 7 and 8.

To verify the comparability of qualitative data and quantitative indicators, the research team used the reports of the Case Studies produced in Work Package 5. The different sections of the report were checked and used to compare with the: (i) descriptive results of the social innovation (i.e. the chronology and agents of the social innovation); (ii) five parts of social innovation (reaction, reflection, reconfiguring, realisation and replication); (iii) five evaluation criteria (i.e. relevance, efficiency, effectiveness, impact and sustainability); (iv) key elements of the social innovation definition as proposed by SIMRA; (v) policy implications, and in particular the policy support of the social innovation initiative. The comparison of the five parts of social innovation (i.e. point (ii)) was facilitated by the

definition of a common list of concepts (i.e. the dimensions of social innovation as defined by the SIMRA Evaluation Framework) used for structuring both the quantitative and qualitative tools.

The results of the comparison showed that the triangulation process can be carried out for all five sections mentioned previously. The empirical analysis of the eleven Type A Case Studies showed that some difficulties were encountered in the qualitative data collection of a few specific sub-dimensions. These problems were case specific.

In conclusion, the triangulation of information based on qualitative information and quantitative indicators is not an easy task and is time consuming. Some negative feedback was received in relation to the evaluation criteria, observing that the information collected is more often reserved for external evaluations. However, overall, the methodology adopted appears to have been effective and used well.

4. Factors Influencing Social Innovations

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4.1 Introduction

This Section aims to identify the factors and characteristics related to context and agency which create a favourable environment for social innovation to emerge and develop in marginalised rural areas, and the factors that hinder or are barriers which obstruct its emergence. Specific barriers were identified and how they can be overcome together with specific enablers that can be enforced. The social innovation is studied in its embryonic phase when it is still an idea yet to be firmed-up and implemented.

The cross-case analysis aims to identify: the needs to which the social innovation has responded (i.e. the leverage), the elements that lead to its conception, the trigger, the external and internal social, economic, and political contextual factors (context), the agency (innovator), the incubation actions (preparatory actions), and the source of knowledge which leads to development of the idea.

Using the empirical data analysed for each case study, in Task 5.3, the data collected across the cases studies are compared to identify factors that hinder or enable processes of social innovation. The comparison across the cases is based on the theoretical framework, indicators, and empirical analysis developed within Work Package 4 (Secco *et al.*, 2017; D4.2.) and Work Package 5 (Marini Govigli, *et al.*, 2019; D5.3).

4.2 Conceptual Model

The influencing factors are elements that empower or hinder the emergence and development of social innovation initiatives. The presence of favourable conditions may cause a social innovation to start-up; while the absence, underdevelopment or lack of conditions might be barriers to its emergence. In this Section, a structure-agency framework is used to analyse the factors influencing social innovation. Social Innovation emerges from the actions of individuals who operate within the enabling and constraining conditions of their own social, economic, environmental and institutional environments to reconfigure social practices which seek to improve outcomes for the creation of societal well-being (Cajaiba-Santana, 2014). Social innovation is a process of change resulting from the dialectic relationship between structure (i.e. resources and factors that empower or constrain the behaviour of agents) and agency (i.e. the capacity of actors to change social structures), as illustrated in **Figure 5**.

Structure/context refers to the existing set of contextual material and intangible resources (e.g. socio-economic context, policy-institutional context, socio-cultural context) that enables or constrains social innovation, and to the perception by actors as to what constitutes an opportunity or a threat (perceived opportunity and threats) which causes the agency to start. Context includes regulatory frameworks, material resources, and intangible resources such as culture and identity, all with respect to social, financial, legislative, economic, and natural territory dimensions or capitals (Osti, 2010; Goodwin, 2003).

Agency is the capability of actors to mobilise and transform existing resources. It includes specific values, visions and trust, willingness to act, reflexivity and capacity for change. All of these influence how actors or groups of actors (agents) seek to change practices to respond to specific needs, and their level of motivation and power to actually act and sustain their action toward specific goals (Sewell Jr., 1992; Janssen and Ostrom, 2006b; Cajaiba-Santana, 2014). Within agency, consideration is also given to preparatory actions and knowledge as influencing factors of Social Innovation, as they contribute to preparing the ground for Social Innovation and its more systematic collective action. Preparatory actions refer to all those activities that innovators, followers and other agents may carry out at a preliminary stage to “set the ground” for realising the social innovation in practice. It refers to all those actions that may be necessary for preparing the process of reconfiguring (Secco *et al.*, 2017; D4.2).

Figure 5. The Framework of structure and agency for influencing factors (Source: Section authors based upon Secco *et al.*, 2017).

Influencing factors can act as enablers, barriers or as missing elements that are completed in the preparatory action of the Social Innovation, or during the project activities. Identifying and understanding a full range of barriers and enablers (linked to structure and agency) and their interconnections is almost impossible because they are specific to a sector, type of organisation, geographical region, or socio-economic context. However, one way to frame influencing factors is to look at structural conditions that can be both internal and external to the context, which impact on social innovation. These conditions refer to the perceived political, social, economic, cultural, and institutional dimensions which drive individual and collective needs and generate a trigger for action. Amongst contextual factors, those which are internal to the territory are very important as they determine the level of fertility of the ground towards the seeds of innovation. They refer to the level of trust between members of the community towards innovators, the presence of local skills and abilities, cooperation between sectors and organisations, and the openness of the community or closeness to new ideas and to change. External factors are still relevant in contexts which are excluded from political centres of power and which have little financial capacity. They refer to the positive influx of independent sources of money and funding and experience and knowledge from outsiders, and to the negative effects of bureaucracy, pressures, and administrative burdens.

Another way to consider the influencing factors is to focus on the characteristics of the actors involved in the social innovation process, the interactions between them, and their individual and/or collective actions. Agency is determined by ideas and values (e.g. ethical or moral ones). Leadership, motivation, networks, learning, diverse cultural and knowledge systems, world views, values, perception, and self-organisation toward sustainability can be analysed as part of the agency which guides changes in practices through social innovation (Westley *et al.*, 2013; McGinnis and Ostrom, 2014).

The actor-related factors which are internal to an individual or group of individuals are: openness to innovation, proactive thinking, consciousness, responsibility, lifelong learning, positive experience, proactivity, and progressive thinking. The factors which are external are proximity to power and the absence of bureaucracy (Westley and Antadze, 2010; Organisjana *et al.*, 2015).

Agency leads to successful innovation when it possesses a deep knowledge of organisational culture and breaks established organisational patterns and rituals (Lave and Wenger, 1991; Battilana, 2006). An ability of institutionally embedded actors to distance themselves from institutional pressures and to take strategic actions (DiMaggio, 1988) is also crucial.

4.3 Analytical Framework

This section explains the approach used to identify the factors related to context and agency which create a positive environment for social innovation to emerge and thrive, and those which hindering effects in relation to the context and to the agency. Empirical information (indicators and textual information from case study reports) was retrieved from Individual Case Study Reports (Task 5.3) according to the main theme of enquiry. The indicators used for the analysis refer to structure, agency and preparatory actions (Table 2).

Table 2. Indicators considered for the analysis of influencing factors.

Code	Indicator label	Value Range
Aa1	Trigger width	[0-1]
Ba1	Perceived Opportunities and Threats (POT)	[0-1]
Cb1	Attractiveness of the leadership	[0-1]
Cc1	Perception of transformers of the resilience of Innovators and Followers	[0-1]
Cd1	Innovators and Followers capabilities to develop the Social Innovation initiative	[0-1]
Da2	Perception of Social Innovation actors of the contribution of external helpers to the results of the Social Innovation initiative	[0-1]
Ea7	Education level within the Social Innovation network	[0-1]

Source: Section authors.

The cross-case analysis examined the variables defined in the SIMRA theoretical model (Secco *et al.*, 2018; R5.1) and identified common patterns in: i) needs and societal challenges fostering social innovations (paragraph 4.4.1); ii) Elements that trigger social innovations; iii) Contextual enablers and barriers; iv) The Characteristics of Agency; v) Setting the Stage for Social Innovation; and v) Knowledge. The results obtained were used to discover the interplay between the influencing factors (structure and agency) which have or have not mobilised resources to enable or constrain social innovation and to develop some cross-case assertions.

4.4 Results

4.4.1 Needs and societal challenges fostering social innovations

Based on the cross-case analysis, five dimensions have been identified that related to unmet individual and collective needs and societal challenges which are most common to the SIMRA Case Studies, and which leveraged the emergence of social innovation initiatives.

The environmental dimension refers to the need to reduce the environmental impact of activities, to valorise, protect and preserve the territory in order to reduce environmental and socio-economic risks. The cross-case analysis shows that some cases (i.e. cases HAW, SEA, ADF, FIN, FLE, LAG, REV, VIL, HER, and partially NWF) are based upon the need for the reduction of environmental impact of activities. Examples from the cases are: i) implementing more environmentally sound cultivation to provide regional, seasonal, organic food as in the case of community-supported agriculture in Austria and The Netherlands (i.e. cases HAW and HER); ii) building a new and fairer market model for the fishing industry enabling the minimalization of the environmental impacts of fishing as in the case of sustainable fishing in Greece (i.e. case SEA); iii) ensuring more resilient forest management (i.e. cases SLC and SKC).

Other challenges and needs that drive cases are :

- i) the need to valorise, protect, preserve the territory, reduce environmental and socio-economic risks, such as protecting the territory against mega-projects of energy production as in the case of the cooperative Noidanlukko for decentralised energy production and a local development strategy in opposition to nuclear power plants in Finland (i.e. case FIN);
- ii) increase community societal awareness about the issue of wildfires, as in the case of forest defence groups in Spain (i.e. case ADF);
- iii) transform a commercial forestry plantation and rural landscape into a public amenity with community forestry in the United Kingdom (i.e. case LAG);
- iv) improve the management of forest and pastoral ecosystems, as well as reconciling local communities with their surrounding natural environment in Tunisia (i.e. case NWF);
- v) revitalizing traditional heritage in Slovakia (i.e. case REV);
- vi) rediscovering the customary Agdal practice for managing the land and growing argan trees (i.e. case ARG);
- vii) improving the environmental standards of life conditions in rural villages in Egypt (i.e. case VIL);
- viii) identifying the systemic value enhancement of the forest understorey in the Guadeloupian forest (i.e. case GUA);
- ix) exploiting natural resources such as water and wind as sources for business-based Social Innovations in the United Kingdom (i.e. cases BRA and HUN).

The economic dimension refers to the improvements in the economic situation by the increase of revenues and quality of work in the primary sector, the creation of more jobs (secure job dignity), local supply chains and fairer production systems, sustainable income generation for a farmer, and the reduction of the loss of skilled people. The analysis across the case studies shows that twelve cases (i.e. cases HAW, SEA, WOM, VAZ, CAR, LUM, LAG, DAI, REV, CRO, NWF and ARG) aim to create job opportunities, increase revenues and quality of work in the sector, or to provide to relevant potential niche markets the opportunity to valorise local resources.

The issue of market failure and competitive disadvantages is reported in several Case Studies. This is due to infrastructural difficulties that increase costs in production, the small size of enterprises which cannot compete with price, and high costs for the introduction of technical innovations. Therefore, there is a need for income diversification and stabilization by inserting social and community based activities that characterize the social farming cases and green care in Italy and in the Netherlands (i.e. cases WOM and CAR) and community supported agriculture in Austria (HAW); the creation of employment opportunities (cases in Austria, the United Kingdom, Slovakia, Slovenia, Morocco and Tunisia), or improvements in the quality of work which characterizes the rural hub in Italy and the cases in Slovakia and UK (i.e. cases VAZ, REV and LAG). Initiatives also strongly emerge from the need to improve the productivity of local firms and to increase the economic situation of the region as a whole, by creating local supply chains as in the case of local economic development in Val Lumnezia (i.e. case LUM) and in cases LAG, REV, VAZ and DAI. In Tunisia (i.e. case NWF), where increasing the income of the forest population, particularly of women, improving skills and entrepreneurship, advancing development, reducing risk of poverty, social exclusion and unemployment were being tackled by stimulating the creation of micro-enterprises generating job places. Finally, the provision of a niche market product, or the establishment of fairer production, is a need which is tackled by several cases (i.e. cases SEA, DAI, HAW, CAR, WOM, ARG and HER).

The social dimension refers to the need to strengthen community social capital, the provision of social and infrastructural services, and the empowerment of vulnerable groups (women, the disabled, and excluded groups) by increasing their ability and integration in the community. All of the Case Studies that were analysed deal with needs that relate to the social dimension of rural development. Some

specifically tackle the rural exodus, the loss of highly skilled and talented people and their causes (i.e. cases VAZ, FIN, DAI, FLE and CRO). Other cases focus on the lack of social and infrastructural services such as childcare services in Italy, green care in The Netherlands, and waste management in Egypt (i.e. case VIL); target the needs of vulnerable groups by increasing their ability and integration in the community or the economic market (i.e. cases WOM, CAR, ARG and NWF); or the provision of leisure services for tourism (i.e. cases LAG, REV and CRO). Many of the initiatives start from the need to increase social networks, bonding and binding ties within the community, amongst producers and consumers, amongst actors from different fields (e.g. social and agriculture), and the engagement of the community (i.e. cases HAW, SEA, VAZ, ADF, WOM, FIN, CAR, LAG, ARG, HER, FAS, DAI, NWF, SLC and CRO).

The policy and governance dimension refer to the need to restructure governance arrangements (in terms of how administrative and political departments work together with each other), and to the need to influence political processes and agenda setting. The cross-case analysis shows that some cases deal with the need for sustained efforts to restructure how administrative sectors work with each other and with other organisations and companies (i.e. cases FLE, DAI, ADF, LUM, LAG and NWF). One set of cases tackles the need to improve public governance processes by engaging the community in a top-down manner (i.e. cases FLE, DAI, ADF and NWF). A second set deals with the need to provide support mechanisms for businesses of tourism, land management for sustainable agricultural produce (e.g. case HER and HAW), forest management (e.g. cases SKC and SLC), social services provision (i.e. cases LUM, ARG, HER, LAG and FAS). A third set of cases aim to influence political processes regarding local development (i.e. cases FIN, REV and CRO) or regarding innovative activities and services (i.e. cases FAS and HAW).

4.4.2 The trigger of social innovation

A trigger is a specific moment or event that determines the emergence of Social Innovation. The trigger may emerge in connection with a single time-bound event, an accumulation of unmet needs, or a long-term process whereby a situation becomes untenable (Secco *et al.*, 2017, D4.2). Triggers may reflect a positive or negative occurrence or situation. Some Social Innovation Initiatives are initiated by a trigger that involves the entire economic- and social system of a region/area (i.e. cases LUM, LAG and REV) whereas other triggers involved more sector-specific initiatives (i.e. cases SEA, HAW, WOM, DAI and CAR). This is partly reflected in the values of the indicator Aa1 (see **Appendix 2**) on trigger width, which shows who has been most affected by the trigger. The larger the affected group with respect to the whole community, the greater the width of the trigger and therefore the greater the value of the indicator. In cases HAW and DAI those affected were very close relatives of the innovators/followers (ranging from 6% to 28% across the three cases); in cases SEA, LAG, REV and WOM, close friends and acquaintances were affected by the trigger (ranging from 33% to 39% across the three cases); and in cases FIN, VAZ and LUM, a majority, although not the entire community, was affected (ranging from 67% to 100% across the three cases).

As preliminarily conceptualized and studied in Secco *et al.* (2017, D4.2; p.38) and Polman *et al.* (2017, D2.1; p.20), the cross-case analysis empirically shows that the trigger of social innovation can be of different types:

- **Dramatic events or crises and/or concern about political processes.** These are situations where there has been a major unanticipated, socio-ecological disturbance, and where policy decisions were not considered satisfactory by the communities. Some cases have been triggered by dramatic events or crises (i.e. cases ADF, FIN and SEA). For the Spanish case (i.e. case ADF), the event relates to a bad season of wildfires in 1986, where 70,000 ha of forests burned in Catalonia. Fire impacted the symbolically important Montserrat mountain range, which plays a central role in the regional identity. The wildfire triggered the idea to modify the pre-existing fire governance system. For the Finnish case (i.e. case FIN), the dramatic event for many was the approval of the nuclear power project in Pyhäjoki municipality by Finnish

parliament by supplementary decision in 2014. The decision was preceded by several efforts to influence on the nuclear project by local people and NGOs since 2007, and followed by an on-site protest camp, which was cleared by the police in 2016. A following vacuum in opposition of nuclear power was a decisive trigger for the idea of establishing the Noidanlukko cooperative in 2017. In the Greek case (i.e. case SEA), the refugee crisis in 2013 led to Greenpeace members and fishers working together to rescue refugees from the sea. The deepening of trust between the two sides led to Greenpeace deciding to take action towards helping the economic situation of the fishers. In the ADF and FIN cases, the dramatic events were strictly related to a common concern towards political processes of either a reduction in the State guarantee for protection against wildfires (i.e. case ADF), or the imposition of power to the detriment of the local population (i.e. case FIN).

- **Political process, law, framework.** These are situations where politicians have the will to engage in solving a need and creating favourable conditions for an idea to emerge. The trigger of the Social Innovation can be a favourable political process, law, framework, or the political will to solve a situation, such as in Slovakia (i.e. case REV) and in the dairy producers' organisations in Tunisia (i.e. case DAI), and the valorisation approach of Non-wood Forest Products implemented in Tunisia (i.e. case NWF). In case REV, it was the political interest towards the restoration of traditional forms of crafts and the cultivation of land. The registration of the site REV in the list of UNESCO World Heritage Sites in 1993 created a favourable situation for the idea to emerge. In case DAI, the trigger was the announcement of the livestock law in 2005, which provided an organisational basis for the private and public partnership. In case NWF the social innovation was triggered by the government's decision to involve, and provide technical assistance to, national institutions in reinforcing their capacities when operating in forests. Policy processes also provide opportunities: in the United Kingdom (i.e. case LAG), the idea was triggered by the opportunity to purchase forest land in 2008, and the Feed-in-Tariffs for renewable energy provided a window of opportunity for the Social Innovation initiatives BRA and HUN to emerge.
- **Vicious circle of socio-economic conditions.** These are situations in which negative factors accumulate and lead to a socio-economic downturn, major failings in services, or gaps in the delivery by the relevant State institution which then also dramatically reduces the range of services provided. In the Swiss cases FLE, it was the economic crisis in the watch-making industry of the 1970s that triggered the emergence of innovative and alternative development pathways. In the Dutch case HER, the innovator started looking for an alternative and more sustainable way in farming, in a period where many farmers had a rough time (socially and economically). In the Italian case VAZ, the trigger was an accumulation of long economic crises, which had particularly negative effects in the development of the agricultural sector of the Province of Foggia. In Croatia, the case CRO was triggered as a response to the Global Crises at the beginning of the 20th century and associated demographic changes. In Greece (SEA), fishers responded to the declining fish stocks and to the impact that the 2010 economic crises had on their income, due to demand reduction and to the intensification of competition from additional labour force that turn into the primary sector as a result of the rising unemployment rates.
- **Unexpected availability of resources, an opportunity to grasp, a revelatory "Aha moment"** that leads the agency to act. Four cases (i.e. cases HAW, WOM, CAR and VIL) were triggered by the sudden availability of resources or knowledge or by an 'Aha moment', story, or encounter experienced by the innovator. In the Austrian case HAW, the idea was triggered by an idea of community-supported agriculture stimulated by a film about this type of agriculture in Illinois, USA. In the Italian case WOM, the actions of the innovator were triggered by the personal stories of women farmers (in particular, her mother's) being disadvantaged and economically dependent upon male relatives. The innovator was moved to act through an 'Aha

moment' together with an ongoing reflection on the disadvantaged, structural socio-economic condition of women in rural areas, as determined by their lack of economic autonomy or social security mechanisms, and that they were totally dependent upon their husbands and other male relatives. In the Dutch case CAR, the trigger was the visit by a relative of a mentally disabled child to the farm in search of opportunities for daytime activities for that person. The visit made the CAR's actors begin to rethink the future of the farm. In the Italian case FAS the trigger was a meeting of the innovator and follower of a very active priest and on the need to create a network among actors of social agriculture in order to consolidate this practice. In the Egyptian case VIL, the trigger was the meeting of the innovator with the local community in ElGharabawi village in a funeral in 2002 and their consensus on the need for an urgent collective action to clean their village from the dispersed garbage and solid waste.

4.4.3 Contextual enablers and barriers

Context typically includes the socio-economic conditions, which cover a broad range of factors. There are:

- the availability and accessibility of resources that influence social and economic prospects of people living in the area;
- regulatory frameworks, such as laws, legislation and policy;
- overall governance and institutional arrangements;
- material resources such as the availability of funding, raw materials, natural resources, and existing infrastructure;
- market opportunities, social and human capital such as cooperation, and capacity building;
- and intangible resources such as social memory, culture, and values.

However, context is not defined objectively. Rather it is subject to the collective attribution that recognises it as being an "opportunity" which contributes to the success of the implementation of the idea, or a "threat" that could obstruct the realization of the idea and the emergence of social innovation, and often is site-specific. Perceived context is also case-specific because it depends upon resources that are visible locally and culturally, and socially identified and defined.

In the SIMRA evaluation approach, context indicators for natural, human, financial, social, and institutional resources have been identified. The analysis of perceived opportunities and threats (POT) of structure and context has been carried out in each case study. The common elements found to be enabling and hindering by the agency for the emergence of Social Innovation are described below. They are categorised into geographical, economic, social, environmental, and institutional aspects.

Perceived Contextual enablers

Marginalisation in economic, institutional and social domains is often a driver of Social Innovation. Marginalisation is determined by the withdrawal of the public interest in delivering services and building infrastructure, resulting in financial constraints and a lack of infrastructure supporting the vitality of these areas. Because of this, rural regions normally have a low capacity to develop genuine technological or market innovations. Therefore, these territories tackle needs and challenges from a social perspective. This paves the way for the emergence of socially innovative ideas.

- **Economic enablers:** market, financial and general economic enablers refer to the availability of funding and resources (i.e. cases SEA, VAZ, FIN, LAG, WOM and REV), existing public or private incentives for firms to engage in offering the new product or service (i.e. cases CAR, DAI, BRA and HUN), market demand for the product or service (i.e. cases CAR, DAI, WOM and HER), and structural economic changes (i.e. case LUM).

- **Social enablers:** human capital and the engagement of local actors is about civic engagement (i.e. cases HAW, ADF, SEA, VAZ, CAR, FIN, WOM, REV, FLE, ARG and CRO), awareness (i.e. cases ADF, LUM, HER and VIL), a good structure or organisation (i.e. cases SEA and REV), trust in the offer (i.e. cases CAR and DAI), the risk-taking attitude of part of the community (i.e. cases LUM and WOM), and knowledge transfer and the networking opportunities available (i.e. cases HAW, ADF, CAR, LUM, FIN, VIL and WOM).
- **Environmental enablers** refer to the existence of natural and built landscape resources considered as assets (i.e. rural landscape, forest for recreation, mountains, food quality, endemic natural resources, renewable energy sources, waste-free villages) (i.e. cases CAR, WOM, LUM, LAG, REV, ARG, VIL, BRA and HUN).
- **Institutional enablers** are from local political support (i.e. cases HAW, CAR, LUM, LAG, WOM and FLE), or a strong political support (i.e. cases ADF, DAI, REV, ARG, NWF), a well institutionalized framework (i.e. cases CAR and WOM), . Public support facilitates the success of the mainstreaming of the idea, and the acceptance of the idea by the community. Those ideas that strive to create radical change of the system take longer to achieve success.

Perceived contextual barriers

- **Market, financial, and general economic barriers** refer to initial market uncertainty towards the new offer of a service or product, which leads to low incentives, utility to compel, adhere to or co-operate with the initiative (i.e. cases HAW, WOM, LUM, DAI and NWF). The lack of capital to start the initiative (i.e. cases HAW and VIL) and to continue the initiative (i.e. case FIN) hinders the emergence of new ideas.
- **Socio-cultural barriers** refer to: i) a feeling of negativity, pessimism, lack of self-confidence of the community (i.e. cases SEA and LUM), previously unsuccessful experiences with similar topics as the idea (i.e. cases FIN and DAI), a lack of basic social infrastructures and skills among communities (i.e. illiteracy) (NWF); ii) close-mindedness, conservatism, or the marginalisation of alternative thinking that hinders the acceptance of new ideas (i.e. cases FLE, VAZ, LUM, FIN, DAI, LAG, WOM, REV, ARG and HER). Both attitudes are linked to the characteristic of ambiguity aversion.

In some cases, there is a lack of local engagement (i.e. cases FIN, DAI and LUM) which can be linked to a lack of social capital due to emigration or to a lack of awareness. Finally, barriers can be related to human capital and a lack of technical knowledge that the idea would require (i.e. cases DAI and NWF) and community illiteracy (i.e. cases ARG, NWF).

- **Institutional barriers** include rigid financing schemes (i.e. case LAG), rigid institutional schemes (i.e. cases WOM, CAR and HER) designed or managed from higher administration levels which limit the action at the local level, institutional fragility (i.e. cases LUM), underdeveloped governance structure (i.e. case ADF), insufficient policies to regulate the new product or service (i.e. cases SEA, VAZ and FAS), or infrastructural obstacles (i.e. cases LAG and NWF).

Each case study may have enablers, barriers or missing elements that belong to the same domain but leverage different aspects of it. For example, in the economic domain, market opportunities or initial market distrust is not incoherent with the presence or absence of funding opportunities. In the social domain, the feeling of negativity of the entire community is not inconsistent with the existence of a solid network that trusts the idea. At the institutional level, strong political support can be perceived as an opportunity but at the same time rigid institutional schemes may impede the emergence of creative ground-breaking solutions.

Each Case Study is a different equation of factors. The types of enabling and hindering factors identified, and the number of both types of factors, means that the cases have different balances between opportunities and threats. Some similarities are identifiable. All Case Studies have a low value

for indicator Ba1 “Perceived Opportunities and Threats (POT)” (see **Table 2**), which ranges from 0.03 as minimum value (i.e. case HAW) to a maximum value of 0.20 (i.e. case SEA) out of 1. These low values mean that many opportunities also correspond to many threats faced by the Social Innovation initiatives. This means that Social Innovation may emerge on a path with many obstacles, but with several enablers in support.

4.4.4 The characteristics of Agency

Agency includes the characteristics of the actors, their motivation and willingness to act to realise the idea and to engage others in the process. The cross-case analysis shows that most of the cases reported strong engagement, leadership and motivation of the innovator (i.e. cases SEA, HAW, WOM, VAZ, LUM, CAR FIN, FLE, ARG, CRO and VIL). In each case the innovator has been the driving force of the idea, invested personal time and resources to its implementation, had a key role in the initiative, and had a clear vision of its future. The charisma of the innovator and their ability to engage with others and encourage them to join the initiative and to present the idea, has played an important role in almost all the cases. Examples in the cases are the high level of capability to contribute to the Social Innovation initiative development in the Austrian case HAW; the ability of being both visionary and practice-oriented, and the networking abilities were crucial for the organisation in The Netherlands (CAR) and Greece (SEA); the capacity to be politically active and to lobby organisations such as in the case of social farming in Italy (WOM), the two Swiss cases (LUM and FLE), and the Slovakian case (REV).

In contrast to the other cases, in the Finnish case (FIN) the low attractiveness of the idea has been explained as being due to contested relationships between opponents and proponents of the project at the local level. There are cases in which qualitative information has not revealed any characteristics regarding charisma or strong engagement by the agency (i.e. cases DAI and ADF). In relation to this aspect, the indicator Cb1 “attractiveness of the leadership” (see **Table 2**) shows whether the leadership and charismatic features of the core group (innovators and followers) have led to the motivation and thus engagement of others (i.e. transformers) to join the initiative.³ The cases REV, VAZ, LUM and DAI show that a share of network members (67%, 40%, 30% and 17% respectively) have engaged in the initiative because they liked the leadership and the charisma of the innovators and followers. The indicator does not, however, represent those who have not chosen this response as their first choice in the relevant data collection survey. Nevertheless, the qualitative data reported above indicate that cases HAW, CAR, WOM, FLE and FIN have charismatic innovators.

The study by Katonáné *et al.* (2017) confirms the findings in the SIMRA case studies with initiators of social innovation who “easily recognise and apply connections between concepts, are quick problem solvers, work at a dynamic pace and are regularly inclined to multitask” (p. 191). That study also found that leadership is important but not essential “Innovators are keen to undertake a leading role but are also happy to follow others if necessary. They are enthusiastic team players” (p.191).

In contrast, for all Case Studies the values of the indicator Cc1 (**Table 2**) about the perceptions of transformers of the resilience of innovator and followers are equal to and above the mean (i.e. > 0.56). Therefore, in all the case studies, the innovator demonstrates resilience for overcoming obstacles and flexibly adapting to changing circumstances. Indicator Cd1 on Innovators and Followers capabilities to develop the Social Innovation initiative (**Table 2**) shows the ranking of the innovator and followers' capabilities to develop the social innovation initiative with respect to other actors involved in the initiative in terms of four types of capacities (technical, influencing the decision-making process

³ In the online survey, members of the network were asked to indicate the motivation for their engagement in the social innovation initiative. Whether or not they liked the idea and believed it made sense explanations were that they wanted to serve a good cause, they liked the leadership and charisma of the innovator(s) and followers, they wanted to share their expertise for the project, they wanted to feel personally fulfilled, they wanted to receive economic benefits, it was part of the duties of their job, there were previous relationships with the people involved, or there were other motivations (with a request to provide details).

internally, creating bridges with external actors, and facing challenges). SEA has far the highest recorded values among the 11 case studies (maximum value of 1), indicating that the highest capacities were concentrated in the clique. CAR, LUM and ADF follow, showing values above 0.10. In other cases, i.e. WOM, VAZ, FIN and DAI, capacities were more equally distributed among clique and network's members.

From the cross-case analysis, it is apparent that although abilities may be concentrated differently between innovators and network members, the main characteristics of the innovator are charisma and leadership skills, strong engagement, vision, and the ability to engage others in the idea. As analysed by Sarkki *et al.* (2019), these characteristics relate to the sphere of human values, which are considered the primary catalyst of social innovations. Particularly relevant are the relational values to local resources, which are "doing", "belonging" and "respecting".

Conclusions can be derived regarding the interest of the social innovators in engaging in developing and implementing an innovative idea. The vision of a social innovator may be linked to serving a good cause, even if the person themselves do not personally benefit from the innovative service or product (i.e. cases VAZ, WOM, SEA, FIN, DAI, FLE and NWF). In these cases, the innovators have a creative interest and an altruistic service interest. They strive to develop new ideas, like to help others, support them, and facilitate processes.

In cases such as NWF, in which the innovators are public and international organisations, the willingness of innovators to act can also be driven by professionalism. These types of social innovators are motivated by brainstorming, are good at problem solving, and have a strong sense of justice. However, they may not be very good at the routine of maintaining or operating an organisation since they have an inner drive to innovate. They need a strong and operational network that supports the implementation. The innovator's vision, on the other hand, can be linked directly to the benefits of the new service or product (i.e. in cases HAW, CAR, LUM, REV and VIL), and the followers are the first beneficiaries of the new service or product, directly interested in its realization (i.e. in cases LUM and WOM). In these cases, agency has an enterprising interest in which the innovators (and the followers) are result-oriented and practical. They have a strong inner drive and have a constant need to get ahead.

4.4.5 Setting the stage for Social Innovation

In most case studies preparatory actions were implemented by the core group (innovators and followers) for the development of the social innovation initiative. Their implementation is characterised by different processes, but the cases can be clustered into three main groups of characteristics.

- **Bottom-up structured preparation** is characterized by a long-term process including project submission for funding, organisation of first information events, consultation processes, and study visits abroad. The actions have been carried out bottom-up, derived from the will and motivations of the civil society, with no directive or impositions from higher levels (e.g. politicians, public officers). These characteristics were observed in the cases of the social farming in Italy (i.e. case WOM), the community forestry in Scotland (i.e. case LAG), the rural hub in Apulia (i.e. case VAZ), systemic value-enhancement of the forest understorey in Guadeloupe (i.e. case GUA), and the Finnish case (i.e. case FIN).
- **Top-down structured preparation** is characterised by the public leading the implementation of preparatory actions with top-down involvement of the civil society. In the Slovakian and Swiss cases (i.e. cases REV, FLE and LUM), there was involvement at the municipal and supra-municipal level, while in Spain (i.e. case ADF), the process was supported at the regional level, and in the Tunisian cases at the national level (i.e. cases DAI and NWF). The actions that characterize this type of process are having constituted steering and working groups, participatory planning, implementation of legal directives, and development of a strategy.

- **Quick preparatory process characterised by learning by doing** comprises a preparatory phase that corresponds to the Social Innovation implementation phase, the core group forming itself very quickly, and the first beneficiaries being present from an early stage. This process characterises the Austrian (i.e. HAW), the Dutch (i.e. CAR), and the Greek (i.e. SEA) cases.

4.4.6 Knowledge

Case Studies may be clustered in four groups according to the type of knowledge, learning, sources of information and abilities that have supported the development of the idea:

- **External knowledge coming from academia and international networks.** This type of knowledge characterized the Finnish, Slovakian, Italian and Austrian cases (i.e. cases FIN, REV, HAW, VAZ and FAS). In the FIN case, most of the core team does not live in the Pyhäjoki area. Board members are environmental activists and researchers. The involvement of global citizens is explained by the character of the problem, which Noidanlukko is addressing: the nuclear power project has wide ranging potential impacts across large geographical areas and over long timescales.
In this cluster the support of the external experts such as academia is perceived as high. The follower in the REV case is a scientist at the University of Bratislava who was approached by the innovator. This person has considerable experience with projects on landscape ecology. In HAW case, the innovator learned about the principles of Community Supported Agriculture and projects during an exchange period in Germany and France the participation in an EU-Grundtvig project on knowledge sharing in Community Supported Agriculture.
- **External knowledge coming from regional, national or supranational entities.** This type of knowledge characterized the Swiss, Tunisian, UK, Greek, Dutch and Moroccan cases (i.e. cases LUM, FLE, DAI, NWF, LAG, SEA, CAR and ARG). In LUM case, network members provided the external knowledge, which was judged to be important by the actors involved. The support and technical knowledge for producers' organisations in DAI case, and for improving the management of the forest sector in NWF case was provided by the FAO, upon the request of the Ministry of Agriculture for Tunisia. In DAI case, the assistance of FAO consisted in supporting public and private actors to promote extension and milk control activities through a public-private partnership programme. In CAR case, the external partner in establishing a care farm is a health care organisation providing knowledge of care and acting as an intermediary with clients in the early years of the CAR initiative. Support for LAG case was obtained from the national level Community Woodland Association and Scottish Natural Heritage. In FLE case, the social innovation was derived from both endogenous and exogenous processes; however, the external helpers are from the same milieu as those who are internal to the territory. In SEA, data collection within the local context, analysis of possible markets and competitors, laws and logistics, and knowledge of existing initiatives taking place outside the region was mainly done by the NGO Greenpeace Greece.
- **Local knowledge linked to experience.** This type of knowledge characterised the Spanish, Dutch, Slovenian, Slovak, Scottish and Egyptian cases (i.e. ADF, CAR, SLC, SKC, LAG and VIL). In the ADF case, forest landowners, farmers, specialists in civil protection, and wildfire experts provided technical and practical knowledge from the pre-existing forest owner associations. The process of knowledge acquisition is derived from peer-to-peer learning. The cases of CAR, LAG and VIL are included in this cluster because in addition to external practical knowledge, embeddedness in the community, and experience in the field, local connections are considered essential abilities for the Social Innovation.
- **Local knowledge based on data collection.** This type of knowledge characterised the Italian and Croatian cases (i.e. WOM and CRO) in which data collected within the local context,

analysis of possible markets and competitors, laws and logistics, and knowledge of existing initiatives taking place outside the region were all relevant to implementing the initiative.

The indicator on the perception of SI actors of the contribution of external helpers, such as brokers, advisors and policy makers, to the results of the Social Innovation initiative is shown by the values for Da2 (Table 2). This indicator is assessed to be high in DAI, LUM, REV and LAG cases, medium in WOM and CAR cases, and low to very low in VAZ, ADF, SEA and HAW cases. The average education level within the social innovation network, as evaluated by indicator Ea7 (Table 2) is very high in ADF, DAI, VAZ and LUM cases (values from 0.71 to 1.00, corresponding to high school to university), medium in FIN, CAR and LAG cases (values 0.50 to 0.67 corresponding to middle school to high school), and low to very low in WOM, SEA and HAW cases (values from 0 to 0.25 corresponding to no formal education up to middle school). The value of the indicator will be influenced by the presence of national level members of the network, who tend to have a higher education level, and on the size of the network, as bigger networks tend to have more diversity of education levels. However, the education level is shown to not be a proxy of the level of capacity of network members to contribute to the Social Innovation. HAW case has the highest value (1.00), whereas it had the lowest value for indicator Ea7. LAG and REV cases also have the highest value. WOM has a high value (0.75), whereas it has a low score for indicator Ea7. Case ADF has high values for both indicators. VAZ, LUM and FIN cases have medium values for both indicators. Case SEA has low values for both.

4.5 Cross-case Observations

Social innovation initiatives emerge as a result of the interactions between the agents and their structures. The origin of social innovation ideas can be of two types, those that originate from a local context and those that originate from outside.

The first type are social innovations that emerge locally from a lively, vibrant agency and a highly knowledgeable local civil society that has identified an opportunity in a disadvantaged, marginalised situation. They can be described as mainly endogenous ideas, produced by re-mixing the local characteristics in a new pattern and approaching local challenges from a different perspective. Their main supporters are the local community and local politicians. The idea is not radical or implying a reversal of the local habits, customs, or culture; therefore, it is not too difficult to accept by the target group (beneficiaries).

The second type of social innovations is where the idea comes from outside. These have been brought to the Marginalised Rural Areas from outside by a visionary agency that may be local or external. They can be described as neo-endogenous ideas, produced by a re-mixing of internal and external characteristics. They are more radical and require more organisation and energy. Some may redefine the way the community or the production is organised and may radically transform the referring conception of development of use of resources.

Overall, social innovations are pollinated by external factors; however, there is always an endogenous seed. This highlights the inevitable interplay between endogenous and exogenous factors leading to social innovation and the fact that the Social Innovation initiatives are embedded in local contexts.

The types of the agency that lead to social innovation initiatives can arise as bottom-up, top-down, or something in the middle. Bottom-up, civic-led initiatives emerge due to the organisation of civil society (e.g. private actors, associations, non-governmental organisations) with no initial intervention from the public sector. They are independent ideas that are derived from the feeling of urgency and need on the part of civic society. Top-down, public-led initiatives emerge because the public administration feels the need to find a solution to a local issue and applies pressure to force the realisation of the idea by the local community. This may include engaging the community in participatory processes or funding some private organisations to develop the idea through to a full proposal or its implementation. Public-private partnership initiatives can emerge as a co-creation between public and

private sector agency, recognising together the urgency and relevance of the idea, and sharing efforts to initiate the initiative.

Conclusions can be drawn about the factors necessary and conditions which influence the emergence of social innovations in marginalised rural areas.

First, the presence of a disadvantaged or marginalised context in socio-economic and institutional terms, with respect to main centres of power, can trigger the emergence of social innovation initiatives. The recognition of the existence of a vacuum in the community which requires to be filled, which can be a market or public service vacuum, is something that motivates people to act. In most cases, the marginalisation of these territories is determined by the withdrawal of the public interest in delivering services and building infrastructures, resulting in financial constraints and a lack of infrastructure for supporting their vitality and potential to thrive. This results in a low capacity for developing genuine technological or market innovations. Therefore, these territories tackle needs and challenges via socially innovative ideas that start in an informal way, bottom up.

Second, social innovation appears to be influenced by leadership skills and community trust in that leadership, and by the presence of strong social capital characterized by trust, collective actions, and collaboration as well as human capital (networking, engagement, abilities). Enhancing these characteristics in an area is likely to increase the capacities of rural communities to make strategic choices and address contemporary challenges.

Third, social innovations arise because of the presence of an innovator with strong leadership, motivational capabilities, creativity, and a personal character that can make connections and bridge divides and recognised by the community as having a certain agency and of their leadership. That is an aspect which, if not necessary is at least highly significant.

Finally, the support of the public authorities, municipal officers, or policy makers at different levels, recognising the capacity of the innovator and the validity of the idea, is necessary to provide good prospects of success of a social innovation. These forms of support also support conditions conducive to its scaling up and out. Indeed, public support facilitates the success of the mainstreaming of the idea and its acceptance by the community.

5. Reconfiguration of Social Practices

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5.1 Introduction

The reconfiguration of social practices is a crucial element of social innovations (Polman *et al.*, 2017). According to the SIMRA conceptual framework (Secco *et al.*, 2017), the analysis of the reconfiguration of social practices can be divided into two phases: the “reconfiguring” and the “reconfigured”, depending on whether the social relations are analysed in the social innovation process stage or in the project stage. The reconfiguring phase is the set of preliminary actions initiated by the core group of actors of the social innovation (Secco *et al.*, 2017). It includes the changes in social practices of the attitudes of actors, the networks, and governance arrangements. The reconfiguring processes eventually leads to the reconfigured phase, which is the moment at which the social innovation project can emerge and be implemented. Typically, the reconfiguring phase kicks off after the trigger event and lasts until the implementation of the initiative.

Based on the theoretical framework and indicators developed within Work Package 4 (Secco *et al.*, 2017; D4.2.), and the analyses conducted at the case study level (Marini Govigli *et al.*, 2019b), this section checks how the reconfiguring process has taken place across the SIMRA cases in terms of the formation of new networks, new attitudes, and new governance arrangements. By comparing available information across cases, checks were also made about whether variables such as the duration or size of the network affects the outcomes of the reconfiguring process. This is done with the final aim of understanding whether the network dimension plays a role in regulating the internal dynamics of the social innovation initiatives that were studied. This section is divided into three main parts: first, it presents the conceptual model (Section 5.2) and analytical approach (Section 5.3); then, it displays the assessment of the main significant results stemming from the analysis (Section 5.4), and finally, it draws some cross-case observation on the theme of enquiry (Section 5.5).

5.2 Conceptual Model

In this section, the existing relationships between the size of the network and its outcomes on the social innovation collective action are analysed. The working hypothesis is that the group size and duration of social innovation initiatives may have significant linear implications for their effectiveness. The size-outcome relationship has been thoroughly explored in social network analysis literature. Groups are fundamental units for achieving collective action beyond the individual level. Their size, however, can have a supporting or hindering effect on the action's outcomes. Larger groups tend to have higher transition costs for ensuring the communication and unity of vision of members (Esteban and Ray, 2001). This can hinder group control, hence increasing the number of members of the network who benefit but contribute little (Olson, 1965). By comparison, smaller groups have limited human and economic resources (e.g. time and funds), which can limit the effectiveness of the network's collective action (Agrawal and Goyal, 2001). Findings in other studies that investigated these trends obtained contrasting results, such as linear positive trends (e.g. Zhang and Zhu, 2011), negative trends (e.g. Uphoff, 2000), or non-linear trends (e.g. Yang *et al.*, 2013) between size and groups outcomes.

The issue of size has been recently observed in social innovation initiatives. One of the reasons why setting up social innovation initiatives is more challenging than those of technological innovation is that social innovations often start from a limited size (Mendes *et al.*, 2012). While Salaran and Maritz (2013) show that innovative processes are more prone to emerge with increasing social ties, there is no evidence that positive or negative linear relationships exist between social innovation networks and their related reconfiguring outcomes.

A further consideration is how bonding social capital (i.e. the level of connections within a group or community) behaves in remote rural areas for spurring social innovation initiatives. Sørensen (2016)

found that rural communities might have stronger internal ties and connections. Whether this also holds true for remote and marginal communities remains to be proven.

Regarding the hypothesis that the duration of an initiative may have an implication for its effectiveness over the long term, no direct evidence has been published. Existing studies focusing on the factors linked to successful social innovation processes identify, amongst other considerations, network-related characteristics (commitment, participation, and acceptance), organisational structures of the initiative, and access to finance (Neumeier, 2017). In this cross-case analysis, an aim is to verify if this is also the case for the social innovation initiatives studied in SIMRA.

5.3 Analytical Approach

This section builds on the data regarding the networks of the analysed social innovation Type A Case Studies, namely: information on network evolution (reconfiguring process duration, changes perceived), indicators based on social network analysis variables (network size, structure), and information on attitudes and governance arrangements. The data were collected by the case study teams using the SIMRA tools (Secco *et al.*, 2018; R5.1), and indicators were built for each case study report following the guidelines of Secco *et al.* (2018). The employed indicators are listed in Table 3. To ensure comparability, all indicators have been normalised to a scale of 0 to 1.

Table 3. Indicators employed in the Reconfiguring analysis across cases.

Code	Indicator Label	Value Range
SIR1	Individual perceptions of actors of the improvement in social practices due to the Social Innovation process ⁴	[0-1]
SIR2	Collective perceptions of actors of the improvement in social practices due to the Social Innovation process ⁴	[0-1]
SIR3	Perception of actors of the extent of the process of reconfiguration	[0-1]
F3	Change in the collaborative relationships between the actors of the Social Innovation process	[0-1]
F11	Change in the collaborative relationships between the actors of the Social Innovation initiative	[0-1]
Ea4	Reputational power in the core group of the Social Innovation network	[0-1]
Ea10	New relationships within the Social Innovation network	[0-1]
OldEa11 ⁵	Social Innovation network internal efficiency during the Social Innovation process	[0-1]
Ea12	Level of internal trust in the Social Innovation network	[0-1]
Eb1	Level of pro-action of Transformers during the Social Innovation process	[0-1]
OldEc4 ⁶	Types of sanctions	[0-1]

⁴ Indicators SIR1 and SIR2 have been modified in the final version of the Manual on Innovative Methods to assess Social Innovation and its impacts (Secco et al. 2019; D4.3). Nonetheless, as data has been collected by the 11 case study teams they have been included in this analysis as to provide a more detailed overview on the reconfiguration processes.

⁵ The indicator “Social Innovation internal efficiency during the SI process” has been removed from the list of indicators reported in the Technical Annex on the Manual on Innovative Methods to assess Social Innovation and its impacts (Secco et al. 2019; D4.3). The authors have chosen to include it in the analysis following the methodology used in D5.3. The indicator has therefore been renamed OldEa11.

⁶ The formula of the indicator “Types of sanctions” has been changed in the final version Technical Annex of the Manual on Innovative Methods to assess Social Innovation and its Impacts (Secco et al. 2019; D4.3) in comparison to the methodology followed to calculate the value in D5.3. The authors have chosen to include it in the analysis following the methodology used in D5.3. The indicator has therefore been renamed OldEc4.

Ec4	Level of trust in public institutions of the actors of the Social Innovation process	[0-1]
F4	Change in internal and external governance arrangements of the Social Innovation initiative as perceived by the actors of the Social Innovation process	[0-1]
I10	Perceptions of actors of the level of improvement in governance aspects due to the Social Innovation initiative	[0-1]
Db3	Expertise motivating the engagement of Social Innovation actors	[0-1]
Ca1	Attractiveness of the Social Innovation idea	[0-1]
Ea1	Attendance level at meetings in the Social Innovation process	[0-1]

(Source: Section authors).

The terminology used in this analysis of the social networks uses the following terms based on Hanneman and Riddle (2005):

- **Network** reflects the relationships amongst a group of people or institutions (nodes). The network is considered to be composed of the innovator(s), the follower(s), and the transformers (Secco *et al.*, 2019; D4.3). The core group is a subset of the network composed of the innovator(s) and the follower(s).
- **Network size** describes the total number of actors included in a network.
- **Network density** refers to the ratio of the relationships found between a group of people as a proportion of the total number of possible relationships they could have (i.e. each having contact with each other).
- **Network distance** refers to the average number of intermediate people one actor needs to contact another.
- **Network centrality** denotes the degree of power of certain network actors in comparison with others.
- **Reputational power** was measured as the perceived influence of the network actors in the decision-making during the reconfiguring process.
- **Core-Periphery analysis** reveals a set of actors who have a high density of ties between themselves (the core), and another set of actors who have very low density of ties between themselves (the periphery).

The aim was to test the hypothesis of whether the duration of the reconfiguring process, the social innovation, or the size of the network, explain the variation across cases of the different indicators. To that end, linear correlations were employed. Only those associations showing a significant trend and an R^2 greater than or equal to 0.15 are reported⁷. Due to incomplete information gathered for some cases, a few indicators are not available for all eleven of the Type A social innovation Case Studies. These are indicators Ea4 and F11 which were not available for the cases REV, HAG and LAG. This meant that some analyses were undertaken with a limited set of observations.

5.4 Results

5.4.1 Duration of the reconfiguring phase

Figure 6. illustrates the approximate duration of the reconfiguring phase across all cases. The longest process was observed in the LUM case in Switzerland, and the shortest duration is of the Finnish case (FIN). The duration of the reconfiguring phase is approximately one and a half years. This value is greatly influenced by the two cases which have the longest durations (i.e. cases LUM and CAR), which

⁷ Due to limited sample size (N=11), we acknowledge the limitation of this analysis. Therefore, the results of the linear regression analysis should be considered with caution.

are outliers in the set of cases. Eight cases have a duration below the mean value. On average, the reconfiguring process lasts approximately 19% of the overall time dedicated to the social innovation.

The Case Studies exhibit a positive linear relationship between the approximate length of the reconfiguring process, and the total duration of the social innovation initiative (**Figure 6.**). This relationship also exists for the Type B case study FLE, which had a long social innovation process associated with a reconfiguring phase lasting six years. An exception to this pattern is the ADF case in Catalonia (Spain), in which the reconfiguring process is much shorter in comparison to its overall duration, probably due to the difficulties on identifying the time limits of the reconfiguration process. Nonetheless, the goodness of fit of the model (R^2) is around 0.30 even considering the outlier value of case study ADF.

Figure 6. Relationship between the length of the reconfiguring process and the overall duration of the eleven Type A Case Studies. The trend line, equation and its goodness of fit (R^2) are also provided. (Source: Section authors).

5.4.2 Effectiveness of the reconfiguring phase

The SIR1 and SIR2 indicators assess the individual and the collective perceptions of actors of the improvement in social practices due to the Social Innovation process. The mean values across the eleven cases are positive for both indicators (SIR1: 0.81 ± 0.03 ; SIR2: 0.71 ± 0.05 on a scale of 0 to 1). This indicates that actors perceive that changes in the network, relationships, and governance mechanisms did take place during the reconfiguring phase.

Indicator SIR3 measures the perception of actors of the extent of the process of reconfiguration in terms of the: (i) number of changes observed in the innovative network, (ii) number of changes observed in attitudes, (iii) number of changes observed in innovative mechanisms of network functioning, and (iv) number of changes observed in the actions of public actors (Secco *et al.*, 2018). Appraising this indicator allows the estimation of whether the actors perceived that the reconfiguring phase was successful. The mean of SIR3 across the eleven Case Studies 0.55 (standard error: ± 0.07), indicating that only a moderate number of changes (approximately one and a half changes over a maximum of three asked) are perceived as having occurred during the process of reconfiguration.

Further details of the main changes perceived by the network actors in the four different elements across the eleven cases are shown in Table 4, based upon indicator SIR3. Across all the cases, REV, DAI, VAZ, and FIN cases have the highest levels of perceived changes during the reconfiguration phase,

whereas SEA and ADF cases have the lowest levels. On average, the main changes observed during the reconfiguring phase take place in the innovative network, whereas the action of public actors is perceived to have seldom changed. The reconfiguring phase has been crucial for changing the network in the HAW, REV, FIN, and LUM cases which shows that the preparatory phase to launch those social innovations entailed a major advance in the establishment or expansion of relationships between actors.

The estimates of changes in attitudes were around the middle of the range of the indicator, but especially important for the DAI, REV, and VAZ cases. Changes in the internal governance of the network are perceived to have been greatest in the cases of FIN and HAW. The largest change perceived in the actions of public actors occurred in REV case. There is no evidence of change in SEA or HAW cases, which is understandable since their direct selling initiative is entirely between private actors (producers and buyers). These results are validated by some of the Case Studies of Types B and C. In the FLE case, the highest level of changes (0.89) is perceived as happening within the network of actors as more contacts and collaborations across municipalities developed as the initiative grew. By comparison, in the NWF case, the greatest extent of perceived changes was in relation to new attitudes, which happened during the reconfiguring phase in relation to awareness of the importance of Non-Wood Forest Products for the livelihood of the rural and forest communities.

Table 4. Summary of the main changes perceived in the eleven Type A Case Studies (values are normalised for indicator SIR3).

Subject for which Changes Observed	Type A Case Studies											Mean
	VAZ	HAW	REV	WOM	LAG	LUM	SEA	CAR	ADF	DAI	FIN	
Innovative Network	0.88	1.00	1.00	0.08	0.33	0.97	0.29	0.67	0.27	0.88	1.00	0.67
Attitudes	0.73	0.67	0.87	0.67	0.67	0.70	0.26	0.50	0.33	0.92	0.56	0.62
Innovative Mechanisms of Network Function	0.75	0.83	0.67	0.50	0.67	0.67	0.38	0.33	0.00	0.54	0.89	0.57
Actions of Public Actors	0.55	0.00	0.60	0.00	0.33	0.42	0.00	0.17	0.33	0.79	0.44	0.33
Mean	0.73	0.63	0.78	0.31	0.50	0.69	0.23	0.42	0.23	0.78	0.72	0.55

(Source: Section authors).

5.4.3 New Networks

During the reconfiguring phases, new networks were created and/or strengthened in almost all of the Case Studies analysed. These networks vary across cases in their structure, composition, and the main relationships formed between actors.

Composition and structure of networks

The comparison of the network size across cases is provided in Section 7.⁸ The mean of the number of actors that constitute networks across the Case Studies is 16.1 people, the largest of which is the case of VAZ (an estimate of 28 actors involved in the initiative), and the smallest in the South Tyrol case WOM (6 actors).

⁸ In the ADF case, the size of the entire network was estimated to be 16 people. This value is an approximation due to the long time that elapsed between setting up the initiative and the interviews. In the REV case, the combined size of the core group and network was estimated to be 25 people.

Figure 7. Size of the entire network (network and core group) for each of the eleven Type A Case Studies. The horizontal line indicates the mean value. (Source: Section authors).

Network structure

The density of the collaborative relationships between actors before and during the Social Innovation process has changed (indicator F3) by over 50% in all except one case (i.e. FIN). A significant negative linear relationship was identified between the level of collaboration between the actors during the Social Innovation process and the level of collaboration before the Social Innovation process, and the full network size (**Figure 8**). Overall, larger networks tend to be less effective during the process of social innovation.

Figure 8. Relationship between normalised indicator F3 (change in the collaborative relationships between the actors of the Social Innovation process) and the size of the entire networks of the cases (i.e. network and core group). The trend line, equation and its goodness of fit are also provided. (Source: Section authors).

All the Case Studies (except the FIN case), where a network analysis has been conducted⁹, show an increase in the density of the collaborative relationships between the period before the social

⁹ In HAW case the network analysis has not been performed

innovation initiative and the one immediately following. Nonetheless, the increasing density of collaboration in the network was not found to be significantly related to the overall duration of the social innovation initiative. This could be motivated by the fact that the longest-operating initiatives (i.e. cases LUM, ADF and CAR), exhibit lower densities of collaboration.

A positive linear relationship was found between change in the collaborative relationships between the actors of the Social Innovation initiative before and after the social innovation initiative (indicator F11) and the change in the collaborative relationship before and during the Social Innovation process (indicator F3), shown in **Figure 9**. This indicates that cases where the collaborative network increased during the reconfiguring process also have an increasing rate of collaboration after the stabilisation of the social innovation initiative. Cases such as WOM, DAI, and SEA have similar values for indicators F3 and F11, indicating that during the project phase their networks did not increase substantially in size. This is probably because during the reconfiguring phase, the network reached maturity in terms of the needs of the initiative for it to be operational and therefore there was no need for further expansion. In the SEA case, the central coordination by Greenpeace limited the network expansion given that new entries should strictly adhere to the principles of sustainable fishing practises, established within the original network. In the DAI case, some of the national nodes (the FAO and central national offices) during the implementation phase faded as contacts across regional offices increased only at the regional level.

Similarly, in FLE case during the process of reconfiguration the network did not expand. This is likely to be due to all relevant actors already having strong ties before the Social Innovation reconfiguration process had started. In comparison, the VAZ and ADF cases continued to grow their networks due to the consolidation of network relationships through time (e.g. the strengthening of the role of the farmers in the VAZ case).

Figure 9. Relationship between normalized indicator F11 (Change in the collaborative relationships between the actors of the Social Innovation initiative) and normalized indicator F3 (Change in the collaborative relationships between the actors of the Social Innovation process). The trend line, equation and its goodness of fit are also provided. (Source: Section authors).

Five cases (i.e. LUM, ADF, FIN, DAI, WOM) have a high ratio (between 70% and 80%) of the members of the core group with the highest level of reputational power (i.e. influence in the decision-making) during the social innovation process. Other cases show considerably lower ratios (i.e. cases CAR, SEA

and VAZ). Network size does explain these divergences (**Figure 10**) as cases with larger networks tend to disperse the reputation power away from the core group. In the VAZ case, for example, only 41% of the core members had the highest decision-making influential positions.

Figure 10. Relationship between the normalized indicator Ea4 (reputational power in the core group of the Social Innovation network) and the full size of the networks in the cases (network and core group). The trend line, equation and its goodness of fit are also provided. (Source: Section authors).

Assessing the distances within the network enables the level of connections across actors in social innovation initiatives to be inferred. From there, an estimation can be made of the internal efficiency of the network as measured by the number of formal and informal collaborations established during the process of the social innovation (Secco *et al.*, 2018; R5.1). The indicator used to assess the network's internal efficiency during the Social Innovation process is OldEa11. The values for the eleven Type A cases range from the lowest of 0.98 steps (0.23 in the normalised indicator) in the DAI and REV case, to the highest of 4.3 (1.00 in the normalised indicator) steps, for the ADF case. The mean of the number of steps is 1.91 across the Type A Case Studies (0.44 in the normalised indicator).

No significant relationship was found between the network distance and the number of actors involved in the network. Looking in more detail at one of the cases with the largest distances (i.e. case ADF), the distance of each actor from all the other actors in the network during the Social Innovation process is approximately 4.3 steps. The network is densest during the Social Innovation project once the relationships between actors is formalised through the approval of the volunteer's decree. In the other case with a similarly large value for network distance, VAZ, the reconfiguring process leads to a significant increase in the density of interactions compared to the previous situation. This is due to the creation of the initiative and the establishment of Cooperative Terra Terra, and the direct involvements of farmers and wider network members. The distance of each actor from all the other actors of the network during the Social Innovation process is 3.5 steps.

Network relationships

The number of new relationships and contacts created within the social innovation network is high in almost all cases (indicator Ea10), with a mean proportion of new contacts created of 71.5% (highest in HAW case with 94% of new contacts, lowest in ADF case with 20% of new contacts). In the case of

HAW, the high figure is related to establishing new agreements between farmers and their consumers. In the case of ADF the low figure is explained by the existing networks of the civil society and the administration with which the network of wildfire volunteers created links.

Internal trust by the network members was assessed as high in all cases (indicator Ea12), with a mean value across cases of 0.83 ± 0.02 . Lower levels of network trust are associated with smaller networks, indicating that the larger the network is the more likely it is to be perceived as trustworthy by its members (Figure 11). Values in this range have also been reported in Type B Cases, such as FLE, in which the trust of the network members is reported as considerable.

Figure 11. The relationship between the normalized indicator Ea12 (Network internal trust) and the full size of the networks (network and core group) in the eleven Type A case studies. (Labels are case study acronyms. The trend line, equation and its goodness of fit are shown). (Source: Section authors).

Trust and sanctions

The contexts of Social Innovation initiatives providing services of common interest (i.e. cases WOM and CAR) or managing environmental or cultural resources (i.e. cases REV and LAG), as well as of those operating within the framework of an international cooperation project (i.e. case DAI), are highly formalised. The fields within which they are operating are usually governed by public rules and regulations with which the Social Innovation initiatives must comply. Therefore, the activities of the Social Innovation require to be closely governed, with formal sanctions in case of noncompliance. This is reflected in the scores for indicators on types of sanctions (OldEc4), which are high for the cases in the United Kingdom and Tunisia (100% and 71.43%, respectively), but "rare" for SEA and FLE cases.

All the other Case Studies indicated "zero sanctions" or did not provide any answer. Most of them refer to "only moral sanctions" for non-compliant actors. This may seem odd but can be explained on further inspection of the interactions between the indicator Ea12 on the level of network's internal trust and Ec4 for level of trust in public institutions of the actors of the Social Innovation process. In general, there were high scores for Ea12 "internal trust", ranging from the lowest of 72% in HAW cases to the highest of 94% in ADF case, with a mean of 84.57%. Trust is an immeasurable success factor of Social Innovation, particularly within the group of core actors. With respect to the level of trust in institutions (indicator Ec4), the initiatives which are perceived as distant to the public sector (i.e. cases HAW, FIN and SEA) score the lowest with 20%, 23.3% and 34% respectively. These scores are associated with a general rejection of public interventions in the field of action concerned (i.e. case FIN), a dismissal of their appropriateness and usefulness (i.e. HAW in response to the Common Agricultural Policy), or a disregard of the relevance of public services except as a cause of hindrance (i.e. case SEA).

By comparison, LUM and FLE cases have the highest scores for the indicator of the level of *trust in institutions* (76%). In LUM case the score is explained by the fact that “*the initiative can be seen....as a successful (but unconscious) anticipation of economic and political processes*”. This is unsurprising given the traditional emphasis on citizen participation and local self-reliance in Switzerland. This also holds true, *mutatis mutandis*, for the relatively high scores for CAR (63.3%) and LAG (58.3%).

The second highest score is for the case DAI (75.4%) in which FAO and a government ministry provide legal security and funding on the basis of contractual arrangements that are characteristic for projects of international development cooperation. A score of 59% for VAZ case may be due to the congregational origin and the backing of the local parish for the initiative. The protective environment of a religious organisation can be effective in a situation in which the initiative cannot count on public support. The case study reveals that VAZ, in its early days, had a lukewarm reception from established agricultural stakeholders.

The other cases lie close to the mean of 49.7% for the score on “*internal trust*”. In particular, the cases that feature a big difference (of approximately 40% and more) between the *internal* and the *external trust* scores (i.e. cases WOM, ADF, REV, FIN, SEA and WOM) seem to confirm that social innovation initiatives thrive mainly in communities of core actors, regardless of the support or reliability of the sphere of influence of public governance. Findings from Types B and C cases show similar results. For example, in case NWF, trust between network members (Agricultural Development Groups, forest community, forest administration, civil society, innovator) was the factor assessed to be the most important for the persistence of the social innovation. However, as the core actors of this case also include governmental organisations, this interpretation should be extended to include trust in institutions.

5.4.4 New attitudes

In almost all the cases, new attitudes have been identified as beliefs and values of actors change during the reconfiguring phase due to new roles, activities, and commitments. In particular, the attitude of Network actors changed and became proactive during the development of the initiative for an average of 81.3% (± 8.1) of the members of the Case Studies, as measured by indicator Eb1, on the level of pro-action of Transformers during the Social Innovation process. The lowest value was recorded was for the LUM case (with a value of 20% of the actors perceived their attitudes as having changed). The highest value was 100% which was recorded for all the cases WOM, SEA, LAG, FIN, FLE and ADF.

There are five indicators to be interpreted with respect to the motivations and behaviours of the members of the network: Db3 (Expertise motivating the engagement of Social Innovation actors), Ca1 (Attractiveness of the Social Innovation idea), Ea1 (Attendance level at meetings in the Social Innovation process), Ea10 (New relationships within the Social Innovation network), and Eb1 (see above). The results for Db3 show that the main reason to motivating the engagement of social innovation actors in the network was their will to share their expertise with the Social Innovation implementation in many case studies, such as WOM, REV, LUM, SEA, and DAI. In other Case Studies, i.e. ADF, VAZ, DAI and FLE, the expertise was judged to be as important as other motivations (e.g. they liked the idea; to serve a good cause; they liked the leadership and charisma of the innovator; to feel personally fulfilled; to receive economic benefits; it was part of the duties of their job; for previous relationships they had with people involved). In the cases of FIN and CAR, the will of network members to contribute their expertise was assessed to be irrelevant. Indicator Ca1 shows the extent to which the attractiveness of the social innovation idea was the main driver for network members to get involved in the Social Innovation. For the cases of WOM, SEA, LUM, FIN, DAI, LAG, REV and FLE the attractiveness of the idea for actors was the main reason to get involved in the network. There are also high values for the indicator for the ADF, VAZ and CAR case studies, intimating that the appeal of the idea led to a high share of the actors becoming involved.

5.4.5 New governance arrangements

Results show that the network actors of the eleven Type A Case Studies investigated used different combinations of governance arrangements (e.g. mutual informal agreements, direct supervision, formal rules, or other additional ways developed during the process), often in combination within a single case. The main formal and informal arrangements set up in different cases are listed in Table 5.

Table 5. Main formal and informal rules adopted across the eleven Type A Case Studies.

	Case Study Acronym	Most Common Informal Rule	Most Common Formal Rule
1	VAZ	Verbal agreements	Designed protocols
2	HAW	Meeting participation and coordination	Declaration of membership
3	REV	Defining tasks and responsibilities	Co-ordination and partners invitation
4	WOM	N.a	Co-operative organisational structure
5	LAG	Internal functioning	Application procedures
6	LUM	Relationship across members	Official project reporting
7	SEA	Relationship across members	Standardisation of work processes
8	CAR	Management	Standardisation of work processes
9	DAI	N.a	Formal protocols
10	FIN	Mutual respect	Co-operative organisational structure
11	ADF	Meeting participation and coordination	N.a

(Source: Section authors).

During the reconfiguring process the main form of tension that emerged was internal conflicts within the network of actors which moved forward with the initiative (e.g. breaching agreements, scepticism, exiting of core actors from the initiative), and conflicts between opposing interests' groups (e.g. collaborationists versus isolationists, developers versus preservers) (**Figure 12.**). By contrast, in at least two cases, no conflicts or tensions emerged (i.e. cases LAG and SEA), where the Community Development Officer (i.e. case LAG) and the commitment of the core group of innovators (i.e. case SEA) ensured an effective coordination and cooperation during the reconfiguring phase. FLE case is an example of a social innovation process in which conflicts could not be resolved. Changes in the State Council representatives created irresolvable frictions with the core of actors involved in the initiative, which then affected the overall trust local actors had in the Cantonal administration.

Figure 12. Main forms of conflicts and frictions that arose in the eleven Type A Case Studies (Source: Section authors).

The case LAG in the United Kingdom is peculiar. After network's initial discussions with the Forestry Commission and steps towards acquisition of the woodland between 1995 and 2000 had been stopped by a government change in 2000, conditions in the institutional framework became favourable again with a number of provisions being made with respect to legal (Land Reform 2003/16; Forest Land Scheme 2005; Community Empowerment Act 2015; Community Asset Transfer Scheme 2015), financial, informational, and networking support (subsidies from Highland and Island Enterprise/HIE; LEADER). This policy and governance change then appeared to be providing a "motorway" for social innovations to happen. As with the other cases, a distinction can be made between those with a high score of 0.83 (in a range of 0 to 1) for indicator F4 "change in internal and external governance arrangements of the social innovation initiative as perceived by the actors of the social innovation process" (i.e. case WOM, CAR and REV) from those with values from 0 to 0.33 (i.e. cases HAW, LUM, FIN and ADF). Case DAI has a lower value of 0.67.

The scores for LUM, ADF and VAZ cases seem to be inconsistent. However, the explanation provided by Swiss respondents is that "social innovation demonstrates a scarce ability to generate changes in governance." In ADF case, the changes in network density and other governance parameters over time were deemed "moderate". For the observer, the moderate rating of both cases may have to do with their long-time span. Over the years, many things tend to be taken for granted which had once been praised as trailblazing innovations. The actors of VAZ case value highly the impact of their networks on the territory; at the same time, they sense that they still have a lot of growth potential, particularly by reaching out to the public sector, which they have not done thus far.

These findings correspond with the values for the indicator I10 perceptions of actors of the level of improvement in governance aspects due to the social innovation initiative, which remains below the mean of 52% in HAW, ADF, FIN, SEA and VAZ cases. The low scores in the Austrian (i.e. HAW) and Finnish (i.e. FIN) cases can be explained by the distance of the former to the public sector and the controversial stance of the latter to the political mainstream (FIN has the lowest score of 11.11%). For ADF and VAZ cases, the duration of the process may be an explanation. High scores for improvements in governance were given by the informants from CAR case (100%), WOM case (76.92%), DAI case (72.22%) and REV case (70%). The score for LAG case is lower (50%), and no score was obtained for LUM case, but reference was made to "some improvement in respect to stakeholder consultations."

5.5 Cross-case Observations

Checks were made on emerging trends which arose in the reconfiguring processes in otherwise what were diverse cases of social innovation with different durations, fields of action, and visions. A particular focus was on understanding what might explain the variation across cases of the internal network and governance mechanisms of the social innovations, principally considering: i) the duration of the reconfiguring process or of the social innovation as a whole; ii) the size of the network.

All of the cases studied show evidence of at least one reconfiguring process which involves the creation or strengthening of new networks, relationships, or governance arrangements. The number of developments undergone during the reconfiguring phase is often limited to one or a few main changes, primarily related to the creation/strengthening/enlargement of the network of actors, and to the development of new relationships and contacts. Therefore, the network emerges as a key element for social innovation actions since its structure determines the overall effectiveness of the social innovation process.

The network dimension plays a role in regulating the internal dynamics of the social innovation initiatives studied. While the level of mutual collaborations and their connectedness appears to be independent from the network size, findings from the cross-case analysis shows that larger networks tend to disperse the reputational power across members more intensely than smaller ones, indicating that the reputation of the core network group could be perceived as a less relevant feature for a social innovation process involving a larger number of actors. This can be linked to the fact that in larger networks, delegating tasks and responsibilities is essential for the long-term stability of the related initiatives. Delegation is most effective in safeguarded social innovation in larger networks. This rationale is aligned with the finding showing that larger networks are also associated with higher perceived levels of internal trust in the network. The analysis shows that once networks enlarge during the reconfiguring process, they can reach a maximum size which is steady, the social innovation initiative having achieved maturity and a stable critical mass. However, networks can also intensify internal conflicts over the long term, especially between different interest groups and diverse groups of actors involved in the initiative.

Results show there are changes of attitudes in the case studies analysed which occur mainly during the reconfiguring process. Often, new governance arrangements have been set up using a combination of both formal and informal arrangements.

6. Checking the Hypothesis of Diverging Paths Across Case Studies

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6.1 Introduction

The scope of this Section is to check the hypothesis of diverging paths (DPs) across the case studies. Using the version of the Diverging Paths model, which was used to run the analysis in Task 5.3 in all of the Case Studies, the aim of this Section is to compare the data collected across Case Studies regarding the development of the initiatives, in order to support the contribution to the empirical testing of the Diverging Paths. This comparison is based on the theoretical models, indicators, and empirical analysis developed by SIMRA within Work Packages 2, 3, 4, and 5, and previously reported in Secco *et al.* (2019; D4.3), and Marini Govigli *et al.* (2019; D5.3).

The theoretical model on dimensions of divergence developed within Work Packages 2 and 3 is linked with: i) the discussions about the theoretical trajectories of Social Innovation developed within Work Package 2; ii) the indicators for scaling up and scaling out developed in Work Package 4 (Secco *et al.* 2019; D4.3); and iii) the data collected and analysed on those indicators and on the divergence paths done by the Case Studies in Work Package 5 (Marini Govigli *et al.*, 2019; D5.3).

The analysis explores the development of the Social Innovation initiatives identified across the Case Studies. To do this, the models of development represented in the SIMRA Case Studies were identified, and the interactions between those models of development and the dimensions of divergence paths (DPPs).

6.2 Conceptual and Analytical Framework

The dimensions of divergence refer both to the reconfiguration of social practice and the types of elements involved in the Social Innovation (e.g. type of actors, type of knowledge involved, etc.) defined in Work Packages 2 and 3. They include a range of multi-factor dimensions that characterise the diversification of Social Innovation in marginalised rural areas. These are the types of actors and knowledge that created and developed the initiative, expansion of the Social Innovation in terms of the dynamics of its institutional evolution, the nature of the activities that ensure the sustainability of the Social Innovation, depth of change of the Social Innovation dynamics, and degradation. It should be noted that degradation of the Social Innovation has not been included in the analysis because there are no data available within the Case Studies. Table 6 contains all the dimensions explored and the categories used for their analysis.

To characterise the models of development, the development of the initiative has been studied from its evolution and implementation through to the creation of systemic change. This includes the evolution of the activities implemented (i.e. diversification of activities) and the growing and scaling stage of the social innovation process (Murray *et al.*, 2010). "Growing and scaling" refers to a critical stage of the social innovation process, which is considered within the SIMRA theoretical framework of Social Innovation in marginalised rural areas (Klůvanková *et al.*, 2017; D2.2).

For the purposes of this analysis, the focus was on the features that represent the main possible directions of growth of the Social Innovation in terms of activities, expansion and influence. Four features relating to the evolution of the initiative have been considered for analysing the "growing and scaling" stage: diversification, business orientation, scaling up processes and scaling out processes. Diversification and business orientation refer to features internal to the initiative, while scaling up and out refer to development beyond the original initiative. Diversification refers to taking up the development of new activities that are substantially different from the original focus of the initiative. An initiative is business-oriented when the activity is developed within market systems and seeks to produce income. Scaling up and scaling out are understood as moving the innovation to a broader system (scaling up) and replicating it in different locations (scaling out) (Secco *et al.*, 2017; D4.2).

Eight theoretical models of development result from the combination of the features scaling up, scaling out, and diversification of activities: “Original form”, “Diversifying”, “Scaling out”, “Scaling up”, “Scaling Up and Out”, “Scaling Up and Diversifying”, “Scaling Out and Diversifying”, and “Scaling Up and Out and Diversifying” (see Table 6).

Table 6. Theoretical models of the development of Social Innovation initiatives.¹⁰

Model		Features
Original form	No scaling up, no scaling out and no diversification	
Diversifying	Diversification, but no scaling up or scaling out	
Scaling out	Scaling out, but no scaling up or diversification	
Scaling up	Scaling up, but no scaling out or diversification	

¹⁰ Column 3 of Table 6 has a slightly different formulation of the wording for scaling out (referred in the figure as Out-scaling) and scaling up (referred to as Upscaling).

Scaling up and out	Scaling up and scaling out but no diversification	
Scaling up and diversifying	Scaling up and diversification, but no scaling out	
Scaling out and diversifying	Scaling out and diversification, but no scaling up	
Scaling up and out and diversifying	Scaling up, scaling out and diversification	

(Source: Section authors)

The models of the development of Social Innovation can be associated with different stages of the process of the development of Social Innovation (Figure 13.). At one end of the spiral, the “Original form” model of development reflects a Social Innovation initiative which has not evolved (yet) and continues with its original activities. It follows a model of no scaling up, no scaling out and no diversification. In relation to the spiral model, it corresponds to an initiative still in the stage of development and implementation.

At the other end of the spiral, the “Scaling up and out and diversifying” model of development corresponds to an initiative which has diversified its portfolio of activities, reached a broader level (scaled up), and spread to other territories (scaled out). The diffusion of the initiative has occurred across scales, spaces, and activities. Between these two models there are six other combinations that would correspond to different positions within the spiral stage of “growing, scaling and spreading”. All of these present some evolution in at least one of the three features. In three of the theoretical models,

the original initiative evolved in only one direction by diversifying its activities (“Diversifying”), being adopted or adapted in other places while maintaining the original activity (“Scaling”) or scaling up while remaining the same original activity (“Scaling”). The other three theoretical models reflect evolution in two directions. “Scaling up and out” refers to an initiative that while (still) maintaining its activities as originally designed, spreads across levels and places. “Scaling Up and Diversifying” refer to an initiative that is growing its portfolio of activities while moving to a broader system, but without signs of being implemented in other places. “Out scaling and Diversifying” refers to an initiative that is growing its portfolio of activities while being adopted in other places but without any signs of being scaled up (yet).

Two aspects should be noted when using these models of development in the analysis:

- As pointed out by Murray *et al.* (2010), there is no single path to systemic change, but there is potential for it to arise from the various models of development described above.
- There are partial overlaps between some dimensions and features analysed. For example, the dimension “expansion” could be part of the “trajectories,” and the “business orientation” partially overlaps with the assurance of viability. These overlaps are considered when explaining the results in Section 3.2.

Figure 13. Models of development in the Social Innovation spiral. (Source: Section authors based on Kluvánková *et al.*, 2017).

The dimensions of divergence considered in the analysis are the types of actors and knowledge, expansion, assurance of viability and depth of change, the Social Innovation features business orientation, scaling up, scaling out, and diversification, as defined in Work Package 2 and 3 (Table 7).

Table 7. Analytical dimensions and data.

Analytical Dimensions		Definition / Theoretical Understanding	Categorisation
Dimensions of Divergence	Types of actors and knowledge	Key actors that create and develop the Social Innovation.	Categories L1, L2, E1 and E2
	Expansion	Institutional evolution dynamic	Categories colony formation, modular-polycentric, and viral
	Assurance of viability	Type of activities that assure the sustainability or consolidation of the Social Innovation	Categories Public responsibility, market, civic engagement, and combination
	Depth of change	Institutionalisation / Consolidation of Social Innovation dynamics	Categories Adaptive and Transformative
Models of Development	Business orientation	The activity is developed within the market systems the purpose of which is to generate income.	Yes / No
	Up scaling	Moving the innovation to a broader system (Secco <i>et al.</i> , 2017; D4.2)	Yes / No
	Out scaling	Replication of the same innovation in different locations (Secco <i>et al.</i> , 2017; D4.2)	Yes / No
	Diversification of activities	Taking up the development of new activities different to the original	Yes/ No

(Source: SIMRA 2019, pp.15-16; Secco *et al.* 2017, D4.2 ; Section authors).

The data used for the cross-case assessment of the dimension of divergence was taken from the assessment of the Case Studies reported in the individual Case Study reports (Marini Govigli *et al.*, 2019; D5.3) and summarised in Work Packages 2 and 3 (Table 8).

Table 8. Summary of dimensions of divergence in Type A Case Studies in SIMRA.

Diverging Paths Characteristics		HAW	FIN	ADF	VAZ	REV	WOM	CAR	SEA	LUM	DAI	LAG
Type of Actors and Knowledge	L1	D	Min	D	D	Min	D	D	Mod	Min	Min	D
	L2	D	Mod	N.A.	D	Mod	Mod	Mod	Min	D	Mod	Mod
	E1	Min	D	Min	Mod	D	N.A.	Min	D	Mod	D	Mod
	E2	Mod	Mod	Mod	N.A.	Min	N.A.	Min	Mod	Mod	Mod	Mod
Collective Action/ Type of Expansion in Social Innovation	Viral	N.A.	Potential	N.A.	Minor	Min	N.A.	D	D	N.A.	Min	Mod
	Modular-polycentric	NA	Mod	D	N.A.	D	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	D	Min
	Colony	Min	N.A.	N.A.	D	Min	D	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	Min	D
Type of Viability Assurance	Public	Min	Min	D	Mod	Mod	D	Mod	N.A.	Mod	Mod	Mod
	Market	Mod	Min	N.A.	Min	Min	D	Min	D	Min	Min	Mod
	Civic	D	D	D	D	D	Mod	D	D	Mod	D	D
Depth of Change	Adaptive	Min	D	N.A.	D	D	Mod	D	D	D	D	N.A.
	Transformative	N.A.	Min	D	N.A.	Min	D	Min	N.A.	N.A.	Min	D

D = Dominant; Mod = Moderate; Min= Minimal, P = Potential, N.A. = No appearance

(Source: SIMRA 2019, pp.26-27).

In addition to Type A cases analysed, information can be retrieved from the Types B and C cases. ARG shows dominance both in the presence of local actors with local knowledge (L1) and external actors with local knowledge (E1); a colony expansion into twelve connected co-operatives to overcome the

issue of the difficulty of women travelling to reach the co-operative headquarters; the viability is assured by a well-thought out economic and marketing model; an adaptive depth of change.

Similarly, case HER has both internal and external actors, and expects to have a viral expansion of its model throughout The Netherlands. It assures its viability through a combination of public responsibility, remunerative service and civic engagement of volunteers and leading stakeholders, as well as through economic return. It is aiming to achieve “transformative” regime change.

The CRO case is driven by a local actor and with considerable local knowledge (L1). The social innovation is characterized by a colony type of expansion model, concerned with a novel form of civic partnership and collaboration based on established regional collaboration for sustainable rural tourism and life. CRO has transformative characteristics, scaling out to other marginalised rural areas.

The NWF case is driven by external actors with external knowledge (e.g. FAO), and local actors with local knowledge (i.e. the local communities). It is characterized by rapid diffusion and multiplication of its model within or out with its territory. No institutionalization or consolidation of the dynamics of social innovation have been observed thus far. In terms of degradation, micro failures of specific micro-enterprises have been observed, but not affecting the overall effectiveness of the social innovation scheme.

The information regarding the features of the Social Innovation pathways was extracted from Individual Case Study Reports using a deductive analysis. For this analysis, a table was completed for each Case Study with information from the corresponding report. Two independent deductive analyses were performed on the information in the tables, the aim of which was to indicate if there was evidence of the presence of the features in the Social Innovations. In the cases where there was a discrepancy between the two analyses, the results were reviewed by the two evaluators to reconcile the characterisation based on further evidence from the Case Study reports, where appropriate. The results of these analysis are summarised in Table 9.

Table 9. Assessment of the dimensions of the models of development in the Type A Case Studies.

Case Study	Scale-up	Scale-out	Diversification of Activities	Business Orientation
HAW	No	No	Yes	Yes
FIN	No	No	No	No
ADF	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
VAZ	Yes	Yes	No	No
REV	No	No	No	No
WOM	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
CAR	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
SEA	No	No	No	Yes
LUM	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
DAI	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
LAG	No	Yes	Yes	Yes

(Source: Section authors based on evidence from case study reports).

Using the characterisation of the Case Studies from Table 9, and an exploratory approach to the configurational of the development of the initiatives, relationships have been identified between the models of development and the diverging paths. The configurational approach is an analysis of “conceptually distinct characteristics that commonly occur together” (Meyer *et al.*, 1993), and a methodology to compare small-N or intermediate-N in a research strategy based on multiple Case Studies (Rihoux and Ragin, 2009). In this case, the “conceptually distinct characteristics” are the attributes ‘diversification’, ‘scaling up’ and ‘scaling out’, the dimensions of divergence, and the diverging paths. As it is exploratory, only the existence of connections between the attributes has been

identified. Exploring the existence of necessary and satisfactory relationships between the resulting sets is beyond the scope of this Deliverable.

The next section presents the main findings of the cross-case analysis starting with a characterisation of the models of development identified in the Case Studies. Then, it compares them with the dimensions of divergence and hypothesis on diverging paths.

6.3 Results of the Cross-case Study Analysis

This section reports on the qualitative assessment of the models of development. Common trends in the patterns of development of the Social Innovation have been identified across the cases. Six models of development are represented in the Type A Case Studies, but there are no examples for the “Scaling out” and “scaling up” models.

- The model of development “**Original form**” is exemplified by three initiatives: FIN, REV and SEA cases had not evolved from their initial form so it could be said they are contained in the implementation stage. This could be attributed to their relatively recent implementation. They may yet reach stages of diversification and scaling up/out.
- The model of development “**Diversifying**” is exemplified by one initiative: HAW case did not scale up/out, but diversified its activities, adding activities to the original Community Supported Agriculture such as workshops and seminars in a range of topics, particularly on fermentation.
- The model of development of “**Scaling up and out**” is represented by two initiatives: VAZ and DAI cases, which had scaled up and out with different prospects. DAI case scaled up through improved technical practices in one of the cooperatives participating in the original project, which would have founded a Central Union of Co-operatives at governorate level, and it scaled out by spreading to other sectors (fishing). VAZ case had already reached certain impact at higher scales and has been replicated outside the local territory.
- The model of development of “**Scaling Up and Diversifying**” (diversification and scaling up) characterizes WOM case. It has developed beyond the original initiative form but has not yet been spread to other areas or sectors. It has already diversified its focus, expanding the activities to elderly care, and has shown impacts of upscaling.
- There are two Case Studies which exemplify the model “**Scaling Out and Diversifying**”: case LAG. In both Case Studies there is a diversification of activities and scaling out, but not scaling up. LAG case’s development demonstrates diversification with the development of different projects related to woodland management and in particular the development of a dairy unit. Regarding its out scaling, it is evident that LAG is part of wider processes, with similar projects existing in other parts of the United Kingdom.
- There are two Case Studies that are already in an “**Up and Out scaling and Diversifying**” Social Innovation model: ADF, LUM and CAR cases. Arguably, ADF and LUM are the oldest initiatives within the SIMRA Case Studies, so they have had more time to develop in all directions and reach societal change. LUM case scaled up, reaching the national level aggregated into a body with similar initiatives which was scaled out and which diversified its activities through *Ir Novas Vias* which reoriented and broadened its scope. ADF case scaled out from the original localities involved to other places across Catalonia, and then scaled up with the creation of the *Secretariat d’Agrupacions de Defensa Forestal* at the Catalan level and its recognition of legal status. These Case Studies indicated that there has been diversification of activities beyond the fire extinguishing and prevention. For the Dutch case CAR, it can be considered out scaling as the idea was in some form adopted by others. It scaled up in terms of growing size. Moreover, over time, the farming system and included more ways of green care.

Considering this configuration of the models of development (as summarized in Table 10), the dimension “diversification” appears as the central element in the articulation of the different models. It is possible for a Social Innovation initiative to diversify its initial activities without scaling up or scaling out (e.g. the HAW case, “Diversifying” model). However, scaling up and scaling out processes do not appear as independent processes in Social Innovations in marginalised rural areas, but rather always occur in conjunction with either the other scaling process or the diversification of activities. From this perspective, it is possible to cluster the models of development depending on the configuration of diversification in the model: no diversification, only diversification, or diversification+ (diversification of activities with scaling up or scaling out)

Regarding the **business orientation**, as mentioned in the description of the models of development, in theory there is scope in all the models both for initiatives that are business-oriented and those that are not. Nevertheless, the distribution of Case Studies shows that there are certain models of development more linked to businesses than other (i.e. cases SEA, HAW, WOM, CAR, LAG, and DAI). SEA, HAW, WOM and CAR cases could be broadly defined as businesses themselves. SEA case aims to develop an alternative market model for the fishing industry that promotes environmental sustainability. HAW case is a private company although building in consumer engagement. WOM case is a social cooperative seeking to generate income for women farmers through the creation of jobs and entrepreneurship LAG case has set up a trading arm to manage the selling of wood, although not the focus of the initiative. In the case DAI, although it is considered as a programme contract and not a business, it targeted small-scale dairy sector producers to help them enhance their production and trading activities. The non-business-oriented initiatives are FIN, REV, ADF and LUM cases since the focus of their initiatives are in the civic or public sector. VAZ case is not business-oriented, but the reported creation of a cooperative to provide extension services could indicate that it is preparing to reorient its activity towards the private sector.

Considering the distribution of initiatives in the growing, scaling, and spreading stage, two trends are evident. First, the initiatives which have already evolved from the original implementation but have not grown in all directions (up and out scaling and diversifying) are all business-oriented apart from VAZ case. As mentioned, VAZ case could be reorienting towards business as well through the reported provision of extension services. This could indicate that being a business initiative pushes the growing and scaling process forward. However, the lack of evidence of business-oriented initiatives in the “Scaling Up and Out and Diversifying” model could mean that there is a limit to the growing push which could be related to, for example, reaching the income target or other market-related goals which the initiative sought. Apart from VAZ case, non-business-oriented initiatives only appear within the Type A Case Studies in the models “Original form” (i.e. cases FIN and REV) and “Scaling Up and Out and Diversifying” (i.e. cases ADF and LUM). This could indicate that initiatives which were originally non-business-oriented have to lean towards the market in order to grow and spread.

Table 10. Social Innovation initiatives in the Type A Case Studies which are in the Growing, Scaling and Spreading stage.

Types of Model of Development	Original Implementation (original form)	Diversification	Diversification + (diversification and scaling up or scaling out)	No Diversification (scaling up and scaling out)	Scaling Up and Out and Diversifying
Business oriented	SEA	HAW	WOM, CAR, LAG,	DAI	---
Not business oriented	FIN, REV	--	--	VAZ	ADF, LUM

(Source: Section authors).

6.4 How Models of Development Inform Diverging Paths

This section focuses on identifying the existing connections between the dimensions of divergence and model of development. At the time of the cross-case study analysis, Tasks 2.2 and 3.3 were finalising the formulation of five diverging paths (DPs) (A1, A2, B, C1, and C2), from the combination of the dimensions of divergence (DPPs). A preliminary assessment of the Case Studies conducted according to Work Packages 2 and 3 assigned the Case Studies to each one of those diverging paths appearing in Table 11.

Table 11. Classification of the Type A Case Studies in the diverging paths

Diverging Path	Description	Case Studies
A1	Social Innovation emerges as an endogenous community initiative or individual actions of local actors with local knowledge (Type L1), through colony formation. It often develops from informal institutions. It can be developed further by the community. Self-organised groups may stay as stillborn Social Innovations. An important characteristic is that this diverging path arises naturally from bottom up with a high level of commitment and determination of an individual and positive social capital of the community. It may be consolidated as a local civic institution which may be adaptive and provide benefits within the local context.	ADF, HAW, LAG
A2	Social Innovation refers to an endogenous community initiative of local actors /knowledge, Type L1 L2. Social Innovations emerge by colony, develop as a viral novel practice, as informal institutions, and create new socially oriented business (model which produces benefits for the community and externally, such as to disadvantaged groups and customers (e.g. social farming, social enterprises, community supermarket, etc.). It may be adaptive or transformative. May scale out from place of origin.	CAR, WOM
B	Local actors and mix of local and external knowledge (Type L2) initiate social innovation via colony and/or modular/polycentric formation which may be adaptive or transformative. New forms of public, market and civic cooperation emerge using knowledge transfer (e.g. foreign experiences and codified knowledge) and will, at the end of the observed period, remain an association of volunteers.	VAZ, LUM, VIL
C1	External actor/external knowledge (Type E) initiates social innovation as modular or polycentric expansion, through formal and informal networks. Transfers and exchange of specific knowledge related to the Marginalised Rural Areas, or topic of Social Innovation, is essential. Institutions of co-operation and participation that are formal in nature are related to the success of Social Innovations, together with education and capacity building. Results are mainly transformative change which will establish as market- or public sector-oriented institutions.	--
C2	External actor local knowledge (Type E1) initiates social innovation as modular, polycentric expansion. Transfer and exchange of specific knowledge related to the Marginalised Rural Areas, or topic of Social Innovation, is essential. Combination of formal institutions of co-operation and participation with informal trust and social capital are related to the success of the Social Innovations. Results mainly of adaptive change to improve the well-being of the community (e.g. social training, new social services etc.).	FIN, SEA, REV, DAI

(Source: SIMRA 2019, pp.15 to 16; Section authors).

A cross-analysis of the diverging paths, and the models of development and ideas explored above, contributes to the description of the diverging paths (see Table 12 and Figure 14) in which:

- Diverging path A1 comprises initiatives with the types of development “Scaling up and out and diversifying”, “Diversifying”, and “Scaling out and diversifying”. The diversification of activities is a feature shared by those three models.
- Diverging path A2 comprises diversification which appears in the models of development, although always with some scaling process, illustrating the trend noted above as “diversification plus”.
- Diverging path C2 includes initiatives with models of development “Original form” and “Scaling Up and Out”, which is models in which there is no sign of diversification.
- In the case of Diverging path B, the shared feature amongst the models of development which was included (Scaling up and out and Scaling up and out and diversifying) does not centre upon diversification, but rather upon the existence of both scaling up and scaling out processes.

Table 12. Features common to the models of development in the diverging paths.

Diverging Path	Model of Development	Shared Features in the Models
A1	Scaling up and out and diversifying	Diversification or Diversification +
	Diversifying	
	Scaling out and diversifying	
A2	Scaling out and diversifying	Diversification +
	Scaling up and diversifying	
B	Scaling up and out	Scaling up and scaling out
	Scaling up and out and diversifying	
C1	---	--
C2	Original form	No diversification
	Scaling up and out	

(Source: Section authors).

Patterns can be interpreted amongst the Diverging paths with respect to the spiral model of social innovation (Figure 14). Diverging Path A1 could cover the entire spectrum within the upwards growing and spreading stage. There is no evidence of an initiative in the model of development of original form in this diverging path, but there also no evidence which indicates that it cannot arise. Diverging Path A2 represents models of development, which are in the growing phase. Diverging Path B could represent the part of the growing and spreading stage with initiatives that have scaled up and out, which indicates the creation of impact beyond the original scope of the social innovation initiative. Diverging Path C2 represents the starting point of the growing and spreading stage, with models of development that have not evolved from the original design or which are diversifying their activity.

Figure 14. Distribution of the Type A Case Studies in the spiral model of Social Innovation process. (Source: Section authors based on Kluvánková *et al.*, 2017; D2.2).

6.5 Cross-case Observations

The key findings of this cross-case study analysis revealed the following trends on the models of development amongst the Case Studies, which might contribute to the hypotheses on the diverging paths of Social Innovations in marginalised rural areas.

- The diversification of activities is a central element in the evolution of the Social Innovation initiatives. In particular, it is possible for a social innovation to diversify its original design without scaling up or scaling out.
- In the set of Case Studies analysed in SIMRA, scaling up and scaling out processes always occur jointly with either one another, or with diversification of activities, but never on their own.
- Business initiatives tend to facilitate the growing and scaling processes. However, there could be limits to that process which would limit its capacity to reach a completed scaling up and out and diversifying model.
- The models of development of the Case Studies analysed in SIMRA provide evidence to support the theoretical classification of the diverging paths developed by SIMRA, locating the diverging paths in different stages of the social innovation spiral model (see **Figure 15**).

Figure 15. Distribution of the diverging paths in the spiral model of Social Innovation process. (Source: Section authors, based on Kluvánková *et al.*, 2017; D2.2).

7. Social Innovation Impacts

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7.1 Introduction

The Section aims to identify the impacts of the social innovation initiatives and to analyse them across the cases. We have evaluated social innovation impacts across cases in relation to components of territorial capital in marginalised rural areas focusing on the social, economic, environmental and institutional/political (governance) dimensions. To analyse impacts empirical data assessed in Task 5.3 have been used, triangulated mainly with quantitative information (e.g. indicators). The comparison across the cases is based on the theoretical framework, indicators and empirical analysis developed within Work Package 4 (Secco *et al.*, 2017; D4.2; Secco *et al.*, 2019; D4.3) and Work Package 5 (Marini Govigli *et al.*, 2019; D.5.3). These were used together with qualitative data reported in the Individual Case Study Reports to inform the identification of common patterns relating to the effects of social innovation.

The Section is organised into four parts: the conceptual framework presents the concepts used to analyse the impacts of social innovations across the cases; the analytical framework discusses the approach used to derive common patterns and main findings; the result illustrates the findings of the cross-case analysis; and the final part describes the main trends identified and conclusions.

7.2 Conceptual Framework

According to the SIMRA theoretical and evaluation framework, the term “impacts of social innovation” means “long-term and widespread effects of Social Innovation at the rural territory level” (Secco *et al.*, 2017, D4.2). Generally, these are positive, but social innovation could also lead to negative impacts. These changes of state within the system context (Emerson *et al.*, 2011: 18) for communities (both direct and indirect beneficiaries) result from the accumulation of outcomes. In marginalised rural areas, they can be related to the enhancement of social cohesion and human well-being, competitiveness, self-organisation and resilience, higher education, and skills (Polman *et al.*, 2017; D2.1). Since marginalisation is a process of socio-economic decline and political disempowerment of certain regions in which production conditions are less favourable, the impacts of social innovation could be assessed in terms of counter tendencies to this process, as Lourenco, *et al.* (1998) describe in their work on the assessment of social interventions.

There are four main domains under investigation in the cross-case analysis of impacts on societal well-being: society, economy, environment and institutions/governance.

The **social dimension of impacts** refers to any change in society, whether adverse or beneficial, which result in whole or in part from the activities, products, or services delivered by the social innovation in the marginalised rural area. The literature reviewed focuses mainly on social capital. Many recent studies have focused on the ability of social capital to enhance development in areas characterised by socio-economic marginality (Marquardt *et al.*, 2012). Sabatini (2009) proposes evaluating social capital according to five dimensions: strong family ties (bonding), weak informal ties (bridging), active political participation, and civic awareness. The social dimension of impacts distinguished social innovations from other forms of innovation, and to which the other dimensions of impacts relate.

The **economic dimension of impacts** refers to effects on both the actors working for the Social Innovation project (e.g. project parents, network), and those working and living in the territory in which the Social Innovation initiative is established, who may have benefited indirectly from the economic performance by the activities, products, and services provided in the Social Innovation. According to Nicholls *et al.* (2012), possible economic impacts are linked to reductions in inequality and improvement in wellbeing by the incorporation of social, environmental, and economic costs and

benefits or, as the OECD framework proposes, an increase in social welfare. All the literature reviewed on the economic impacts of social innovation links economic performance to social wellbeing.

The **environmental dimension of impacts** refers to solving societal and environmental issues which are not being addressed by current systems (Science Communication Unit, 2014). Social innovation can enhance win-win situations for society and the environment as preserving nature does not hinder socio-economic wellbeing (Schartinger *et al.*, 2017; D6.3). Examples of target issues for social innovation which impact on the environment are: producing renewable energy and distributing such energy and its revenues equally, fairly and ethically; improving sustainable mobility models; reducing waste and altering mass consumption models; and, indirectly, improving skills and awareness, as well as educational initiatives can influence environmental outcomes (e.g. a European Union social innovation academy).

The **institutional and governance dimension of impacts** refers to improvements in the coordination amongst actors, including public administrations and policy makers. BEPA (2013) notes that social innovation paves the way to the creation of collaborative, informal platforms or programmes, capacity building, benchmarking and impact measurement, good public services, modernisation of public administrations, faster setting of standards, and new information and communication technologies. BEPA (2013) also refers to experimentation with new institutional models based on social innovation, the creation of enduring partnerships between the private and public sectors and making corporate social responsibility a systematic and essential element of the analysis and operating mode of all businesses.

Emerson *et al.* (2012. P. 2) proposed the concept of “collaborative governance” as “the processes and structures of public policy decision making and management that engage people constructively across the boundaries of public agencies, levels of government, and/or the public, private, and civic spheres in order to carry out a public purpose that could not otherwise be accomplished.” They also describe it as “a system in which cross-boundary collaboration [among organisations/actors/sectors/levels/scales represents the predominant mode to conduct decision making and activity”. From the literature reviewed, one of the impacts of social innovation is the transition to ways of collaborating and structuring governance.

7.3 Analytical Framework

The impact indicators developed in WP4, and as used in the assessments in the Individual Case Study Reports (Task 5.3), have been used to identify similarities and differences across cases with respect to the four impact domains (Table 13). They represent the perspective of the interviewee about the impacts that social innovation initiatives have had on their territory. The cross-case analysis considers the following aspects of impacts: impacts on the marginalization; overall impacts; impacts inside and outside the territory; and social, economic, environmental, and institutional/ governance impacts.

Table 13. Indicators considered for the analysis of impacts

Code	Indicator label	Value Range
I3	Proportion of marginalisation problems improved by the Social Innovation initiative, as perceived by stakeholders	[0-1]
I11	Perceptions of actors of the level of improvement in European societal challenges due to the Social Innovation initiative ¹¹	[0-1]
I6	Level of effects of the Social Innovation initiative in the four domains according to the actors	[0-1]
I7	Level of effects of the Social Innovation initiative inside the territory in the four domains according to the actors	[0-1]

¹¹ Identified in the Europe 2020 strategy <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/societal-challenges>

I8	Level of effects of the Social Innovation initiative outside the territory in the four domains according to the actors	[0-1]
Hb1	Deadweight effects of the Social Innovation initiative in the territory	[0-1]
I4	Proportion of the number of impacts of the Social Innovation initiative in the four domains which were positive, according to the stakeholders	[0-1]

(Source: Section authors).

An assessment of the impacts in the Austrian case (i.e. HAW) has been difficult due to the small-scale of the initiative. The initiative of community supported agriculture (CSA) focuses on the individual needs of the group of harvest-sharers and does not aim to satisfy the needs of the territory.

The impacts are also difficult to assess in the Finnish and Slovakian cases (i.e. FIN and REV), because the social innovation projects to be evaluated are too early in their development. In the Greek case (i.e. SEA) it has been acknowledged that the indirect beneficiaries are the local fishing community, and wider society through improved marine ecosystem services. However, the small size of the initiative means that it has not had a high impact on the elements of marginalisation.

7.4 Results

The analysis of impacts across the cases has shown that social innovation in marginalised rural areas has substantially improved the overall conditions of the territories and of the communities in which social innovation appears. It has contributed to a reduction in the loss of skills and emigration, and at the same time increased socio-economic and cultural liveability of the rural communities, with an aim of the preservation of the territory, the environment and its assets, and contributing to the improvement in overall societal wellbeing.

Impacts of social innovation on the aspect of marginalisation

Two indicators were used to evaluate the social innovation impacts on Marginalised Rural Areas: I3 “Proportion of marginalisation problems improved by the Social Innovation initiative, as perceived by stakeholders” and I11 “Perceptions of actors of the level of improvement in European societal challenges due to the Social Innovation initiative” (Table 13, see values in Appendix 2). Indicator I3 measures the proportion of marginalisation problems improved by the Social Innovation initiative, as perceived by stakeholders. Indicator I11 measures the perceptions of actors of the level of improvement in European societal challenges due to the social innovation initiative within the territory in which it is implemented. Considering the values of I3, the cases may be divided into two groups: those recognising a high degree of influence of the social innovation initiative over the improvement of the situation (i.e. cases WOM, FIN, CAR and FLE) and those acknowledging that the initiative could not have impacted the marginalisation situation directly (i.e. cases SEA, VAZ and LUM). Two cases lie in between these two group. The Slovakian case (i.e. REV) registered a high value for the indicator I3, and the Tunisian case (i.e. DAI) had a value of the indicator which was towards the middle of the range of the values of the indicator for all cases. More detailed information regarding which aspects of marginalisation have been tackled are provided in the following paragraph, reporting the impacts in each domain.

Considering indicator I11, the cases report high values of indicator I3 with a mean of 0.81. The highest values are reported in the Swiss, UK and Finnish cases (i.e. CAR, LAG, VAZ, FIN and FLE) the values for which range between a minimum of 0.89 and a maximum of 0.98. The Tunisian, the South Tyrolean, the Slovakian, and the Swiss cases (i.e. DAI, WOM, REV and LUM), form a group with values in a range between 0.75 to 0.88. The third group of cases are the Greek, Austrian and Spanish cases (i.e. SEA, HAW and ADF) with values in the range 0.6 to 0.71. Interpretation of the results for the Spanish and Swiss cases (i.e. ADF, LUM and FLE) is that the initiative reaches a high number of final indirect beneficiaries, covering the entire region and valley, respectively.

Overall effects, inside and outside the territory

Four indicators were used to evaluate the overall effect of social innovations: I6, I7, I8, and Hb1 (Table 13, see values in Appendix 2). As assessed with I6 “level of effects of the Social Innovation initiative in the four domains according to the actors”, overall the balance between positive and negative effects is positive, with values ranging up to 0.81 (for case DAI), just below which several cases are scored (i.e. cases REV, WOM, VAZ, LAG and FLE), followed by the cases of CAR and LUM scoring 0.63 and 0.64, respectively. The minimum value is reported for the HAW case (0.56), which is similar to the FIN case (0.58). In these two case studies, the positive impacts are double the negative ones.

According to indicator I7 “Level of effects of the Social Innovation initiative inside the territory in the four domains according to the actors”, the case study with the most balanced positive impact inside the territory is the DAI case, and the case with the lowest impact is HAW. Regarding the level of effects of the social Innovation initiative outside the territory in the four domains according to the actors, the indicator I8 “Level of effects of the Social Innovation initiative outside the territory in the four domains according to the actors” shows in general lower values, meaning that Social Innovation generally has a greater impact on the territory in which it is located, and only occasionally does it have spill-out effects. The lowest indicator values for effects outside of the territory is for case LUM (0.5), and the highest is for cases DAI and SEA (0.75). Indicator Hb1 (Deadweight effects of the Social Innovation initiative in the territory) evaluates whether there are other initiatives that could have determined similar effects on the territory (deadweight effect), according to the actors in the Social Innovation. Generally, the values of this indicator are low, ranging from 0 to 0.50 (out of 1.00), meaning that the social innovation initiative is not unique in satisfying the needs of the territory.

Impacts on the four domains: social, economic, environmental, governance

The proportion of the positive impacts of the social innovation initiative in the four domains (social, economic, environmental and governance) according to the stakeholders was assessed using indicator I4 “Proportion of the number of impacts of the Social Innovation initiative in the four domains which were positive, according to the stakeholder” (see value in Appendix 2) and triangulated with the results of the Focus Groups run in each case study. Qualitative information has been also retrieved from the Types B and C case studies to reinforce the findings.

The cases show high positive impacts of social innovations in all four of the domains. The greatest positive impacts were perceived by actors in the WOM, VAZ, LUM and FLE cases, followed by DAI and LAG cases.

The following sections present the social, economic, environmental and institutional impacts of social innovation across the analysed cases using the qualitative information collected and analysed. Note, there are only qualitative data for the Spanish case (ADF).

Social impacts. When considering the social impacts, distinctions are made between those which relate to (a) enhanced cognitive and cultural impacts, (b) social bonds and collaborations, and (c) those that foster civil society engagement, and (d) political participation.

- a) Several Case Studies report improvements in the valorisation of community rural symbols, local knowledge and identity. The Austrian case (i.e. HAW) has reinforced the consumer-farmer relationship and the appreciation of the value of vegetables. The South Tyrol case (i.e. WOM) has transformed the farm into an educational place for the transmission of rural lifestyle values and a meeting place for the whole community. The Slovakian case (i.e. REV) and Moroccan cases (i.e. ARG) have restored local traditional practices and activities and encouraged repopulation (i.e. REV). The Croatian case (i.e. CRO) has encouraged repopulation of island communities.
- b) Other Case Studies show that social innovation has contributed to the creation of community ties, networks, cooperation, and relationships. One Italian case, and those for

Greece and The Netherlands have increased cooperation at the sectorial level (i.e. cases SEA, VAZ and CAR), while in the Swiss and Egyptian cases (i.e. LUM, FLE, and VIL), co-operation was expanded beyond municipal boundaries. This impact has also been achieved by supporting socially excluded or marginalised people (i.e. cases CAR, WOM, FIN, DAI, ARG, NWF), and in general in by increasing community solidarity, trust, and collaboration (i.e. cases HAW, FLE and HER). In the GUA case community solidarity and civic engagement have increased with the aim of ensuring food security, and in the SLK and SLC cases old rules of the commons relating to forest management have been reintroduced to strengthen the community.

- c) Case Studies that provide evidence of fostering civil society engagement and capacity building have enhanced the involvement of citizens in local issues/problems. The Spanish case (i.e. ADF) has empowered civil society in acting for self-protection against wildfires. The Greek case (i.e. SEA) has provided direct support to marginalised fishermen and local communities. The Scottish case (i.e. LAG) has enhanced the empowerment of communities over the forest resource and developed a multi-functional vision of the woodland (i.e. LAG). The Finnish case (i.e. FIN) led to the creation of a knowledge-transfer platform regarding large-scale industrial projects which provides alternative information to the perceived biased public discussions on nuclear power by increasing international contacts, involving new actors and different types of knowledge. The Egyptian case (i.e. VIL) increased the self-reliance of the local community by improving the village environment. The Scottish community energy projects were based entirely on proactive members of the local communities either as shareholders (i.e. BRA) or promoters (i.e. HUN), revenues from which are reinvested in improving community wellbeing.
- d) Case Studies that enhanced active political participation and civic awareness have enhanced citizen participation in the decision-making processes of local government. The Spanish case (i.e. ADF) increased environmental awareness of wildfires within local communities and better preparation of local actors towards a fire event in terms of knowledge, equipment, and infrastructure. The rural hub in Italy (i.e. case VAZ) promoted better inclusion of socially excluded citizens (i.e. young farmers) in the decision-making process, enabling them to remain in the territory, hence reducing the loss of skilled people. The Finnish case (i.e. FIN) empowered people by providing a forum (Hanhikivi Information Centre) for discussions and by encouraging them to express their opinions in a region dominated by one-sided media discussions on the benefits of nuclear power. It improved awareness and knowledge on risks associated with nuclear power amongst local stakeholders and provided the possibility for local actors to discuss their experiences about nuclear power projects. The case of Slovakian forest commons (i.e. case SKC) has shown that members living in the municipality usually have traditional knowledge about forest management, value their shares in the forest. Their aim to manage the forest with longer-term goals and these principles have been communicated to forest experts, which results in changing traditional forest management practices towards those of carbon smart forestry.

The evidence relating to social impacts are in line with the different types of social capital proposed by Sabatini (2009). They also expand the arguments of Marquardt *et al.* (2012) that social capital enhances development in marginal areas and that increases in social capital are an impact of social innovation (Ravazzoli *et al.*, 2019).

Economic impacts. Amongst the economic impacts a distinction is made between those linked to the enforcement of local networks and those that fostered entrepreneurship and business opportunities. In the case studies these are apparent in the following ways.

- a) The creation or enhancement of local value chains, or networks of firms is a characteristic of the Greek case (i.e. SEA) and the Moroccan case (i.e. ARG), which focus on consolidating existing networks, and characterises the NWF initiative, which focuses on consolidating local value chains. The Swiss initiatives (i.e. LUM and FLE) promoted the expansion of a new distribution channels, new business partners and the creation of new economic and social activities, or the renewal of the manufacturing profile with new companies having settled in the valley (i.e. case FLE). The VàZapp' case (i.e. VAZ) focused on the promotion of territorial marketing of agri-food products.
- b) Cases that strengthen the local labour market and foster entrepreneurship have created new economic opportunities and workplaces such as in the UK, Swiss, and Slovakian cases (i.e. LAG, BRA, HUN, LUM, REV and NWF), or fostered the promotion of the possibility of apprenticeship in the enterprises like in Val de Travers (i.e. case FLE). In other cases, social innovation has promoted business diversification on the farm for the farmers in South Tyrol, where agriculture structures are small-scale (i.e. case WOM).
- c) The creation of a culture of corporate social responsibility and new consumption models, which is evidence in several cases. Cases in this category are oriented towards long-term direct relationships between producer and consumers (i.e. cases HAW, SEA, ARG and HER). These initiatives contribute to the delivery of quality produce, establishing a relationship based on trust, inverting the trend towards big distribution channels in which there is no contact with the source of the produce. Some cases have contributed to the creation of new business models such as towards new uses of ICT and social media for smarter and more direct communication (i.e. cases SEA and VAZ), or the development of an innovative protocol and format for organising social events enhancing exchange and the inclusion of new ideas and people (i.e. case VAZ). New business models created by the Social Innovation initiatives are oriented towards having a new role in rural marginalised areas for delivering tailor-made care and so responding to the needs of "social inclusive care" (i.e. cases CAR and WOM), and towards creating an enabling environment for producers' organisations with improved relationships between producers' organisations and farmers (i.e. case DAI). The community energy enterprises in Scotland (i.e. cases BRA and HUN) produce revenues for their shareholders and contribute to their community wellbeing projects through the distribution of funds generated. In Guadeloupe (i.e. case GUA) the impact is related to creation of new economic and social activities, investments in research, and experiments and innovation that increase knowledge on forest multifunctionality.
- d) A general improvement of local aggregated income and socio-economic conditions has been created by SEA, DAI, WOM, CAR, CRO and NWF cases.

This confirms the arguments of Nicholls *et al.* (2012) that the economic impacts of social innovation are linked to reductions in inequality and the improvement of wellbeing by the incorporation of social, environmental, and economic costs and benefits.

Environmental impacts. According to the analysis of the case studies, social innovation has had the following environmental impacts:

- Reduced vulnerability towards risks through the conservation of natural resources conservation and increased awareness. Examples are due to actions on wildfire prevention and the associated reduction in risk of wildfires (i.e. case ADF) and promoting the planting of trees to reduce the risks of desertification by (i.e. case ARG). Some initiatives have increased awareness and care towards sustainable landscape, land uses and ecosystems and carbon sequestration (i.e. case GUA), and towards new and sustainable uses of the forest resources (i.e. case NWF). Finally, the Finnish initiative has contributed to improved awareness and

knowledge of nuclear power amongst local stakeholders and increased the level of transparency regarding social and environmental impacts (i.e. case FIN).

- Enhanced wellbeing and human health through the production of healthier and environmentally friendly agricultural products, favouring agricultural biodiversity (i.e. cases HAW and HER), sustainable management of fish stocks (i.e. case SEA), and natural resources (i.e. cases DAI, LAG and ARG), and forest (i.e. case NWF), and of healthier and cleaner rural villages (i.e. case VIL).
- Enhanced livelihood and the value of ecological and environmental assets through: i) increases in biodiversity by the re-introduction of native tree species (i.e. cases LAG and ARG); ii) increasing the quality of the area through the reconstruction of characteristic landscape features (i.e. case REV); iii) better planning of land-use and waste (i.e. case FLE); iv) the expected creations of new green jobs (i.e. cases NWF, BRA and HUN); v) support for sustainable tourism (i.e. cases REV and CRO); and, vi) better planning of land-use and waste, improvement of public mobility (i.e. case FLE), therefore providing support to the ecological transition.

These findings are in line with those of Schartinger *et al.* (2017b), confirming that environmental protection and sustainability can be in a win-win situation with socio-economic wellbeing.

Governance/Political impacts. The examples of social innovation have had institutional or political (governance) impacts in all the case studies. Examples of those impacts are:

- The creation of collaborative, informal platforms, or programmes. The cases of cooperation have enhanced the transfer of knowledge from the farmers to the harvest sharers in HAW and HER cases, and between different societal groups such as young people, forest owners, volunteers in ADF case. The level of co-operation was increased amongst fishers, and between fishers and consumers in the Greek initiative (i.e. case SEA). Horizontal cooperation in the VAZ case enables farmers and members to group together, enhances trust towards younger generations and associations, and enables knowledge and information sharing. In the LUM case, the innovation in governance arrangements means the creation of a wider and more heterogeneous network, which for the first time included environmental organisations that until then had been considered hostile in the strategic planning discussions. Similarly, in the FLE and ARG cases the enhanced relationships between public organisations, businesses, and civic associations enables the sharing of data, knowledge, and experiences. The FIN case provides a promising format of collaboration within civil society-led boundary organisations, connecting activism, art, science, and journalism. The REV case is an example of how a municipality can establish partnerships with members of interest organisations, experts from universities and other professional institutions, local, and organisations outside the region. The VIL case created a network of villages which collaborate in improving the environmental resilience of the communities involved. In the GUA case, empowerment and representativeness of stakeholders in decision-making process has been achieved by initiating a project for diversifying and increasing their productivity by engaging in agroforestry practices, through an Operational Group.
- The empowerment through participatory models. In ADF case, citizens were empowered and engaged through participatory landscape and territorial planning, dissemination activities, inclusion of minorities, new policy initiatives, improvements in public services and tackling risks of wildfires. In REV case, participatory models include the establishment of Council for Vlkolinec as a platform where representatives of municipality meet, share ideas, and exchange knowledge with representatives of universities, NGOs, local municipal maintenance companies and other experts. Thanks the SI implementation new actors and connections are created. In the LUM case this means consultations, transparency and accountability of

stakeholders, a reduction in bureaucracy, and an overall improvement in public services and their levels of co-operation. In LAG case the community is being empowered over the woodland and developed a multifunctional vision of the woodland. In NWF case a Market Analysis and Development (MAD) approach to the creation of community forest enterprises was used to build the capacity of local communities to create small businesses that generate profits without harming natural resources. In BRA and HUN cases the community was empowered through the development of trusts that establish renewable energy in their localities and raise revenues for locally identified projects.

- The provision of alternative, high-quality social and public services. In CAR case, social services were provided for the social integration of the disabled through collaboration amongst farmers, volunteers, local governments, schools, and care organisations. In WOM case, there has been an improvement in the delivery of childcare services with rural characteristics through a small familial structure, and contact with nature, plants, and animals. The social innovation initiative has provided the equivalent functions of a public administration in terms of the creation of a complementary offer of the provision of childcare service in remote rural areas of South Tyrol, as an alternative to the official public structures. In FLE case, there has been an improvement in the public transport connection to the Val de Travers and within the valley. This has led to a reduction in the marginalisation of the valley through a reduction in the constraints associated with mountainous rural areas, and those of public transport connectivity due to physical and land use issues.
- The modernisation of public administrations either through more rapid setting of standards, new institutional models, and/or reductions in bureaucracy. Evidence comes from the willingness of the surveillance units on wildfires to listen to the people in the territory (i.e. in ADF case), the local agriculture sector and their challenges (i.e. in VAZ case), the intersectoral collaboration between care, well-being, education, and agricultural sectors (i.e. in CAR case), and the improvement in the legal framework regarding the provision of childcare service and social agriculture in general (i.e. in WOM case). The merging of municipalities in LUM and FLE cases led to a new way of thinking regionally, a broader context and landscape level approach to tackling issues, and an improvement in infrastructure. Similarly, in FLE case the initiative improved the capacity of public administrations to manage collaboration and dialogue between public actors, the private sector and civil society, and increased the transparency and accountability of both private and public sector organisations.

The findings reported above confirm the positions on collaborative governance described by BEPA (2013) and Emerson *et al.* (2012).

7.5 Cross-case Observations

Social innovation initiatives are perceived to deliver improvements in societal wellbeing across a wide range of topics, while contributing to the empowerment of citizens and communities. They create impacts in different dimensions which are strictly related to social impacts (Figure 16).

Figure 16. Empirical evidence on relationships across domains of impacts. (Source: Section authors).

The impacts of social innovation result from the material activities carried on during the social innovation projects (e.g. delivery of social services, revitalization of local communities) and refer to the enhancement of societal wellbeing and the improvement of social, economic, and environmental assets (i.e. impacts on societal wellbeing). They also result from the process of the reconfiguration of social practices, and relate to changes in existing relationships, community ties, new forms of collaboration, and in new distributions of power relations (i.e. impacts on human-social capital and governance). Both dimensions have positive impacts at the community level (e.g. improved community empowerment, community resilience, local development, new governance arrangements), and at the civil society level (e.g. active political participation, citizen engagement), making a positive contribution to rural sustainable development.

The types of specific actions developed by social innovations that contribute to impacts on societal wellbeing are very diverse. Examples of these actions are the provision of services in response to new societal needs and addressing market failures or austerity policies to the development of new regulations including innovations in governance, and reorganisation of the welfare system (Evers and Ewert, 2015). Social innovations, which make services available and accessible to local communities and to specific vulnerable groups contribute to the improvement of rural societal wellbeing in different ways. These are: i) an increase in employment opportunities; ii) the provision of resources for generating other activities; iii) the development of human capital potential (e.g. training); iv) improving community relationships (e.g. intergenerational relationships, integration of vulnerable groups); and v) improving overall social cohesion in the wider social territorial system.

Social innovation is a process developing new partnerships, collaborations, networks, etc. based on trust, reciprocity, collaboration, and autonomy (Avelino *et al.*, 2019) that has an impact on the creation of new social and power relations in the community (Moulaert, 2010). This can have positive impacts through the modernisation of public administration, on the reduction of bureaucracy, and on the level of efficiency in the delivery of services in the public sector. Social innovation is also an opportunity for civil society actors and citizens to play a more active role in their communities, as well as to improve their access to existing resources (including knowledge and power to act), empowering them to contribute to the overall wellbeing of the community. The participation of individual citizens in social innovation activities contributes to the empowerment of the community and of its citizens.

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To continue having an impact on societal wellbeing, the social innovation initiatives require to provide a bridge between society and government. Unlocking the potential of social innovation in communities requires action and engagement by civil society and local, national, and international governments or government bodies. Together, they can provide feasible alternatives for satisfying the needs of citizens and for addressing complex societal challenges, taking on greater roles that enable positive behavioural changes.

8. Relationships Between Policy and Social Innovation

Authors: Gerhard Weiß, Alice Ludvig and Robert Lukesch

8.1 Introduction

This Section aims to analyse policy impact and the implications of social innovation using the in-depth SIMRA case studies. Using a conceptual model of the relationships between policy and social innovation developed for this purpose, the aim is to describe the various patterns of relationships, types of relevant policies and their role with respect to social innovation, and the policy conditions, which help or hinder for social innovation (Ludvig *et al.*, 2017; D6.2). The Section provides a cross-case analysis of the eleven Type A SIMRA Case Studies with respect to the implications for policy of social innovation. Information from Type B and C case studies are used to provide additional support for that analysis.

The aim is to identify similarities and differences of impacts on social innovation exerted by public governance and policies, how and to what extent they may have supported or hindered its development, and influences which the social innovations in the case study may have had on political frameworks and evolving policies. The conceptual and analytical framework used for the comparative analysis is presented, followed by the main findings from testing the model empirically, and conclusions on the policy conditions that support or hinder social innovation in marginalised rural areas.

8.2 Conceptual Model

Social innovation has been defined in different ways, including two aspects of new processes and new outcomes, usually in combination (Moulaert *et al.*, 2005). More specifically, the two aspects mean that: i) social innovations are new institutional arrangements or structures, decision making processes or actor relationships (Moulaert *et al.*, 2005); and ii) they aim to (better) meet social needs, solve societal problems, or enhance societal well-being (Mulgan, 2007). The first aspect can be supported by policies that support actor collaboration and participatory processes in general. The second requires policies directed at specific social goals such as the support of vulnerable groups.

This analysis considers the entire range of different types of policies relevant to social innovation. For the examination of policy implications of social innovation, the approach is to undertake a comprehensive analysis of the different roles that policies and social innovations may have in rural areas. Consideration of policy influence on social innovations has to be able to take account of the character of social innovations, which often occur because of gaps in policy, as alternative models to existing policy approaches, or in conflict with them. Relationships can change over time when, for example, social innovations which developed from a bottom-up process and independent from specific policies are a trigger for new policies or institutional arrangements. Therefore, we apply a model of mutual relationships between policy and social innovation (Ludvig *et al.*, 2017; D6.1) that aims to structure those relationships through consideration of different types of policies and different stages of the innovation processes (Figure 17).

Figure 17. Conceptual model of the relationships between policies and social innovation. (Source: Section authors).

The model considers the following four characteristics of the relationships between policies and social innovation:

- 1) **Mutual relations.** Relationships between policies and social innovation can be observed in terms of how policies can impact on social innovations, and social innovations can impact on policies (Ludvig *et al.*, 2017; D6.1).
 - **Policies impacting on social innovations** – Every social innovation occurs in a certain political-institutional context with influences from multiple policies that affect the possibilities of civil society engagement, the specific aims of the initiative, or innovative or entrepreneurial activities in general. However, some policies may not have the effects intended due to poor formulation, deficiencies in implementation, or other factors which would hinder their effects.
 - **Social innovations impact on policies** - Social innovations can trigger the creation of new policies or lead to improvements in existing institutional frameworks.
- 2) **Positive and negative role of policies.** Social innovations often arise to fill market or policy gaps. Policy makers and stakeholders may either welcome social innovations, as alternatives that are complementary to existing modes of policy or market delivery. On the contrary, they may consider them as competing approaches that call existing approaches into question (Buttoud *et al.*, 2011). Social innovation initiatives often face numerous barriers (Chalmers, 2013). They may face high levels of bureaucracy or must tackle unfavourable framework conditions when existing institutional arrangements do not encourage the uptake of new ways of working or solutions to problems. This happens when any such new approaches work against established rules or common practices, also unintentionally (Prokofieva *et al.*, 2019; Rogelja *et al.*, 2018).

To some extent, a successful Social Innovation depends on supportive framework conditions or opportunity structures. They may find support from some policy fields but experience barriers from others. Certain policies aim to support social goals and/or innovations and may provide very important support to innovative initiatives when designed and implemented appropriately (Ludvig *et al.* 2017; D6.1). Policy instruments may be specific regulations, advisory services, or funding.

- 3) **Specific or general policies.** Relevant institutional environments may include more general regulations such as those from agricultural, social, or welfare policies that are relevant to the social innovation initiative, as well as regulations directed at their specific activities. General policy or institutional environments may support or hinder social innovation, for example when encouraging or discouraging innovative solutions or civil society participation. Specific

policies may or may not be implemented successfully. Alternatively, social innovations can affect the broader policy environment, or lead to or improve specific policies in their field.

Policies of either a general or specific nature are important in the support of social innovation. General policies may be important for creating a supportive environment for the development of new social innovation initiatives. Specific policies may be needed for the effective regulation of social innovation activities and supporting the diffusion and scaling up of the social innovation.

- 4) Changing relationships between policies and social innovation over time.** Policies for different topics and purposes may be relevant in different stages of social innovation processes. Social innovations often develop as bottom-up processes without specific policies. This early stage may still be supported by policies in the form of an open and innovation-friendly institutional environment. Social Innovation may also trigger or actively lobby for institutional adaptations or new policies in favour of the Social Innovation activities (institutionalization; policy entrepreneurship, scaling up, Westley *et al.*, 2014). Or, new policies may support the growth or diffusion of the innovation (diffusion and adoption by others, scaling out). Perceived deficiencies may trigger improvements in policies.

The SIMRA conceptual framework and its feedback loops (Klůvanková *et al.*, 2017; D2.2; Secco *et al.*, 2017, D4.2) describes a cyclical process in which innovation activities lead to the improvement of policies which in turn have an impact on the social innovation activities (policy and social innovation cycle, Figure 18).

The establishment of new ideas which are sustainable will require a change in cultural norms and beliefs, within single projects and for moving beyond the niche to the regime or system (scaling deep, Moore *et al.*, 2015).

Figure 18: Policy and social innovation cycle. (Source: Section authors).

8.3 Analytical Approach

The approach used to perform the cross-case analysis is based on in-depth interpretative analysis of policy in the case studies. The following aspects have been tackled using a qualitative analysis: a) constitutional, political and institutional context; b) the type of policy support for the Social Innovation initiative; c) the lifetime of the Social Innovation initiative from the main trigger event to date; d) the territorial dimension of the Social Innovation initiative; and e) the stance of the key actors in the Social Innovation initiative towards politics and policies. A triangulation of qualitative and quantitative information deriving from indicator Ba2 was also performed (Table 14).

Table 14. Indicators employed in the cross-case analysis

Code	Indicator label	Value Range
Ba2	Role of supportive policies for sustaining the results of the Social Innovation initiative	[0-1]

(Source: Section authors).

The reflection on similarities and differences was nurtured by the interpretations and discussion points provided by the case study authors. This is particularly about: political framework conditions, laws, regulations governing the specific sector, policies offering financial and technical support or

attempting to influence the development of the initiative for each project, the formal and informal rules affecting the course of the initiative, and the aspects of governance in the relevant sector or territory.

8.4 Results of the cross-case analysis

The main findings of the cross-case analysis of the types of policies and supportive and hindering factors that influence social innovation are presented, together with the impacts of social innovation on policies. It closes with a reflection on varying or changing relationships between social innovation and policy with the social innovation process over time, using examples from agriculture, forestry, and rural development.

8.4.1. Amount of policy support

Social innovation initiatives can emerge because of perceptions of unfavourable situations or a lack of certain services. Policy instruments can offer windows of opportunity (i.e. cases LAG, BRA and HUN). Some Case Studies have developed largely without policy support, either intentionally or because of a lack of such support being available. However, in some cases specific barriers to activities were reported such as against the civic movement opposing the nuclear power plant in Noidanlukko and several previous initiatives (i.e. case FIN) or against small-scale fisheries in general in the Greek case study (i.e. case SEA).

The Austrian and the Finnish cases (i.e. HAW and FIN) both are characterized by an absence of specifically targeted supportive policies. The emergence of HAW case was closely linked to knowledge transfer, which occurred in various forms between single CSAs in Austria, Europe, and USA as well as within an informal Community Supported Agriculture network in Austria; the FIN case is a civil society movement that seeks to influence policy decisions and received no support; similarly, the Greek case (i.e. SEA), strongly led by an international environmental NGO (Greenpeace Greece) also acted with no supportive policy.

Agricultural subsidies are not tailored for Community Supported Agriculture or for very small farms or fisheries, which operates largely separately from established governance structures, even though it received support from some local governments. Community Supported Agriculture is often supported by the initiators and their personal networks, or by NGOs, semi-public organisations, or local governments. In the field of social innovation, NGOs or international organisations play a particularly important role, in poorer countries where the institutional structures are often very weak. This is the case in the case of the dairy producer/s cooperative in Tunisia (i.e. case DAI), and to an extent to the Greek case, which primarily had support from an international NGO.

Some cases benefit from supportive policies. The Tunisian, UK, Moroccan, and Dutch cases (i.e. DAI, NWF, LAG, ARG and HER) all reflect encouraging and enabling policy environments which was timely for their emergence. The Spanish and Slovakian cases (i.e. ADF and REV) evolved within the context of a local initiative and in the forms of public-private partnerships, with an increased emphasis on local self-governance. The Swiss initiatives (i.e. LUM and FLE) are a timely coincidence with the initial Swiss-wide discourse among scholars, consultants, and policy makers about a shift from compensatory regional policy to a policy of support to endogenous "*potential and unique selling products*". Eventually this came into being as the "New Regional Policy" (NRP), adopted by the Swiss Federal Parliament (Bundesrat) in 2005. Finally, the WOM case faced barriers from male-dominated institutional structures and from established service providers that perceived the initiative as competition.

A broad range of policy sectors may be relevant to social innovation. The role of policies is manifold, but in general policy support can be expected in three policy dimensions (Table 15). These are policies aimed at fulfilling governmental objectives in the social sector; policies dealing with economic and societal challenges which are cross-cutting in nature, including those aiming at territorial cohesion and/or economic and technological development; and policies aiming at institutional change which are

embedded in society. This latter set concern public participation, inclusion, legal provisions for associations and co-operative self-organisation, and the ways that democratic values are operationalised. These three dimensions can be regarded as three layers of technical, institutional, and constitutional rules (see Figure 19), and different forms of scaling out, up and deep (Moore *et al.*, 2015). An adapted set of these categories is presented in Table 15 and described in Ludvig *et al.* 2017b. (D6.2, p.12).

Figure 19. Policies aiming at sectoral, structural, and institutional change. (Source: Section authors).

The cross-case analysis of the indicator Ba2, on the role of supportive policies for sustaining the results of the Social Innovation initiative, shows that policies and policy frameworks supporting institutional change have less of an impact than structural and sectoral changes. The values of the indicator is 67.9% for Case Studies belonging to the sectoral policy dimension; 67.9% for Case Studies belonging to the structural policy dimension; and 48.0% for Case Studies belonging to the institutional policy dimension. These values may be the result of their character, which is more enabling than supportive, and focused on the provision of technical advice and information, learning, and networking rather than on funding. Moreover, it is the social innovation initiative itself which must make all the efforts required to obtain the support. It is the financial resources which make the key difference, particularly in the early phases of a Social Innovation initiative.

Table 15. Policy dimensions of social innovation in SIMRA Type A Case Studies.

Policy Dimension	Examples	Key Policy Focus	Case Studies
Sectoral	Sectoral laws, rules, and regulations (e.g. Greencare)	Vulnerable groups	WOM, DLO
Structural	Territorial and social cohesion policies EAFRD, ESF); Measures 19 (CLLD/LEADER) and 16 (Cooperation) of the EAFRD; Land Reform Act (Scotland, UK); contract agreements between the Ministry and producer organisations (Tunisia), renewable energy feed-in-tariffs (in cases BRA and HUN), community forestry norms (in cases SKC and SLC), New Regional Policy (Switzerland)	Territorial (regional and rural) and value chain development	VAZ, LUM, FLE, DAI
Institutional	Constitution (FI); law on co-operatives (FI) or legal provisions for Community Interest Companies (UK), the devolution of public tasks to civic associations (UK); funding for transnational networking and learning amongst civil society actors (AT)	Civil society inclusion and participation	HAW, ADF, VAZ, FIN, REV, LAG, SEA

(Source: Section authors based upon Ludvig *et al.* (2017); D6.1, p.4).

Social policies specific to social innovation. The most relevant specific social policies relating to Social Innovation are the those linked to the provision of care in various forms. Those are the European Union and national green care and social farming programmes. Within SIMRA, the care farm Pitteperk (i.e. case CAR) was supported by national level programmes as were the Italian social farming initiatives, including the farm nurseries in South Tyrol (i.e. case WOM). The Type C Moroccan case (i.e. ARG) benefitted from the support of national social policies through its social development agency (ADS). These programmes were also supported by the Social Innovation initiatives, further details of which are presented later in this Section.

Structural policies supporting social innovation or social entrepreneurship in general. Certain instruments aiming at supporting Social Innovation or social entrepreneurship have the character of providing specific support to socially directed activities. They do not however specify the area of activities. These include the EU LEADER/CLLD instrument for integrated rural and regional development, other regional development programmes and policies for the support of civil engagement, the third sector and social entrepreneurship. LEADER-funded projects can be considered, potentially, at least as innovative (Lukesch *et al.*, 2019, p.75). In line with earlier statements from Dargan and Shucksmith (2008, p.282) it is possible to say that *social innovation belongs to the core tasks of LEADER* (Lukesch *et al.*, 2019, p.95). Measure 19 of the EAFRD, CLLD/LEADER, is tailored to help social innovation initiatives as the LEADER approach reflects the basic requirements of policy which fosters (social) innovation in rural areas.

LEADER was the main funding source for the LAG, VAZ, and REV cases. Measure 16 (Co-operation) was used by VAZ case, and Measure 6, which supports young farmers, was used by REV case. There is no record of Measure 7, which supports cross-sectoral “Basic services and village renewal”, being used anywhere in the EU-based case studies. Funding from this type of source usually comes together with technical assistance and advisory services. However, the administrative burden can still be high due to the requirements of accountability at both EU and governmental levels.

Development programmes at the EU, national rural, or regional levels supported various projects in the SIMRA cases. The UK case (i.e. LAG) received important support from Scottish Community Empowerment policies. Similar regulations were relevant for the national Green Deal (public-private partnership policy on nature including land use) which supported the Dutch Community Supported Agriculture case (i.e. case HER), and the regional policies in the Swiss cases (i.e. LUM and FLE) (Expertenkommission 2003; Schuler *et al.*, 2004; Stucki *et al.*, 2004).

Institutional policies providing an enabling environment for social innovation. Support can be provided through several different sectors including agriculture, and regional and rural development, SME and start-up funds in rural areas, social policies, and environmental protection. These institutional rules are often so unspecific and of general relevance, that it is difficult to identify their specific roles in the Case Studies. For example, in Finland the civic movement in Noidanlukko (i.e. case FIN) did not receive specific support under any policy programme. Instead, it drew on constitutional rules, the law on co-operatives, and got some financial support from The Grassroots Foundation (<http://www.grassroots.de/index.html>), which was founded in 1999 with the goal of supporting civil society movements in their struggles for the protection of nature and the respect for human rights.

When examined in detail, a conclusion can be drawn that all cases operate in an institutional environment which provides opportunities in sometimes or places, and limitations to their activities in others. With the start of the social farming initiative in South Tyrol (i.e. case WOM), several supportive (as well as hindering) institutional structures were reported (see the detailed analysis at the end of this Section). A final example is that of the Tunisian, case which was implicitly supported by the new formulation of the forest code in 1988 (NWF).

This differentiation in policy support has implications on how the policy context of the Social Innovation initiatives is framed:

- **Social Innovation initiatives providing social support** (i.e. cases WOM and DLO), or public services in the environmental (i.e. case LAG) and cultural (i.e. case REV) domains, once consolidated, have good prospects of receiving long-term funding contracts. This happens as soon as they can be proven to be providing the public goods in line with their objectives. They are subject to standards, criteria, and corresponding control systems which constrain choices on how to manage things, sometimes making operational management and administration unwieldy. All four initiatives complained about the burdens of bureaucracy. The initiatives respond to the requirements of bureaucracy by employing professional staff (supervisors in the CAR case; a community and a forest officer in the LAG case) or by including State, municipal, and university experts in the core partnership and planning staff (i.e. cases REV and VIL).
- **Social Innovation initiatives which mainly benefit from cross-cutting structural policy support.** Generally, these are in the form of local, regional, or value chain development programmes or schemes, benefiting from time-bound measures, financial support, and technical assistance within a defined project period (i.e. cases LUM, SEA, VAZ, DAI and LAG). The time limitation constitutes a challenge to their sustainability in terms of finance and technical assistance. Whereas the latter can be resolved through intermediary or State agencies, the former requires either the full marketability of the services provided (i.e. cases SEA and VIL), or maintaining the level of civic engagement, thereby keeping the fixed costs low (i.e. case VAZ). In summary, there is funding available, but it is quite complex to obtain and to maintain.
- **Social Innovation initiatives which have not (yet) actively sought to gain public recognition** of the common benefits they provide (i.e. cases HAW, SEA and VAZ), or are denied such recognition (i.e. case FIN). They look to policies and frameworks which are designed to support institutional change (e.g. laws on co-operatives or citizen participation, and their roles in environmental impact assessments) and funding for networking and exchanges for learning (i.e. cases HAW and VAZ). This implies that they have the fewest dependencies and constraints. The downside is that in the absence of enough marketability or civic engagement, their status can be precarious.

8.4.2. Impact of social innovation on policies – implications for policy

The SIMRA Case Studies constitute a broad spectrum of Social Innovation initiatives. Distinctions are made between social innovation initiatives which are triggered or influenced by policies from those, which are influencing the emergence and mainstreaming of policies. Some social innovation initiatives have avoided contact with or are distant from the influence of public sector (i.e. cases HAW, FIN, SEA and VAZ). Three cases are early manifestations of emerging policy trends (i.e. cases WOM, LUM and CAR). Five cases have co-evolved with new policy approaches and serve as examples for testing and demonstration (i.e. cases WOM, ADF, REV, LIV, and DAI). A final pair of cases respond to a coherent set of policy frameworks and incentives that enable local entrepreneurs and communities to innovate (i.e. cases DLO and LAG). Social innovations have the capability to influence the policy environment when they are part of a larger societal changes. In many cases, societal change occurs gradually and cannot be observed easily, and the impact of specific Social Innovation projects is then difficult to identify. Two examples are: i) the evolution over recent decades of environmental awareness, which has been institutionalized by the creation or change in environmental policies (e.g. Environmental Impact Assessment including the EU Directive in 1988), and ad hoc governmental positions; ii) the establishment of organic agriculture as an accepted form of agricultural practice, which has also taken place over recent decades and involved numerous independent initiatives by producers and consumers.

The changing role of agriculture in society has led to institutionalised policies, for example in rural development in the European Union, which aim at integrated local development and extending and

improving the multiple functions provided by agriculture. Social farming is an example of such expansion in functions, which is documented and represented by the cases of CAR and WOM, as well as by the institutionalisation at a national level in the FAS case. The creation of specific policies (e.g. EU-Grundtvig programme for Lifelong Learning and policies of decentralisation of powers) was also relevant in the cases dealing with community supported agriculture (i.e. case HAW) and community development in the United Kingdom (i.e. case LAG). Longer term institutional developments are also behind the REV case, which is built upon the political changes which followed the break-down of socialist regimes in Eastern Europe, together with the re-establishing of the historical forest commons (i.e. cases SKC and SLC) and with international support through the establishment of the UNESCO heritage site. The volunteer forest fire fighters in Catalonia (i.e. case ADF) is another example which illustrates very complex interactions between various policy developments and the Social Innovation initiative.

The cases analysed represent specific projects that belong to larger social innovations which are part of societal change. Their relationship to policy depends, amongst other things, on the stage of the life cycle of the larger Social Innovation phenomenon. When they are in an early stage of development, they may be drivers of policy change (scaling up); when they occur later, they may benefit from pre-existing policies. Those specific policies may trigger a spreading of the innovations into further projects (scaling out). Examples follow of cases which are scaling up or out.

Childcare on farms (i.e. case WOM) had a very active role in establishing specific rules (scaling up), when the Dutch care farm (i.e. case CAR) was being established in recent decades (scaling out). It also developed the idea and methods of providing care for disabled people (scaling deep). HAW and HER cases are part of a European Community Supported Agriculture movement in which the Dutch case had a strong pioneer role (scaling up) whereas the Austrian one was established independently with some support from Community Supported Agriculture networks (scaling out). The example of a Community Development Company in the United Kingdom (i.e. case LAG) benefitted from a well-developed policy framework (scaling out). The scaling deep process or impact is also visible in the WOM case, in which initial scepticism of the main farmer's association changed, with the idea being accepted in a cross-sectoral working group with participants from agriculture and social care domains.

Scaling up and scaling deep occurred in the LUM and FLE cases, where their ideas became institutionalised in co-operative structures and policies. The VAZ case is a unique project which stands alone amongst numerous and diverse regional development initiatives in Italy and elsewhere as part of a response to challenges of the depopulation of rural areas and a rejuvenation of rural landscapes using traditional skills and practices and local resources. As such it was supported by the EU LEADER programme (scaling out). The REV case has a similar aim and character. The FIN case represents local resistance against industrial colonisation, and the SEA case is an example of the trend in direct marketing for local, green, and sustainable products. These cases may all be viewed as examples of scaling out within larger societal movements and social change trends in rural areas (Westley *et al.* 2014, Moore *et al.* 2015).

8.4.3. Mutual relationships between social innovation and policies

Across the cases there is evidence of strong interdependencies between social innovations, political framework, and policies. Table 16 illustrates the many ways mutual relationships are represented between various types of policies and social innovations. Three Case Studies are also presented in the field of agriculture, forestry, and rural development to explain the mutual relationships between policy and social innovation over time (Boxes 1, 2 and 3).

To develop an understanding of the mutual relationships between social innovations and policies, information was retrieved from the case study reports. For agriculture, use was made of the in-depth case study in South Tyrol (i.e. WOM) and the case study on the Italian social farming policy (i.e. FAS). For forestry, the Spanish case (i.e. ADF) was used, which illustrates several development steps from

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precursor activities to changes in the policy framework (scaling up), and further related initiatives that lead this social innovation to create impact (scaling out). For the field of rural development, the case used was LAG, the community woodlands movement in the UK. The UK community woodlands movement is unique in Europe but community engagement for supporting the conservation and reviving of local land resources and initiating local development based on such assets is documented in many European examples (SIMRA database: www.simra-h2020.eu/index.php/simradatabase/).

The comparison across agriculture, forestry, and rural development does not demonstrate specific differences between those sectors, but rather it shows how such social innovation initiatives relate to specific local needs and resources as well as to the various roles of institutional frameworks and policies. The Case Studies enable the derivation of common supportive or impeding conditions and policy recommendations.

Table 16. Links between Social Innovation and Policies across Type A Case Studies.

Case Study	Degree of Policy Coherence	Policy impact on Social Innovation	Policy implication of Social Innovation (Is there an implication for Policy? If so, what is its nature?)
HAW	None	A project funded by the EU-Grundtvig program for Lifelong Learning facilitating information transfer and networking seemed to have had the biggest impact on the emergence of HAW. HAW case study does not participate in area-based CAP measures due to its farm size as well as the relatively high bureaucratic burden in relation to the respective amount of support. No specific formal rules and formal policies in Austria yet, which specifically address Community Supported Agriculture.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No (with regard to the single initiative). • Not (with regard to the Community Supported Agriculture movement, represented by a loose network of single farm initiatives). • Public authorities and established agricultural institutions start acknowledging the potential of alternative ways of food production and consumption such as Community Supported Agriculture.
LUM	High	Pro Val Lumnezia has benefited from a wide range of federal and cantonal local/regional development support instruments.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, as a precursor to the Social Innovation. • The sub-regional initiative Pro Val Lumnezia has foreshadowed the Swiss New Regional Policy. It has contributed to the shaping of the New Regional Policy over time, by informing experts, planners, and consultants with awareness of or links to the initiative.
ADF	High	The recognition of the firefighter associations (ADF) as statutory bodies, working on the basis of contractual and budgetary agreements with the municipalities and the state of Catalonia, has contributed to the mainstreaming and scaling up of the voluntary approach to disaster prevention and management.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes. • With the establishment of the umbrella organisation of all ADFs in 1999 (i.e. the secretariat of the ADF/SFADF), there has been a co-evolution of the political and legal frameworks (e.g. the policy programme <i>Foc Verd</i>, and other policy instruments).
FIN	Controversial	The initiative emerged as a direct response to the Finnish nuclear energy strategy and the decision to build a nuclear power plant in Pyhäjoki.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unsuccessful attempts. • The issue can only be solved at the national level.
SEA	None	The initiative refers to the European Fisheries Strategy but does not connect to any policy instrument at any level of decision-making.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No. • An aim of the initiative is to serve as a model which goes viral after consolidating a viable business case. It is kept apart from any political activities, local to national.
WOM	High	The initiative grew on the basis of national and provincial laws concerning sectoral, structural, and institutional aspects, and co-evolved with the green care policy in the province.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The strong influence through the association of women farmers and its president, who acted as the core innovator and shortly thereafter as a member of the provincial parliament. This influence extended to the national legislation, the shaping of provincial legislation, and the governance of the green care sector.

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VAZ	Low	The initiative draws from EU cohesion funds and local contributions. Having started as an informal group of young farmers and rural activists, the political acceptance of the initiative has grown, but there is no formal link to public partners.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minor. • The initiative has largely by-passed political channels to remain within the realm of civil society.
CAR	High	The health care sector is regulated according to standards and quality criteria. In times of budget restrictions, Dutch legislation helped deinstitutionalise and decentralise the responsibilities that led to the emergence of many (of the order of hundreds) similar care farms across The Netherlands.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No direct influence. • The regional support structure SZZ (Collaborating care farmers in the south of the Netherlands; in Dutch: Samenwerkende Zorgboeren Zuid) which is part of the overarching federation "Agriculture and Care" is leading negotiations with the public sector, from municipalities to the government, with the eventual aim of helping to shape policy in this sector.
REV	High	The settlement of Vlkolínec is a UNESCO Heritage Site and part of the city of Ružomberok. Environmental and cultural preservation are public tasks, but it is acknowledged that private actors have to get involved in the maintenance and use of the site for it to remain lively and sustainable.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is an influence mainly at the municipal level through the Vlkolínec Council and the expertise provided by the academic researchers involved.
DAI	High	The dairy sector is a focus of national economic policy. The FAO provided the main funding and technical assistance to build up the cooperatives in the value chain.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not directly. • Successful establishment of enterprises in the dairy value chain in the governing councils of Sfax, Monastir, and Mahdia will be taken up as model examples by the responsible Ministry for the establishment of equivalent arrangements in other regions of Tunisia.
LAG	High	The initiative waiting to be developed emerged as a direct response to has benefited by a policy of decentralisation and the instruments and structures which were enacted in Scotland. It has benefited from a "motorway" open for social innovations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not directly. • The supervisory and supporting structures in Scotland, UK, take ideas from community partners in a process of continuous exchange and learning. Eventually, this leads to incremental adaptations of the relevant policies.
VIL	High	The initiative emerged by individual innovator and supported by family ties but benefited from the umbrella of on-going national rural development program "SHOROOK" that had operational mechanisms encouraging local initiatives.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indirectly but later on directly. • When the public local development authorities got informed with the initiative in 2002, they supported it. Further, they established a regional network in 2006 under a new branch program of development to include also other villages adopting specific criteria to become Model Environment-Friendly Villages. Later on, the authorities contracted with the concerned local civil society organizations to take care of the local cleaning services

(Source: Partly from Ludvig *et al.* (2018; D6.2), and Section authors).

Boxes 1, 2, and 3 below report examples of relationships between social innovation and policies on agriculture, forestry, and rural development, respectively.

BOX 1 - Agriculture case. Social farming: a local case within a European movement.

The local initiative for childcare on farms in South Tyrol started in 2003 from a discussion within the South Tyrolean network of women farmers and was founded in 2006 as a social co-operative. No specific policy on social farming existed at that time, although similar ideas and activities also occurred in other places in Europe. Institutional frameworks of relevance to the local project were available, such as European Social Funds providing financial and advisory assistance for setting up the social co-operative and funding for a training activity.

A cause and motivation for the initiative was a general lack of awareness of the situation of women farmers by a male-dominant institutional environment (Dalla Torre *et al.*, 2019). This context meant that at the outset of the movement there was some opposition by the main regional farmer's association. The political activities of the female initiator, who was the main driving force of the project, were crucial to securing political support throughout the project. Strong support came from the establishment of a national law for social agriculture in 2015 which was a trigger for a later law which was introduced at the provincial level (2018), also strongly shaped by the project and the innovator. Having been elected a member of the provincial parliament, she initiated a parliamentary working group and mobilised support from actors across sectors and research institutes (Dalla Torre *et al.*, 2019).

A further achievement of the innovator and colleagues was the lobbying for improved contractual conditions for social workers and the inclusion of farm childcare in those regulations. The project aims to broaden activities to care of the elderly, which is also covered by the new law. The development of these activities faced opposition from established social services which viewed the new social farming activities as unfair competition. This was due to the asymmetric levels of educational qualifications required, for which those who have trained to be educators have to attend courses over multiple years, and farmers providing the service on their farm attend a shorter course.

Care, or social, farming is recognised by European Union bodies as an important field of activity. Initiatives in several countries have driven the scaling up to national and EU levels. The European Economic and Social Committee have called on national and regional authorities to develop regulatory frameworks for social farming and green care (Elsen and Finuola, 2013). As of 2019, green care is supported by the European Union and several Member States (Haubenhofner *et al.*, 2010; Renner and Haubenhofner, 2013).

Figure 20. Mutual relations of policy and social innovation over time: the case of social farming. (Source: Section authors).

BOX 2 - Forestry case. Volunteer forest fire fighters in Catalonia: an institutionalised regional innovation

This social innovation is founded on a strong regional tradition of mutual help between farmers in tackling forest fires. For the problem of forest fires, during the 1960s and early 1970s in several locations in Catalonia, associations of forest owners were formed to share the costs of paying the fire fighters in case of forest fires, to provide effective fire prevention activities, or to reach the site of the fire more rapidly than the official fire brigades. A regulation was triggered by a wildfire on Montserrat mountain (August 1986) which brought the issue onto the political agenda in Catalonia (Catalan Law on Forest Defence Groups 1986). Within the first year (1987), 140 groups covering 351 municipalities (approximately one third of all Catalan municipalities) were established. In 1988, the Forest Defence Groups received legal recognition with their inclusion in the Catalan Forest Law. They were a very important part of the Green Fire (*Foc Verd*) policy programme, and in the Wildfire emergency plan for Catalonia, "INFOCAT", which was established in 1994. In 1999, an umbrella association was created for all Forest Defence Groups in Catalonia. The groups receive funds mainly from the Catalan Government (Department of agricultural) and may also receive further economic support from the provincial government and municipalities. The main source of conflict reported regards the role of these groups, with opinions varying as to whether the groups should engage more in firefighting or in fire prevention activities. One challenge is the engagement of local landowners on the topic of the trends of depopulation and decreasing incomes in rural areas. Today, some of these groups go beyond their basic functions (which are to support fire prevention, fire suppression, and post-fire reforestation) and are establishing new activities (e.g. bio-energy use) or alliances (offering opportunities for community work in collaboration with the law courts).

Figure 21. The policy and social innovation cycle in the case of Volunteer Forest Fire Fighters in Catalunya. (Source: Section authors).

BOX 3 - Rural development case. Lochcarron Community Development Company: community woodlands as a basis for rural development

The SIMRA case study on the Lochcarron Community Development Company (case LAG) is a local initiative which runs projects that aim to serve the community through providing direct benefits from local resources and operating commercial activities. Several of the activities are forest related. The core resource of the company is a plot of woodland purchased by a community group from the State (Forestry Commission) in 2012. The initiative forms part of a movement of the stewardship of community woodlands in Great Britain which started in the 1980s with initiatives at a local level. The approach spread to other communities, disseminated by organisations such as Reforesting Scotland and the Community Woodlands Association, and supported by land reform policies in England, Wales, and Scotland (Lawrence *et al.*, 2009; Lawrence and Ambrose-Oji, 2013). Scottish laws of relevance include the Land Reform Acts (2003, 2016), the Community Empowerment Act 2015, and the establishment of a Land Fund.

A characteristic of this social innovation is the reconfiguring of governance of woodlands and challenging traditional land ownership structures in Scotland. The background to this movement is that communities/populations felt excluded from the benefits of forests that were in either private or State ownership and mostly intended for sports/hunting or timber production. Community ownership is oriented toward local benefits through income and/or other forest ecosystem services. In the case of Lochcarron, the idea was raised initially in 1995 and reinvigorated when the woodland became available for sale in 2008. In 2009, the Kirkton Woodland and Heritage Group was formed, obtaining charitable status, and merging with the previous Smithy Heritage Centre, an initiative to restore an old blacksmith workshop.

The application for purchasing the woodland was submitted in 2011 after a community consultation process and a community ballot. The purchase of the woodland was supported financially by the Scottish Land Fund and the operation was supported by trees donated from the Woodland Trust for with the aims of improving biodiversity. Highlands and Islands Enterprise provided support through advice regarding organisational, legal, and commercial issues, and support for the project was obtained from the European Union LEADER instrument amongst others. A company was set up in 2014 with the purpose of felling trees to rejuvenate the woodland, which received a felling license in 2015. Household surveys were conducted to identify the community needs for wood fuel and housing. When asked about hindrances, representatives mentioned a generally high level of bureaucracy which makes many of their activities difficult to implement. In addition to the woodland management, the Lochcarron Community Development Company runs numerous projects including a heritage centre and café at the old smithy, a tree house, an educational trail, and an artisan dairy.

Figure 22. Local initiatives and policy support around community woodlands in the case of the Lochcarron Community Development Company. (Source: Section authors).

8.5 Cross-case Observations

The in-depth analysis of the Case Studies enables the success factors for the Social Innovation initiatives to be extracted. From the field of policy, we can describe policy conditions that have supportive or hindering effects. Policies foster social innovation when they can create a supportive environment and “room for manoeuvre” for the innovators to develop and implement their ideas. Policies need to invest in knowledge exchange, capacity building and infrastructure in rural areas. In regions with poor technical and advisory infrastructure there is a greater need for solutions but at the same time this is hindered by the lack of support structures. To break such vicious circles, improvements in the basic infrastructure as well as specific support activities for innovation, participatory regional development and social initiatives are needed.

Social Innovation does not necessarily need to be strictly regulated. It can and should be tackled across a range of areas for which there are different policies. Social innovation in rural areas would benefit from some form of cohesion tool, or “hybrid” organisation or body to tackle divisions between policy sectors, with a high level of importance attached to openness, flexibility, and cross-sectoral coordination. Recognition of the benefits of social innovation for, and by all, stakeholders is a precondition for success of such initiatives.

Supportive policy conditions that foster social innovation in marginalised rural areas can be described as:

- Openness of public actors towards innovative activities. Innovations need to be flexible and to take account of risk. Targeted seed-money can have a big impact on the viability of social innovation projects, even with small amounts of money.
- Cross-sectoral cooperation is often necessary, as innovative solutions can often answer non-sectoral, cross-cutting problems, or are needed because of the blindness of established sectoral structures.
- Broader understanding of the social innovation concept, recognising that innovations are not only technological, e.g. opening-up the EIP-Agri concept to social innovation.
- Support of opportunity structures in rural areas, such as education, employment opportunities, regional and local development investments, basic technical infrastructure, and advisory and information services.
- Policies that offer opportunities of participation for stakeholder and citizen engagement/involvement. These can foster social innovation when people share their concerns and visions regarding their communities and needs and proposing solutions. LEADER/CLLD are examples of “transformation policies” for institutional change.

Impeding policy conditions which hinder social innovation were identified as:

- Divisions between departments and thinking in silos which limits the effectiveness of policies.
- Conventional policy administration is often contrary to characteristics of innovation of openness and risk-taking.
- In some countries, conventional government or governance institutions and actors are not supportive of “bottom-up” civil society engagement. They appear to fear a loss of control and power. However, bottom-up approaches can have advantages for conventional government notions as they reduce risks of social unrest and strengthen the trust of voters in political institutions.
- Short-term political priorities and direction of projects. The evidence from the SIMRA Case Studies shows that these social innovation initiatives are often long-term projects and societal processes,

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results from which are not always immediately visible. The long-term timespans of such projects are not always understood by policy makers.

- Inadequate understanding of social innovation can lead to policy failures, for example when the focus of innovation programmes is on technical outputs, which are often more easily measured in short-term time periods.

9. Towards a Better Understanding of Social Innovation in Marginalised Rural Areas

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9.1 Introduction

This Section presents some observations on social innovation in marginalised rural areas based on the empirical findings from the SIMRA Case Studies in different dimensions of social innovation. A selection of composite indicators has been used, based upon the methodology developed by Secco *et al.* (2019; D4.3) for developing these observations.

Composite indicators help to understand the complexity and characteristics of the social innovation process and its dimensions to measure performance across cases. In this Section, composite indicators explain the issues and main trends in relation to the following social innovation dimensions linked to steps in the evolution of a social innovation:

- the elements that influence social innovation,
- the process of reconfiguring social practices,
- the impacts on the territorial dimension,
- the replication of social innovation.

However, it should be acknowledged that if the construction process is not robust then this type of construction may disguise failings in some dimensions and increase the difficulty of identifying proper remedial actions. Due to the limited numbers of cases it was not possible to carry out tests of robustness. In some cases, as explained in the following sections, the composite indicator or the index report data that may appear inconsistent to those of single indicators. To make the analysis more robust and complete, composite indicators were used together with qualitative information retrieved from Individual Case Study Reports (Task 5.3). This Section is structured into two main parts: it presents the analytical framework used to create and interpret the indicators, and then discusses the results of the analysis according to themes of enquiry.

9.2 Analytical Approach

To derive the main findings from the cross-theme examination of social innovations composite indicators have been developed. These are basing upon the methodology developed by Secco *et al.* (2019; D4.3), which aimed to explain the dimensions of Social Innovation presented within the SIMRA evaluation framework (Secco *et al.*, 2018; R5.1).

The following steps were followed to build the composite indicators:

1. All the indicators were employed to analyse the following themes of enquiry: influencing factors, reconfiguring process and impacts. The themes of enquiry “diverging path” and “policy impact and implications” primarily used textual information for their assessment and no indicators.
2. To build composite indicators a linear (or additive) aggregation method was used, as suggested in Secco *et al.* (2019; D4.3). This was because all the individual indicators have the same measurement range of units (0 to 1). The linear aggregation method requires the computation of the mean values of the selected indicators for each case study.
3. Composite indicators were developed that refer to sub-dimensions of investigation (Figure 23). These partially follow the approach used in Secco *et al.* (2019; D4.3) in their selection of which indicators to use for which sub-dimension. The main criteria used for this operation was thematic in accordance with the indicator with the sub-dimension. This enables the

exploration of each sub-dimension (e.g. trigger) has determined the main dimension of investigation (e.g. influencing factor). By aggregating composite indicators related to the sub-dimensions of investigation, an index was built for each dimension of investigation.

- To support the interpretation of general cross-case results, the values of the indexes were compared across the Case Studies. The mean values were used as reference values (Figure 26) to compare performance. The full list of indicators is provided in Appendix 2, while the list of composite indicators and indexes and their values is reported in Table 21.

Composite indicators are useful tools for illustrating and summarising multidimensional aspects of a complex phenomenon, as well to for comparing cross-case characteristics and processes. They are easy instruments for identifying common trends across separate indicators, enable the identification of the main trends, and identify what can be elusive issues. However, because composite indicators create “big pictures” of a phenomenon, they could lead users to draw overly simplistic conclusions. Hence, composite indicators in this Section have been used together with qualitative information in a process of triangulation.

9.3 Results

9.3.1. Elements that influence social innovation

To investigate the elements that influence the emergence of social innovations composite indicators were developed which merge the following sub-dimensions of the influencing factors: “trigger and social needs”, “perceived opportunities and threats”, and “agency” (Secco et al., 2019; 4.3) as shown in Figure 23 and Table 17. A full list of the values of the composite indicators which have been developed is provided in Table 20.

Figure 23. Selected indicators to build composite indicators for the dimension of influencing factors (Source: Section authors based upon Secco *et al.*, 2019; D4.3).

Table 17. Name, code, and range of the selected indicators for the composite indicators on influencing factors

Sub-dimension	Code	Indicator label	Value Range
Trigger and social needs	Aa1	Trigger width	[0-1]
Trigger and social needs	Aa2	Needs tackled by the Social Innovation idea	[0-1]
Trigger and social needs	Aa4	Consistency of the Social Innovation initiative with European societal challenges	[0-1]

Perceived opportunities and threats	Ba1	Perceived Opportunities and Threats (POT)	[0-1]
Perceived opportunities and threats	Ba2	Role of supportive policies for sustaining the results of the Social Innovation initiative	[0-1]
Perceived opportunities and threats	Ba3	Consistency of Social Innovation initiative with issues of governance	[0-1]
Agency	Ca2	Innovativeness of the Social Innovation idea in the territory	[0-1]
Agency	Cb1	Attractiveness of the leadership	[0-1]
Agency	Cc1	Perceptions of Transformers of the resilience of Innovators and Followers	[0-1]
Agency	Cd1	Innovators and Followers capabilities to develop the Social Innovation initiative	[0-1]
Agency	Da1	Role of newcomers in the Social Innovation process	[0-1]
Agency	Da2	Perception of Social Innovation actors of the contribution of external helpers to the results of the Social Innovation initiative	[0-1]
Agency	Ea7	Education level within the Social Innovation network	[0-1]

(Source: Section authors).

Based upon the results of the composite indicators (Figure 24), the Case Studies can be divided into two categories, as follows:

- i) Trigger and needs-driven cases (i.e. WOM, VAZ, LUM, FIN, CAR and HAW) are those in which the value of the composite indicator for this sub-dimension prevails over the others. In these cases, the emergence of the social innovation idea was stimulated by a reaction to the collective needs and to the trigger.
- ii) Agency-driven cases (i.e. SEA, ADF, DAI, LAG and REV) are those in which the value of the composite indicator for the sub-dimension agency prevails over the others. In these case studies, agency has determined the emergence of the social innovation idea. The sub-dimension of perceived opportunities and threats never prevails over the other two sub-dimensions, meaning that it remains as a background determinant of the emergence of the social innovation idea. Values of this composite indicator are around the mean value in all case studies, except for HAW case in which it seems that perceived opportunities and threats play a minor role in the emergence of the social innovation idea.

Factors Influencing Emergence of Social Innovation

Figure 24. Comparison of composite indicators for the sub-dimensions of influencing factors (Source: Section authors).

Apart from the values of the composite indicators presented above, some observations can be made on the influencing factors of social innovation based upon the evidence in the Individual Case Study Reports.

Regarding **agency**, findings from the case studies shows that civic engagement is the central theme of social innovation. It is primarily a group of committed citizens, small in number, who are supported by concerned scientists and committed consultants who engage in the cause and get things done (i.e. cases LUM, VAZ, REV, FLE and CRO). All cases have in common a focus on civic engagement as their dominant form of viability. Therefore, a conclusion is that civic engagement, to different degrees, is the leitmotif through all the social innovation initiatives over their life cycle.

With regard to **context**, evidence from the case studies shows that the framework of the constitutional and institutional rules leverages social innovation.

- Constitutional rules are long-term in nature. They embody values and norms that are broadly accepted in society. They are the vantage point from which institutional rules can be changed and are linked to cultural norms and habits. In many cases, a political shift towards decentralisation, devolution, and the empowerment of local communities' acts as an important driver (i.e. cases CAR, LAG, ADF and WOM).
- Institutional rules pertain to sectoral and territorial policy making and governance. Discussion of changes that result from social innovation usually refers to institutional changes. Example in the case studies are the ways in which the healthcare and social care sector is integrated and makes use of green care farms in cases WOM and CAR, the ways and means of disaster prevention in the ADF case, and in the community-based forest management in LAG case.

With regard to the institutional context, aspects of governance appear to be factors of significant influence as early as at the trigger stage of a social innovation. The HAW case mirrors the CAP policy context. There are CAP measures HAW could have applied to, e.g. measures supporting agricultural production (pillar 1; pillar 2 measures e.g. agri-environmental scheme) and more specifically RDP measures related to cooperation among actors (e.g. M16 of the RDP). However, the HAW case study does not participate in area-based CAP measures due to its farm size as well as the relatively high

bureaucratic burden in relation to the respective amount of support. There are no specific formal rules and formal policies in Austria yet, which specifically address CSA.

In contrast, the well-functioning governance which was reported in VAZ case may reflect the value system of Catholic young people from which the case emerged.

The Tunisian and Moroccan initiatives (i.e. cases DAI and NWF) took shape as a project implemented by the FAO, promoted, and systematically supported by the government. In the case of DAI, the Social Innovation project was supported by the Ministry of Agriculture, Water Resources and Fishery/MARHP and the regional Livestock and Pasture Offices/OEP, in partnership with the cooperative producer organisations (OP). In the case of NWF support was from the Ministry of Agriculture and Hydrological Resources and the central Forest district administration in collaboration of the forest district of the two Governates (Béja and Jendouba). Support coming from sectoral self-organised or intermediary structures (i.e. cases HAW, FIN and SEA) cannot compensate for the absence of political encouragement or support. Encouragement from at least local or municipal leaders seems to be of significant value. A mix of policy incentives and enabling governance is the most effective, although the bureaucracy and controls which can be associated seem to increase with the number of regulatory, financial, informational, and networking support systems.

9.3.2. Reconfiguring process

Preliminary actions led by agents within a favourable context led to a process of reconfiguring, i.e. a change in “social practices”, which in turn leads to a reconfigured situation in which new networks, attitudes, and governance arrangements appear in different combinations. To investigate the reconfiguring and reconfigured social practices, composite indicators were prepared in three sub-dimensions: “new networks”, “new attitudes”, and “new governance arrangements” (Secco *et al.*, 2019; 4.3). The structure of the composite indicators and of the index of reconfiguring is shown in Figure 25 and

Table 18, and the results in Figure 26 and Figure 27.

Figure 25. Indicators selected as components of composite indicators for the dimension of reconfiguring process (Source: Section authors based upon Secco *et al.*, 2019; 4.3).

Table 18. Name, code, and range of the selected indicators for the composite indicators on reconfiguring process

Sub-dimension	Code	Indicator Label	Value Range
New networks	Ea4	Reputational power in the core group of the Social Innovation network	[0-1]
New networks	Ea10	New relationships within the Social Innovation network	[0-1]
New networks	OldEa11	Social Innovation network internal efficiency during the Social Innovation process	[0-1]
New networks	Ea12	Level of internal trust in the Social Innovation network	[0-1]
New networks	F3	Change in the collaborative relationships between the actors of the Social Innovation process	[0-1]
New networks	F11	Change in the collaborative relationships thanks to the Social Innovation initiative	[0-1]
New attitudes	Ca1	Attractiveness of the Social Innovation idea	[0-1]
New attitudes	Ea1	Level of attendance to the Social Innovation process meetings	[0-1]
New attitudes	Db3	Expertise motivating the engagement of Social Innovation actors	[0-1]
New attitudes	Eb1	Level of pro-action of Transformers during the Social Innovation process	[0-1]
New governance arrangements	Ec4	Level of trust in public institutions of the actors of the Social Innovation process	[0-1]
New governance arrangements	F4	Change in internal and external governance arrangements of the Social Innovation initiative as perceived by the actors of the Social Innovation process	[0-1]

(Source: Section authors).

In Figure 26, the results show that the highest degree of reconfiguring of social practices was observed in the WOM and DAI case studies, followed by LAG and REV cases, and then by VAZ case. All these cases have values above the mean value. The case CAR displays a value close to the mean, and ADF, LUM, SEA and FIN cases are at levels below the mean.

Reconfiguring Process of Social Innovation

Figure 26. Results of the composite indicator on the reconfiguring process of social innovation (Source: Section authors).

Figure 27 shows the types of social practices that have been reconfigured into “new networks”, “new attitudes” and “new governance arrangements” across the cases.

Factors Determining Process of Reconfiguring of Social Practices

Figure 27. Comparison of composite indicators for the sub-dimensions of reconfiguring process (Source: Section authors).¹²

¹² Value of indicator “New Attitude” for HAW case study does not display due to data not available.

In several cases (i.e. WOM, SEA, ADF, LUM, FIN, DAI, LAG, FLE, NWF, VIL and REV) the prevailing reconfigured social practices are “new attitudes”. In only two (i.e. cases CAR and REV) was the reconfiguring of “new governance arrangements”. Data about this aspect are missing from the HAW case. CAR is the only case in which reconfiguring of “new governance arrangements” prevails. “New networks” prevail as a social practice in VAZ and HAW cases. These results appear to contradict the analysis reported in Section 5, Table 4, which shows that “new networks” is the prevailing sub-dimension over all others. This mismatch is explained by the nature of the indicator used in Section 5 (i.e. SIR3), which is qualitative and perception-based, whereas the composite indicators used in this Section are built on different indicators and sub-dimensions.

The relevant qualitative information shows that new governance arrangements have been observed in most of the SIMRA cases. These are at the level of institutional rules, regardless of whether they apply to the local level without scaling out (i.e. in cases HAW, LUM, FIN, SEA, VAZ, CAR, REV and ARG), or if scaled to a regional or national level (i.e. in cases ADF, WOM, DAI, FAS, HER, FLE and NWF). According to the qualitative information, the capability to reconfigure governance arrangements is accompanied by a higher degree of public interference. Such interference implies policy support but with associated tighter control systems and administrative restrictions. Social innovation initiatives can compensate, in part, for the absence of public backing with the support of like-minded networks (i.e. in cases HAW and FIN), or with market demand for their services or products (i.e. in cases HAW, SEA, ARG, WOM and HER). Initiatives which rely on civic engagement over the long term (i.e. in cases ADF, VAZ and FAS) will always depend upon public recognition of the services they provide for common public well-being, and public co-funding.

Co-operatives, associations, and community development enterprises provide shells that enable social innovation initiatives to act and mature according to their own rules. They shield the individual actors from the complexities of government negotiations while at the same time being acknowledged officially as a partner providing services of common interest (i.e. cases DAI, LAG, WOM, CAR, HER and ARG). The FAS and SEA cases have not reached that state, however the promoters of SEA plan to transform the project into a co-operative. Nudged by the legislative framework and European Social Fund (ESF) funding opportunities, WOM case founded the social co-operative “Learning, growing, living with women”, coordinating childcare on farms across the entire Province of Bolzano, Italy.

Different countries have different traditions of (self-) governance, and therefore the legal form of a co-operative is not the same everywhere. Entrepreneurial shells, such as the Scottish Lochcarron Community Development Company in the LAG case, and the Community Development Trusts of BRA and HUN case fulfil similar functions to co-operatives but in different institutional arrangements.

There appears to be a renaissance of co-operatives in the realm of social innovation. These may be in the organisational form of the initiative itself (i.e. cases FIN, REV and DAI), or within the framework of a governance arrangement encompassing several social innovation initiatives of the same type, protecting the initiatives on the outside and enabling the growth and development of their member initiatives (i.e. cases WOM and HER). In certain countries other legal forms, such as local community development companies and trusts (i.e. case LAG), and first and second tier associations (i.e. cases ADF and CAR) have roles of protecting and enabling their members with respect to social innovation.

9.3.3. Impacts of social innovation

Impacts are derived from the cumulative outcomes and their broader effects, i.e. including the indirect beneficiaries of the project. Typically, they manifest as long-term changes which can be intended or unintended, positive, or negative, producing new routines, rules, and institutions across the entire local community and society. These are changes of state within the context of the system (Secco *et al.*, 2019; 4.3). The structure of the index of the impacts is shown in Figure 28 and Table 19.

Figure 28. Indicators selected as components of the index of impacts of social innovation (Source: Section authors based upon Secco *et al.*, 2019; 4.3).

Table 19. Name, code, and range of the selected indicators for the composite indicators of impacts of social innovation

Code	Indicator label	Value Range
13	Proportion of marginalisation problems improved by the Social Innovation initiative, as perceived by stakeholders	[0-1]
14	Proportion of the number of impacts of the Social Innovation initiative in the four domains which were positive, according to the stakeholders	[0-1]
16	Level of effects of the Social Innovation initiative in the four domains according to the actors	[0-1]
17	Level of effects of the Social Innovation initiative inside the territory in the four domains according to the actors	[0-1]
18	Level of effects of the Social Innovation initiative outside the territory in the four domains according to the actors	[0-1]
111	Perceptions of actors of the level of improvement in European societal challenges due to the Social Innovation initiative	[0-1]

(Source: Section authors).

Overall, the values of the index for impacts are high for the Case Studies (Figure 29). Cases with the highest values are WOM and CAR cases (0,84 the highest), followed by DAI, LAG, and REV cases. All of them have values above the average. FIN, VAZ, and ADF cases have values slightly below the average, and SEA, LUM and HAW cases have the lowest value (0,59).

Figure 29. Results of the composite index on impacts of the 11 Type A Case Study social innovations (Source: Section authors).

Combining values of the composite indicators with qualitative information confirms that the common denominator of all social innovation initiatives is that they seek to produce benefits for the community. This is particularly clear in the cases of providers of care services (i.e. cases CAR, WOM and FAS), disaster prevention and management (i.e. case ADF), and in the provision of better environmental services to rural villages (i.e. case VIL). Other social innovation initiatives operate more deeply within local society. They focus on the long-term liveability of a specific territory within a globalising environment, such as the initiatives in cases of VAZ and LUM, which are tackling prospects of rural people in a rural province with a strong focus on farming, the food sector and, in the case of FLE, manufacturing value chains. The evidence from the cases studied shows that the voices of farmers and foresters, in their capacity as actors in their own development, are heard increasingly. Examples in the case studies are GUA where they are empowering themselves and taking responsibility for their own future; LAG case, and the forest commons cases SLC and SKL, through ways and means of common pool resource management. Similar evidence is available in relation to other sectors of communities, such as the revitalisation of a rural village protected as a cultural heritage site (i.e. case REV); acting to reverse trends of depopulation in rural areas (i.e. case CRO); and in the development of a cooperative-run information centre for a nuclear energy-free society (i.e. case FIN).

A third group of Case Studies relates to social innovation initiatives which seek to create added value through fostering local or regional value chains. The argument for common benefit lies in the endeavour to improve the living conditions for economic actors whose contribution to society is deemed important in the sense that their disappearance would cause common harm. This is apparent for cases of a small-scale fishery (i.e. case SEA), small-scale biodynamic agriculture (i.e. cases HAW and HER), small dairy and oil producers cooperating in producer organisations (i.e. case DAI), in a cooperative arrangement (i.e. case ARG), and microenterprises in the forestry sector (i.e. case NWF). When dealing with Trusts (i.e. cases BRA and HUN), community projects are the economic beneficiaries of the community companies.

9.3.4. Replication of social innovation

Once the social innovation project(s) have been implemented, the first outcomes (and/or long-term impacts) have appeared, the lessons learned start to spread, and the innovation can be replicated or proposed in other territories with local adjustments. Feedback loops, multiplier effects and critical effects can be observed in the phase of learning processes. This is the key dimension of the “learning processes” (Secco *et al.*, 2019; 4.3).

The structure of the replication index is represented in Figure 30. For the purposes of interpretation, a higher value in the replication index could mean that there is a higher possibility that the social innovation can be replicated in other areas. Therefore, it could be a role model for other initiatives tackling similar needs and in similar contexts.

Figure 30. Selected indicators for building the composite indicator for replication and learning process. (Source: Section authors, based upon Secco *et al.*, 2019; 4.3).

Table 20. Name, code, and range of the selected indicators for the composite indicators on replication of social innovation

Code	Indicator label	Value Range
Hb1	Deadweight effects of the Social Innovation initiative in the territory	[0-1]
Hb2	Substitution effects of the Social Innovation initiative on other actors	[0-1]
Hb3	Displacement effects of the Social Innovation initiative outside the territory	[0-1]

(Source: Section authors).

Based on the results, as presented in Figure 31, the highest values for replication were for the REV and VAZ case, followed by LAG, CAR, and DAI cases, implying that the social innovation initiative has more potential to be replicated or proposed with adjustments in other territories than other initiatives. The values for cases WOM and SEA are in line with the mean value of the eleven Type A cases, while ADF and FIN are slightly below the mean. The LUM and HAW cases have the lowest values for replication.

Figure 31. Results of the composite indicator on replication and learning process (Source: Section authors)

The values for replication are supported by qualitative information on the factors that are likely to nurture the replication of social innovation. These have been obtained from the individual Case Study Reports which report several characteristics of the replication process across the cases.

Overall, the resilience and dynamism of cooperation systems benefit from actor configurations called “triads of actors”, explained below:

- (i) a trusted core of key actors of the social innovation initiative, who are the core group and the network.
- (ii) an intermediary support structure, which is a “third sector agency or structure” that provides support to the social innovation initiative(s). This may be in the form of funding for networking, training, knowledge provision, coaching, and lobbying. It may have only one function but often it is a combination of these functions. Intermediary support structures can be represented by mature, resourceful networks and umbrella organisations (i.e. cases LAG, CAR, ADF LUM, VAZ, HER FLE and WOM) or by transitional arrangements such as vocational schools, dialogue forums, and meeting spaces (i.e. cases VAZ and SEA), and again in ADF and WOM cases. The weakest form of intermediary structure is the networks of NGOs, which fill a gap where there is a lack of suitable support structures in the area (i.e. cases FIN, SEA and HAW). As is often typical for developing countries, international development organisations, such as the FAO, can play a role as an intermediary support structure, acting together with public service providers in DAI, ARG and NWF cases.
- (iii) the shadow of hierarchy, which means the presence and active inclusion of public partners. Symbolically, this gives the social innovation initiative the “blessing” of the authorities. It provides the decisions made by the initiative or the intermediary support structure (if public partners are included) with the necessary legal backing and creditworthiness. In return, the public sector is relieved of certain tasks which are better undertaken by other actors and can, at least in part, transfer liabilities which are caused by problems in the daily operations. There are several degrees of intensity or influence, ranging from passive involvement in long-term contractual relationships to legally binding engagements in public-private-civic governance arrangements. This provides

the social initiative protection and space to grow for, but it can also reduce its room for its manoeuvre.

The cases show that every social innovation initiative has its own lifespan, but there is always an end. There is no 'endless innovation cycle'. However, the end point may in turn become the starting point for something new. The lifespan of the SIMRA Case Studies ranged from four years (i.e. case SEA) to 35 years (i.e. case LUM). The initiative LUM is trying to continue operating with a wider territorial mandate, as the old innovation cycle appears to have come to an end with the formation of a grouping of the eight municipalities. The long-lasting initiative FLE has also faced undergoing new negotiations and rearrangements. The innovation cycles of WOM case (which has been in operation for 14 years) and ADF case (in operation for 33 years) seem to have either come to an end or be close to their end.

Innovation cycles in other case studies are in earlier stages of evolution. Examples are: i) the local heritage initiative of REV case (operating for 6 years), in which there are numerous ideas and projects at the planning stage; ii) the community-based agriculture case of HAW; iii) the Tunisian dairy producers organisations (i.e. case DAI); and iv) the young farmers exploring their future prospects in VAZ who are seeking to find a reliable pathway for growth or stabilisation.

In the case of SEA, the dependency of the Greek fishermen on Greenpeace, their lack of self-organisation, the distance to consumers, and the non-involvement of public actors' points towards the need to relaunch the initiative which otherwise is still fragile in its structure.

Every initiative operates at its own speed. After 12 years, FIN case is in its third attempt to become established, which compares to the relatively advanced state of the LAG case (11 years), albeit the latter has more potential for growth and differentiation from its starting point. The case of CAR in The Netherlands appears to be a relevant case of innovation as, after 17 years, it still experimenting and diversifying activities on the farm.

After some time, social innovation initiatives tend to become institutionalised either: i) due to intersection of the public domain and the civil society (as experienced with LUM and FLE cases, and may become true in VAZ case); ii) as parts of the social economy with its mix of public regulation and financing, and market mechanisms (i.e. cases WOM and CAR); iii) putting their emphasis on the private sector with some civic engagement in and around the enterprise or value chain (i.e. cases NWF, DAI and HAW); or, iv) perpetuating their services on the basis of strong and regular voluntary involvement (i.e. cases ADF and LAG). Each form of viability implies specific requirements regarding the political and institutional environment. As the SIMRA Case Studies have been analysed at different stages in their life cycles, and their limited number, it is difficult to derive generic conclusions, but they provide evidence upon which to explore the matter more systematically in further research.

Table 21. Value of composite indicators and indexes

Composite indicator/Index label	WOM	SEA	ADF	VAZ	LUM	FIN	CAR	HAW	DAI	LAG	REV	Mean value
Index on impacts of social innovation	0.84	0.63	0.67	0.68	0.62	0.68	0.82	0.59	0.78	0.77	0.75	0.71
Replication	0.75	0.76	0.71	0.83	0.64	0.71	0.78	0.57	0.78	0.80	0.85	0.74
Index on influencing factors of social innovation	0.50	0.43	0.38	0.52	0.58	0.47	0.48	0.35	0.55	0.49	0.58	0.48
Trigger and social needs	0.68	0.38	0.30	0.61	0.84	0.76	0.55	0.51	0.51	0.43	0.56	0.56
Context	0.39	0.30	0.36	0.42	0.44	0.24	0.39	0.03	0.55	0.44	0.42	0.36
Agency	0.48	0.48	0.41	0.52	0.53	0.45	0.50	0.42	0.56	0.53	0.66	0.50
Weighted average influencing factors	0.52	0.39	0.36	0.52	0.61	0.48	0.48	0.32	0.54	0.47	0.55	0.47
New networks	0.64	0.50	0.61	0.64	0.63	0.43	0.63	0.44	0.68	0.77	0.51	0.59
New attitudes	0.94	0.74	0.72	0.65	0.73	0.72	0.52	NA	0.84	0.83	0.76	0.74
New governance arrangements	0.83	NA	0.33	NA	0.00	0.17	0.83	NA	0.67	NA	0.83	0.52
Weighted average reconfiguring (excluding perception)	0.80	0.62	0.56	0.65	0.45	0.44	0.66	0.44	0.73	0.80	0.70	0.62
Perception of reconfiguring	0.64	0.54	0.54	0.78	0.72	0.61	0.69	0.62	0.86	0.77	0.82	0.69

(Source: Section authors).

10. Conclusions

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10.1 Results from the Workshop with the SIMRA Social Innovation Think Tank

The strategy of the SIMRA project builds on a trans-disciplinary approach and the involvement of different types of experts and stakeholders in the development of the project. This approach aims to develop and maintain a systematic knowledge exchange and build learning processes over the duration of the project and beyond. The aims of the second meeting with the Social Innovation Think Tank (Aberdeen, United Kingdom, 14 to 17 October 2019) were threefold: a) feedback on, and confirm, the formulation of the key findings; b) provide a reality check based on the experience of the members of the Social Innovation Think Tank; c) help with the formulation of recommendations.

Three groups of stakeholders were involved in the workshop:

- Type 1: Key organisations and actors in rural development, agriculture, and forestry at international, regional, and national levels (in the European Union Member States, associated, and non-EU countries) including qualified academic experts.
- Type 2: Stakeholders directly linked to Case Studies (CSs) and innovation actions (IAs) brought together in under Work Packages 2 (Theoretical and operational frameworks), 3 (collecting examples of social innovation and selecting Case Studies), 5 (Case Study assessment), and 7 (Innovation Actions).
- Type 3: Other local and regional stakeholders, drawn from outside the Case Study areas, identified through institutions such as the Rural Development Helpdesk, and a snowball approach starting from the key stakeholders already involved in the project, and other tools.

Project partners involved in Work Packages 5, 6, 7 and 8 were also present. In total, 30 people attended the workshop.

A World Café participatory approach was adopted for the consultation with the Social Innovation Think Tank and project partners specifically in relation to the cross-case analysis (Task 5.4). From the interactive involvement of stakeholders in presenting the results from Task 5.4, their views, experiences, and perceptions of social innovations have been integrated into the design and implementation of the cross-case analysis.

The World Café was structured into three discussion tables and three rounds of discussion, lasting two hours overall. A general introduction was followed by a presentation and discussion of key findings related to the theme of enquiry. Key findings were displayed on posters (Appendix 1) and clustered into three discussion tables. These were, Table 1 - influencing factors and impacts of social innovation; Table 2 - reconfiguring process and models of development of social innovations; and Table 3 - policies and steps towards recommendations formulation. The results of the consultation process with the Social Innovation Think Tank are presented below, by theme of enquiry and include suggestions from the roundtable discussions, summarized as key messages.

10.2 Themes of Enquiry

The main feedback on the key findings is presented below by theme of enquiry

10.2.1 Theme of Enquiry 1 - Influencing factors of social innovation

The Social Innovation Think Tank suggested improvements to specifying the relationship between the idea and the related needs. The idea should always respond to a need to be relevant. Social Innovation

finds the opportunity to emerge and develop where there is a problem or need to be resolved. The role of Social Innovation initiatives is to showcase and prove the viability of novel solutions.

Some members of the Social Innovation Think Tank suggested that it would be better to specify the existing interactions between trigger, need, and contextual factors as conditions that enhance social innovation. Members also made observations on the origins of the social innovation idea, emphasising that for an idea to become a social innovation the engagement and involvement of local people is necessary. If the idea comes from external actors, then these actors must be able to forge ties with the local inhabitants.

The Social Innovation Think Tank also highlighted that a better understanding of the contextual factors is necessary; the same factor can be hindering or enabling depending on the context. Therefore, enabling and hindering factors could be reformulated as “objective” (natural/contextual) factors and assessed by means of a scale (e.g. from 0 to 10) according to what they are enabling or hindering. Further enabling factors which could be considered are: a) the presence of a public good/bad and the dilemma of how to manage the situation enhances the emergence of a social innovation to solve it, and b) intergenerational, legacy values, and sense of belonging. The relationship between risk aversion and the existing policy framework as a hindering factor for social innovation was also noted.

10.2.2 Theme of Enquiry 2 - Reconfiguration of social practices

Regarding the theme of the reconfiguration of social practices, the following feedback was collected in relation to the attitudes of the actors, size of network, and duration of the process.

With regard to trust, the following observations were made. A high level of trust is very important, but “wider” trust is more important. Less trust could cause more tension in the wider network than would be visible in the results but, eventually, the impact of those tensions can be positive. A lack of trust creates polarisation, tension, and division and it is present when the process splits groups in two. In larger initiatives, the collaboration is more complex, which is why greater trust is necessary, and trust between single actors is not the same as trust between organisations. Finally, it is important to consider leadership in the generation of trust, and the role of facilitators or mentors amongst the actors.

Regarding tensions, they can be positive if they translate into open discussion (for example, between developers and conservative groups), which could help with development of the initiative. It may be more appropriate to refer to “resistance” (lack of awareness, difference of opinion) rather than tension.

Concerning the ideal size of the networks of social innovation, it was observed that larger networks require more effort. The growing of the initiative from small partnerships to larger groups can mean a loss of focus. However, the effectiveness of larger networks depends on their context and the definition of “effectiveness”.

Finally, regarding the duration of the process, the reconfiguring is usually not clearly defined temporarily, and it is very difficult to define when it starts.

10.2.3 Theme of Enquiry 3 - Impacts of Social Innovation

The members of the Social Innovation Think Tank suggested clarifying the limits of impact evaluation, stressing that the social innovation initiatives studied in SIMRA might be too small or too recent to have a real impact on the territorial dimensions. Therefore, it may be more appropriate to talk about outcomes, which relate to shorter time spans. Moreover, in discussion of impacts it is necessary to understand the links between the social innovation and the observed outputs and impacts.

A further suggestion was to reflect upon how impacts are interdependent between each other, thus stressing the need to develop an approach that can identify chains of impacts to be tested in selected case studies.

In general, all the impacts presented were considered to be very positive. Discussion considered the extent to which social innovation initiatives create trade-offs which are not always positive and not for everybody. It would also be appropriate to consider the negative impacts of Social Innovation that have rarely been studied or evaluated.

10.2.4 Theme of Enquiry 4 - Models of development and checking the hypothesis of diverging paths

The feedback from the Social Innovation Think Tank regarding this theme of enquiry regarded the term “divergence” in the concept of diverging paths. Feedback noted that more than just divergence matters, and that consideration should also be given to “conversion” as well as “diversion” in the processes of social innovation initiatives. It was suggested that the terminology could be reformulated to make it easier to understand (e.g. simpler labelling), and that combination of the models of development is difficult to follow. It was also observed that the dimension depth of change (either adaptive or transformative) is scale-driven, therefore analysis is needed to contextualise this dimension to clarify it.

The members of the Social Innovation Think Tank suggested analysing the involvement of the public sector more thoroughly as this is always a critical factor in social innovation regardless of its function and which can have negative effects.

10.2.5 Theme of Enquiry 5 – Policy implications

The members of the Social Innovation Think Tank made several observations about the role of policies regarding social innovation, emphasising that policy frames and structures emerging developments in different sectors and across sectors. Topics raised which are of particular importance are reported below.

Recognition and awareness of social innovation among policy makers and politicians: Recognition of social innovation is important. Many stakeholders have reported the lack of specific policies considering social innovation in marginalised rural areas, which resulted from too little awareness of the concept across the community of politicians and political experts. The lack of recognition of social innovation leads to protracted processes. There needs to be greater awareness and acknowledgement by policy actors of the need for reconfiguring government support and action which may require the integration of sectors, and subsequently funds. A step to take would be to plan workshops for politicians to demonstrate the added value of social innovation based upon the findings of the SIMRA project.

The members of the Social Innovation Think Tank emphasised the important roles of local authorities and policy makers. Municipalities, local councillors, and mayors consider themselves to be local agents of change, or as being “in charge”. In some cases, they perceive bottom-up social innovation initiatives as competition or a threat to their role. Discussion concluded that the quality of a local policy maker is determined by their ability to take a side without regard to partisan relationships with party politics, and that social innovation is neither apolitical nor post-political.

The members of the Social Innovation Think Tank highlighted the problem of labelling. When dealing with social innovation policies, the prevailing mindsets and government structures at all layers of society will have the tendency to absorb the “new” into the “old” moulds of policy making, even though the terminologies and labelling might sound “new”.

They stressed the importance of adopting strategic policies and policy principles for social innovation, using “tools” such as the Sustainable Development Goals at the national level. These provide a useful framework for deriving policies that support social innovation (e.g. in the European Union, and more widely), and an entry point for social innovation. They can be translated into cross-sectoral thematic strategies as well as into sectoral strategies.

At an abstract level, the Sustainable Development Goals are low risk for policy makers. However, the more they are broken down into operational objectives and policy measures, the more they become controversial in the political arena.

Discussion considered the recognition that change is needed amongst politicians and policy makers. Changes introduced in policy need to be complementary and supportive of each other, such as taxation of CO₂ alongside behavioural shifts amongst consumers. Starting at the local level will help to generate momentum. This can lead to a growing of public awareness as novel solutions emerge and become evident. This can lead to new forms of organisation emerging in response to political gaps or where politicians have become out of touch with groups of the population. Helpful principles of governance to justify policies that support social innovation at the local level are diversity and subsidiarity.

10.3 Recommendations for Successful Social Innovation

The recommendations derived from the cross-case analysis are intended to inform policy makers and decision makers at all levels, from local to regional to trans-national, about the key findings of the project, and to stimulate further development of social innovation initiatives within Marginalised Rural Areas. The recommendations primarily target government agencies, local public officials, and regional and local policy makers as well as agencies at the EU level. They are also relevant to other types of actors coming from private or third sector organisations as they also interface with social innovation experiences. Each of the recommendations presented in the following points is based upon the empirical findings obtained by cross-studying eleven Type A Case Studies in SIMRA in relation to the five themes of enquiry, as presented in this deliverable (Sections 4 to 8).

1. Decentralisation and self-determination

The Case Studies show that social innovation benefits from decentralised governance. A decentralised governance system is more likely to encourage local self-determination and self-organisation which is conducive to the emergence of social innovation. Public support, including funding, is more accessible if public governance structures operate on a spatial scale that is aligned to the area in which the social innovation initiative emerges. This increases the likelihood of personal networks and trusting relationships between civil society and public actors in a decentralised governance context.

Therefore, policies that are decentralisation and enable local self-determination which transfers power, tasks, and responsibilities down to the local level are recommended.

2. Coordinated and cross-sectorial structural policies

The analysis of the Case Studies has shown that social innovation benefits from cross-sectorial structural policies, particularly from territorial policy instruments. The ideal solution would be that policy instruments of all three types¹³ (sectoral, structural, and institutional) work alongside each other and cooperate well.

Therefore, a crucial task is to align and to coordinate structural policies both horizontally and across scales. This means that in local social innovation the structural policy dimension should be prioritised against the sectoral perspective.

3. Easy-to-use and ring-fenced funding

¹³ Sectoral policies regulate the particular thematic field (childcare or elderly care, environmental or heritage site protection); structural policies are mainly cross-sectorial and primarily directed towards cohesion objectives (such as local and regional development, employment and income distribution the provision of basic infrastructures and services); and, institutional policies provide the basic software for civic action, private business and public interventions, such as constitutional laws on basic rights, or legislation on cooperatives, on public-private partnerships and on other governance arrangements.

The analysis of the Case Studies has shown that even if structural provisions ensure policy integration between sectors, allowing the tackling of a broad variety of challenges in different types of territories, the over-specialization of policies may hinder supporting local social innovation. Moreover, policies that specifically target social innovation were found to be supportive. For example, LEADER programmes, cooperation measures under Rural Development Programmes, and emergent policies such as those to support Smart Villages, provide some focus on social innovation.

Therefore, it is necessary to provide leeway for local agencies (such as local action groups) to provide seed funding and help, which is not burdened by bureaucracy, for the unexpected creative moment to emerge, whether at its earliest stages or in phases of reorientation. Having surmounted those critical moments of transition, the initiative can access other sources of support in its phase of growth and consolidation. Moreover, unless funds are ring-fenced and facilitation is undertaken by skilled animateurs, the significant potential of social innovation will not be fully harnessed.

4. Role of municipalities

The Case Studies have shown the role of municipalities in sharing responsibilities in the promotion or support of social innovation initiatives. The size and proximity of municipalities to the realities of people's lives means that they are conducive to the convergence of participative and deliberative democracy. If their representatives (mayors, council members) recognise this potential, they may contribute greatly to the long-term stability and embedding of the initiative in the local society.

Promoting effective partnership with civil society actors is needed to empower in such a way as to enable the weak to become stronger and more resilient to withstand the shocks and adversities that affect their lives.

5. Intermediary support structures

The analysis has shown that the sustainability of social innovation depends, arguably, on reliable support structures. Social innovation initiatives on a growth path tend to spawn intermediary bodies which serve as protective shells and support providers for the individual initiatives. In other cases, public entities or mixed agencies take over the role of support structures. The bottom-up representation of social innovation initiatives in intermediary structures seems to favour policy dialogue and policy integration.

Therefore, intermediary support structures should be empowered and promoted. Local and regional development funds, organisations and agencies should be capable of fulfilling that role as the first contact point for local actors seeking orientation, advice, seed funding or exchanges with like-minded initiatives or projects.

6. Multilingualism and the support of professional experts

The Case Studies show that animation and capacity building is needed for stakeholders from different realms of the society (academics and workers, politicians and citizens, public officials, and private entrepreneurs) to get together and build partnerships.

Therefore, support structures of social innovation should be run by professional staff that are able to liaise with different types of stakeholders and create links between them. Potential instruments of relevance are local advisory bodies serving as hubs for support to local actors, promoting effective partnerships of the public with civil society actors.

7. Leadership and social capital

Social innovation appears to be influenced by leadership skills and collective action originating from effective cooperation. Investing in human and social capital is likely to increase the capacities of rural communities to make strategic choices and address contemporary challenges.

Therefore, the consolidation of social capital and the emergence of nuclei of leadership should be promoted and not be perceived as a threat to public administration action. Building effective strategies for bottom-up community action to help empower the local population and help them to satisfy currently unmet needs is essential to address these challenges.

8. Enabling cultural and policy environment

The cases showed that promoting an enabling policy environment is crucial for the emergence and growth potential of social innovation. This starts with a culture of tolerance and openness; encouragement grows with recognition and the availability of acknowledged forms of organisation and coordination (community companies, cooperatives, trusts and associations) of social innovation. The formative effects of political frameworks, policies, and formal rules on people's minds and beliefs should not be underestimated. They provide the societal texture regarding what is considered to be good from a moral perspective, desirable from a behavioural perspective, and beneficial from the practical perspective.

Policy makers should embrace the breadth of scope of social innovation in rural areas, recognising its potential to provide a cost-effective third sector component to accompany public and private provision of goods and services. It delivers in ways that go beyond the social realm to include activities which also support positive economic and environmental outcomes. Most importantly, social innovation is concerned with the liveliness and liveability of rural areas, and their capacity to shape their future.

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Appendix 1. Posters used to display findings during the workshop with the Social Innovation Think Tank (Aberdeen, UK, 16th October 2019)

Figure 32. Influencing factors of social innovation, Part 1

Figure 33. Influencing factors of social innovation, Part 2

Figure 34. Impacts of social innovation

Figure 35. Reconfiguring process and depth of change of social innovation

Figure 36. Models of development of social innovation

Figure 37. Supporting policies and policy impacts

Figure 38. Towards recommendations for the success of a social innovation

Appendix 2. List of indicators and values

Code	Indicator label	WOM	SEA	ADF	VAZ	LUM	FIN	CAR	HAW	DAI	LAG	REV	Mean Value	Min Value (data)	Max Value (data)	Related composite indicator in ch.9
Aa1	Trigger width	0.39	0.33	0.28	0.7	1	0.67	NA	0.06	0.17	0.33	0.33	0.43	0.06	1	Influencing – Trigger and social needs
Aa2	Needs tackled by the Social Innovation idea	1	0.5	0.4	0.66	0.8	0.8	NA	0.8	0.8	0.4	0.7	0.69	0.4	1	Influencing – Trigger and social needs
Aa4	Consistency of the Social Innovation initiative with European societal challenges	0.64	0.32	0.23	0.46	0.73	0.82	0.55	0.68	0.55	0.55	0.64	0.56	0.23	0.82	Influencing – Trigger and social needs
Ba1	Perceived Opportunities and Threats (POT)	0.05	0.2	0.09	0.13	0.12	0.08	0.17	0.03	0.12	0.1	0.1	0.11	0.03	0.2	Influencing - POT
Ba2	Role of supportive policies for sustaining the results of the Social Innovation initiative	0.56	0.27	0.7	0.47	0.64	0	0.48	0	0.82	0.61	0.67	0.47	0	0.82	Influencing -POT
Ba3	Consistency of Social Innovation initiative with issues of governance	0.57	0.43	0.29	0.67	0.57	0.64	0.52	0.06	0.71	0.6	0.5	0.51	0.06	0.71	Influencing - POT
Ca2	Innovativeness of the Social Innovation idea in the territory	0.89	0.89	NA	0.92	0.89	0.89	0.89	0.5	1	0.89	0.83	0.86	0.5	1	Influencing - Agency
Cb1	Attractiveness of the leadership	0	0	0	0.4	0.3	0	0	NA	0.17	0	0.67	0.15	0	0.67	Influencing - Agency
Cc1	Perceptions of Transformers of the resilience of Innovators and Followers	1	0.76	0.89	0.79	0.82	0.78	0.85	NA	0.7	0.56	0.74	0.79	0.56	1	Influencing - Agency
Cd1	Innovators and Followers capabilities to develop the Social Innovation initiative	0.06	1	0.1	0.06	0.14	0.05	0.2	NA	0.04	NA	NA	0.21	0.04	1	Influencing - Agency
Da1	Role of newcomers in the Social Innovation process	0	0	0	0.07	0.1	NA	NA	0.5	0	0	0	0.07	0	0.5	Influencing - Agency
Da2	Perception of Social Innovation actors of the contribution of external helpers to the results of the Social Innovation initiative	0.63	0.33	0.34	0.37	0.88	0.09	0.48	0.22	0.9	0.75	0.84	0.53	0.09	0.9	Influencing - Agency
Ea7	Education level within the Social Innovation network	0.25	0.29	1	0.71	0.73	0.67	0.5	0	1	0.5	NA	0.57	0	1	Influencing - Agency
Ca1	Attractiveness of the Social Innovation idea	1	1	0.67	0.88	1	1	0.67	NA	1	1	1	0.92	0.67	1	Reconfiguring – New attitudes
Ea1	Level of attendance to the SI process meetings	NA	0.53	0.9	0.73	0.93	0.83	0.78	NA	0.94	1	1	0.85	0.53	1	Reconfiguring – New attitudes
Db3	Expertise motivating the engagement of Social Innovation actors	1	0.67	0.33	0.44	0.7	0	0	NA	0.67	0.33	1	0.51	0	1	Reconfiguring – New attitudes
Ea4	Reputational power in the core group of the Social Innovation network	0.75	0.5	0.71	0.42	0.8	0.75	0.5	NA	0.75	NA	NA	0.65	0.42	0.8	Reconfiguring – New networks

Code	Indicator label	WOM	SEA	ADF	VAZ	LUM	FIN	CAR	HAW	DAI	LAG	REV	Mean Value	Min Value (data)	Max Value (data)	Related composite indicator in ch.9
Ea10	New relationships within the Social Innovation network	NA	0.64	0.21	0.9	0.65	0.72	NA	0.94	0.88	NA	0.79	0.72	0.21	0.94	Reconfiguring – New networks
Eb1	Level of pro-action of Transformers during the Social Innovation process	1	1	1	0.76	0.2	1	0.67	NA	0.83	1	0.67	0.75	0.04	1	Reconfiguring – New attitudes
SIR1	Individual perceptions of actors of the improvement in social practices due to the Social Innovation process	0.94	0.73	0.74	0.81	0.69	0.6	0.84	0.89	0.9	0.89	0.82	0.80	0.6	0.94	
SIR2	Collective perceptions of actors of the improvement in social practices due to the Social Innovation process	0.68	0.66	0.66	0.8	0.77	0.52	0.81	0.33	0.89	0.87	0.86	0.71	0.33	0.89	
SIR3	Perception of actors of the extent of the process of reconfiguration	0.31	0.23	0.23	0.73	0.7	0.72	0.42	0.63	0.78	0.54	0.78	0.55	0.23	0.78	
F3	Change in the collaborative relationships between the actors of the Social Innovation process	0.7	0.7	0.55	0.59	0.65	0.47	0.67	NA	0.72	NA	0.71	0.64	0.47	0.72	Reconfiguring – New networks
F11	Change in the collaborative relationships between the actors of the Social Innovation initiative	0.72	0.69	0.66	0.8	0.54	0.5	0.67	NA	0.7	NA	NA	0.66	0.5	0.8	Reconfiguring – New networks
OldEa11	SI network internal efficiency during the SI process	0.3	0.35	1	0.81	0.37	0.33	0.37	NA	0.23	NA	0.23	0.44	0.23	1	Reconfiguring – New networks
Ea12	SI network internal trust	0.83	0.77	0.93	0.87	0.84	0.81	0.86	0.72	0.81	0.78	0.89	0.83	0.72	0.93	Reconfiguring – New networks
OldEc4	Types of sanctions	NA	0.07	NA	0	NA	0	NA	0	0.71	1	0	0.25	0	1	
Ec4	Level of trust in public institutions of the actors of the Social Innovation process	NA	0.27	0.33	0.54	0.73	0.15	0.59	0.11	0.73	0.54	0.45	0.44	0.11	0.73	Reconfiguring – New governance arrangements
F4	Change in internal and external governance arrangements of the Social Innovation initiative as perceived by the actors of the Social Innovation process	0.83	NA	0.33	NA	0	0.17	0.83	0	0.67	NA	0.83	0.46	0	0.83	Reconfiguring – New governance arrangements
I10	Perceptions of actors of the level of improvement in governance aspects due to the Social Innovation initiative	0.88	0.71	0.56	0.63	0.71	0.33	1	0.33	0.78	0.58	0.8	0.66	0.33	1	
I3	Proportion of marginalisation problems improved by the Social Innovation initiative, as perceived by stakeholders	1	0	NA	0	0	1	1	NA	0.43	NA	0.71	0.52	0	1	Impacts

Code	Indicator label	WOM	SEA	ADF	VAZ	LUM	FIN	CAR	HAW	DAI	LAG	REV	Mean Value	Min Value (data)	Max Value (data)	Related composite indicator in ch.9
I4	Proportion of the number of impacts of the Social Innovation initiative in the four domains which were positive, according to the stakeholders	1	0.86	NA	1	1	0.83	0.67	0.88	0.97	0.97	0.67	0.89	0.67	1	Impacts
I6	Level of effects of the Social Innovation initiative in the four domains according to the actors	0.75	0.73	0.73	0.75	0.63	0.58	0.64	0.56	0.81	0.71	0.77	0.70	0.56	0.81	Impacts
I7	Level of effects of the Social Innovation initiative inside the territory in the four domains according to the actors	0.82	0.68	0.8	0.8	0.75	0.61	0.64	0.6	0.87	0.77	0.83	0.74	0.6	0.87	Impacts
I8	Level of effects of the Social Innovation initiative outside the territory in the four domains according to the actors	0.62	0.75	NA	0.7	0.5	0.55	NA	0.51	0.75	0.64	0.67	0.63	0.5	0.75	Impacts
I11	Perceptions of actors of the level of improvement in European societal challenges due to the Social Innovation initiative	0.82	0.71	0.6	0.9	0.75	0.89	0.98	0.63	0.88	0.92	0.82	0.81	0.6	0.98	Impacts
Hb1	Deadweight effects of the Social Innovation initiative in the territory	0.25	0.33	0.2	0.5	0	NA	0.33	0	0.33	0.5	NA	0.27	0	0.5	Replication
Hb2	Substitution effects of the Social Innovation initiative on other actors	1	0.94	0.93	1	0.92	0.42	1	0.7	1	0.9	0.69	0.86	0.42	1	Replication
Hb3	Displacement effects of the Social Innovation initiative outside the territory	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	Replication